

Inclusive Education and Classroom Practice in Secondary Education

Literature Review

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INTRODUCTION

This report contains an overview of the findings of the first phase of the Classroom and School Practice project focussing upon the **secondary level** of educational provision. This project has been a replication of the European Agency project that examined the primary level of education. The current project aims to reveal, analyse, describe and disseminate information about classroom practice in inclusive settings in secondary education in such a way that European teachers can implement inclusive practice on a wider scale in their classrooms.

The overall Classroom and School Practice project consisted of three study phases. In the first phase a literature review was conducted in the participating countries in order to identify the current state of the art in effective inclusive practice. In addition to country based literature reviews, an international (mainly American) literature review was also conducted. This part of the project addressed the question: which practices are proven to be effective in inclusive education? In the second phase, concrete examples of good practice were selected and described in a systematic way. In the final phase, exchanges between different countries were organised in such a way that transfer of knowledge and practice was maximized.

This report presents the information collected during this first study phase of the project: the literature review.

Review reports were received from 12 countries and they are all presented in this document. Of course these reports display considerable variation: some countries have an enormous amount of research information in the field, whilst in other countries the research tradition is less rich. As this study does *not* in any way involve comparing countries in terms of the state of the art of research into effective practice in inclusive settings, this variation is of no importance. The focus here is to identify and present the current body of knowledge on the issue in a way that is independent of any specific country.

In the next chapters the following issues will be expanded upon:

- The questions, goal and output of the Classroom and School Practice project (Chapter 1)
- The framework for the literature review study (Chapter 2)
- The methodology of the study (Chapter 3)
- The international literature review (Chapter 4)
- The European country focussed literature reviews (Chapter 5)

A European Agency project manager edited the literature review study, but different parts of this report (mainly Chapter 5) have been written by authors selected from the countries participating in the Classroom and School Practice project. These authors were National Co-ordinators of the European Agency, or 'guest writers', selected by the National Co-ordinators. In each section of Chapter 5, there is an indication of the author. For more contact information, please refer to the IECF web area on www.european-agency.org

This report forms a data source for the secondary school level Classroom and School Practice project. As previously stated, the aim of this study is to provide information from the literature available in the participating countries and also at an international level. The aim here is not to try and summarize the findings in relation to the overall Classroom and School Practice project. This synthesis is presented in the final summary project report published in 2004, which also includes information from the case studies and the exchanges of experts organised in 2003.

1 GOALS OF THE CLASSROOM AND SCHOOL PRACTICE PROJECT

The Classroom and School Practice project is thought to be of particular interest for the field of special needs education as it focuses directly on the *practical aspects* of special educational provision. As such, it has the potential to have great impact in the field, particularly for the main end user group of the European Agency's work: classroom teachers.

Two main issues have formed the basis for the project:

1. How can differences in the classroom be dealt with?
2. How can mainstream schools be equipped and organised in order to meet the needs of pupils with SEN?

The project has attempted to answer several questions about effective inclusive education. In the first instance, it is argued that an understanding of *what* works within inclusive settings is necessary. Furthermore, it is felt that a clearer understanding of *how* inclusive education works is needed. Thirdly, it is important to gain insight into *why* inclusive education is working i.e. the conditions for successful inclusion.

Different types of information output have provided answers to these questions. In the first stage in the project, the study activities resulted in this report: a literature-based description of the different models of inclusive education as well as an identification of the conditions necessary for the implementation of these models. As such, the what, how and why questions have been partly addressed through this systematic literature review.

However, the how and why questions have also been addressed through a description of a number of actual examples of inclusive practice. Finally, through visits to different locations where inclusive education is implemented, a more qualitative and broader understanding of what, how and why inclusion works has been achieved.

2 FRAMEWORK

Generally, it can be assumed that integration or inclusive education depends upon what teachers do in classrooms. The way in which teachers realise inclusion within their classrooms can take different forms. It is the goal of this study to describe these different approaches and to make this information available for others. Identifying various models of dealing with differences in classrooms - variously known as 'differentiation', 'multi-level instruction' as well as other terms - therefore forms the main task of this study. However, it should be clearly noted that the existence of different models of dealing with differences in classrooms depends not only on teacher factors, but also on the way in which schools organise their educational provision. This fact is particularly relevant for education within the secondary sector.

2.1 Classroom Practice and Teacher Factors

Inclusion largely depends on teachers' attitudes towards pupils with special educational needs (SEN) and on the resources available to them. In a number of studies, the attitude of teachers towards educating pupils with SENs has been put forward as a decisive factor in making schools more inclusive. If mainstream teachers do not accept the education of these pupils as an integral part of their role, they will try to ensure that someone else (often the specialist teacher) takes responsibility for these pupils and they will organise covert segregation in the school (e.g. the special class).

The different types of resources available for teachers includes not only teaching methods and materials, but also time available for instruction and the knowledge and skills teachers have acquired through training and experience. All these resources can be drawn upon when dealing with differences in classrooms.

Teaching pupils with SEN in the mainstream classroom invariably involves deviation from the 'regular' programme. Teachers are confronted with the question of how to educate these pupils. Pupils with SEN may require more instruction time or other learning methods and professional knowledge. In that case, teachers will feel the need for more time, materials and knowledge. Generally, this can be achieved in two ways: by an increase in resources (more time allocated to teachers) or by re-arranging available resources (different uses of available time).

Increasing available time (e.g. through the use of educational assistants) or enhancing teachers' professional knowledge (e.g. consultation teams) are ways of increasing the necessary resources for inclusive education, but teachers may also need to re-arrange resources specifically related to the pupils in the classroom. Teachers can, for example, encourage above-average pupils to work more independently, to work with ICT tools and to help each other, so that more teaching time is left for pupils with SEN.

To realise the inclusion of these pupils in mainstream education, teachers will try to enhance the level of resources and differentiate between pupils with respect to the amount and type of resources available to them. The argument is that the successful inclusion of pupils with SEN largely depends on the availability of resources in the

mainstream classroom, but also on the way teachers differentiate the resources between pupils.

A final important issue at the teacher and classroom level is a teacher's sensitivity and skill in relation to enhancing significant social relationships between pupils. For pupils with SEN - and their parents - in particular, meaningful interactions with non-SEN peers are of the utmost importance. The teacher requires the right attitude, but also needs a good understanding of how to develop these interactions and relationships.

In summary, teachers' attitudes, available instruction time, the knowledge and skills of teachers, teaching methods and materials seem to be important pre-requisites for successful special needs education within mainstream settings.

2.2 School Factors

It is clear that providing for pupils with SEN is not only a question of necessary resources at the classroom level. It should be recognised that the organisational structure at the school level also determines the amount and type of resources teachers can use in teaching pupils with SEN.

In relation to secondary schools with a variety of subjects and usually with subject-specific teachers, the organisation of how to deal with pupils with SEN is particularly relevant and challenging. On the basis of earlier studies, it is generally accepted that the inclusion of pupils with SEN is very complex in secondary schools. In primary schools, the co-ordination and planning of support for pupils with SEN is already challenging; this was demonstrated in the European Agency project investigating classroom practices within primary education. In secondary education, there is an expectation that inclusion is even more challenging as educational provision is usually organised according to the different subjects of the curriculum and the number of teachers involved in delivering the curriculum is usually far higher.

Support can also be made available through external support services such as school advisory centres or specialist visiting support staff. In summary, the issues involved in organising inclusive education at the school level centre upon structures for providing special support within schools, the involvement of external special education services and the internal school structure. These are all conditions for the organisation and provision of support.

2.3 The Main Questions

Generally, it can be assumed that inclusive education depends on what teachers do in classrooms. The way in which teachers realise inclusion within the classroom can take different forms. It is the goal of this study to describe these different approaches and to make information on them more widely available for others. To identify various models of dealing with differences in classrooms forms the main task for this study. However, it should be clear that the existence of different models of dealing with differences in classrooms depends not only on teacher factors, but also on the way in which schools organise their educational provision. This is particularly the case within secondary schools.

3 APPROACH AND METHODOLOGY

The Inclusive Education and Classroom Practice in Secondary Education project consisted of three different stages.

During the first stage - the focus of this study report - systematic literature reviews were conducted. Through the description and analysis of European and other international literature, an attempt has been made to address the question of what works in inclusive settings. Different criteria were used for selecting articles, books and other documents for this stage of the study. These are discussed below. National Co-ordinators of most countries of the European Agency submitted reports that contained an overview of the existing literature in their languages and descriptions of current problems within the context of inclusive education in their countries.

Alongside the reports of the participating countries, a more general international literature review was conducted.

Within the second stage of the project, examples of good practice were selected, described and analysed. These examples are described in the *Country Reports* presented within the Inclusive Education and Classroom Practice in Secondary Education (IECP) web area: www.european-agency.org

In third and last stage of the project, a selection of examples of good practice in action were visited and evaluated. During this phase, exchanges of experts from participating countries were organised in order to maximize learning from other experiences and identify solutions for certain problems within the context of inclusive education. Every location selected was visited and described and the findings are also available through the *Expert Visit* reports in the IECP web area.

The remainder of this report presents the findings of the first stage of the project. Below the approach for the literature reviews is described in detail.

The goal of the overall literature review was to gather information about possible models of classroom practice in inclusive settings and the effects of these approaches on pupils with SEN or their peers. The European Agency project manager co-ordinated a literature review from an international perspective (see Chapter 4); the National Co-ordinators representing countries participating in the project were asked to conduct a literature review within their own country (Chapter 5).

National Co-ordinators were asked to collect all relevant information available from their own countries' perspective – either in an international language or in the country's own language, but always referring to the situation in that specific country. National Co-ordinators were asked to collect information (from articles, books, theses, reports etc), to describe the findings systematically and to write a synthesis of these findings.

The combined literature review was focused on the 'state of the art' of classroom practice in a given country. The central question was: *what works?*

The overview of available literature considered the following questions:

- What arrangements and factors within the context of the curriculum (classroom practice, teaching methods, educational organisation and so) are considered as essential for meeting the needs of pupils with SEN in mainstream classrooms?
- What is known about the outcomes of these approaches (at the pupil level)?

National Co-ordinators were asked to provide an overview of the existing findings from literature (research or evidence based opinion documents) in *their own country* (a national oriented review). It was stressed that only literature that referred to practice within their own country (in their own or another language) should be selected. The more international oriented review, completed by the European Agency project manager, provided a broader overview concerning the issue of classroom practice.

National Co-ordinators were also asked to provide an answer to the following two questions:

1. What are the main problems (at the levels of classroom practice, school organisation and teachers) in your country within mainstream classrooms that include pupils with SEN?
2. Which groups of pupils with SEN cause the most problems within mainstream settings and why?

It was agreed to select information that:

- Referred to findings after 1990
- Referred to secondary stages of education
- Referred to inclusive education, mainstreaming or integration
- Referred to pupils with SEN, disabilities or handicaps (a range of terms for special needs)
- Referred to classroom practice, curriculum, educational arrangements, teaching methods and so on
- Referred to achievements, outcomes, effects or output in terms of academic achievement (or cognitive ability), emotional outcomes (emotional development, self-esteem, self-concept, student attitudes) or social behaviour (social adjustment, social development, interpersonal relationship)
- Referred to situations within the National Co-ordinators' country only.

National Co-ordinators were asked to complete a form (based on a template used by the NFER, UK) for every specific document reviewed. This form is used in 'critical literature reviewing'. It is useful for systematically describing and processing information.

The form covered the following areas:

Author and title	Details of author and title of book, journal article etc.
Publication details	Details of publisher, place and date of publication.
Language	What language is the document written in?
Country of origin	What country did the publication originate from?
Type of research	Qualitative, quantitative, longitudinal study, literature review,

	discussion of research findings etc.
Methodology	Explanation/justification of the research rationale, design etc.
Sample	Population characteristics (type of SEN, size, age, geographical location, socio-economic factors, ethnic mix etc.) Sampling method employed, sample size, response rate.
Method of research	Type and quality of instruments used – questionnaires, interviews, observation etc.
Main findings	Summary of main findings/conclusions drawn from the research.
Evaluative commentary	Comments on the quality/limitations of the research: reliability of methods used? Quality of evidence? Bias? Findings of particular interest; implications for policy.

Synthesis reports were received from the 10 countries:

- Austria
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- The Netherlands
- Norway
- Spain
- Sweden
- Switzerland
- United Kingdom.

Each synthesis report is presented in Chapter 5. From Iceland and Luxemburg, a selection of literature reviews were received and these are included in the Appendix section of this report. In total, 12 countries provided documentation for this part of the project.

It should be noted that due to the variety of terms and descriptors evident in the studies reviewed, the international and country based literatures reviews in Chapters 4 and 5 are presented using the terms and phrases (relating to pupils/students, SEN and/or disability, programmes/approaches etc) that have been used by the authors of each specific synthesis report. In addition, the referencing styles and formats used by authors have been retained in synthesis reports presented in Chapter 5. Full publication details for all articles considered by authors are presented in the Appendix section.

4 THE INTERNATIONAL LITERATURE REVIEW

Charissa J.F. Van Wijk and Cor J.W. Meijer

4.1 Introduction

In order to address the questions posed in the Classroom Practice project, several studies were located by searching the ERIC database. An additional search was completed in the Academic Search Elite database, using the EBCO host. To be included in the search, studies had to meet three methodological criteria:

- The use of control groups
- Information about the sample such as age and type of special needs, disabilities, or handicap
- Information on the type and method of research.

The search descriptors used to locate information were directly based on the criteria for the literature reviews as described in Chapter 3. Initially, the following descriptors were used: secondary-education, high school, inclusive schools, mainstreaming, special needs, classroom techniques and curriculum development, teaching methods.

To determine the possible effects on emotional development, the following descriptors were used: self-concept, self esteem, student attitudes and emotional development. To determine the effects on social behaviour: social networks, social behaviour, social integration, social status, interpersonal communication, social adjustment, social development, interpersonal relationships and to determine the effects on academic achievement: cognitive ability and academic achievement were used as descriptors.

Since the descriptors regarding emotional, social and academic outcomes were too specific, they limited the outcomes of the search to a large extent. It was therefore decided to delete these descriptors.

In addition, reference lists from identified studies were searched for additional sources.

'Critical literature review' forms were filled in for every document selected. The form consisted of the following categories: author and title, publication details, language, country of origin, type of research, methodology, sample, method of research, main findings, and evaluative commentary.

Over 200 studies were located by searching the databases. Many of these were excluded from the review because they did not meet the study criteria. Studies concerning the integration of bilingual or gifted students were not relevant for this search. The search showed that many of the studies detected contained qualitative data; many qualitative studies based on teachers' perceptions of effective classroom practices were identified.

After the screening process, a disappointing total of 7 studies were considered relevant for this review. It was decided to include 4 more articles that did not meet all criteria, but were considered to be of a supplemental value to the 7 evidence-based research studies. These studies are mostly based on teachers' perceptions and make use of interviews and observations.

4.2 Results

For the past decades various studies on the inclusion of pupils with SEN have been conducted in elementary (primary) schools in the United States. Only recently has the focus of literature been further extended to secondary inclusion programmes. Some of the concepts of classroom practice that have proved to be successful in primary education seem to be used to develop secondary inclusion programmes, such as 'peer tutoring' and 'co-teaching'. In addition, the emphasis of some studies on secondary education is focused on 'learning strategies'.

Studies that pay attention to the consequences of intervention mainly focus on cognitive outcomes. Social or behavioural outcomes appear to be neglected.

In this section, the available literature on classroom practice in secondary education will be discussed in consideration of some identified themes.

4.2.1 Peer tutoring

McDonnell et al (2001) examine a programme, which combines Class-wide Peer Tutoring with collaboration between special and general teachers. The programme was focused on increasing the amount of time students with disabilities spent in mainstream education classes and improving the quality of the instruction they received in these classes. Dependent measures focused on the levels of academic responding and competing behaviours of students with and without disabilities. Key members in each department received in-service training to introduce strategies for supporting students with severe disabilities in general education classes (response adaptation, curriculum overlapping and multi-element curriculum and developing natural support in the classroom). In addition, some members received on-site technical assistance to develop educational programmes for students with severe educational and behavioural needs.

The study was conducted in a pre-algebra, a physical education and a history class. The experimental conditions for students with disabilities consisted of Baseline and the Instructional Package. The conditions for the students without disabilities consisted of Baseline and Class-wide Peer Tutoring. During baseline instruction, the students with disabilities focused on their own IEP objectives. The instructional package for students with disabilities consisted of Class-wide Peer Tutoring, multi-element curriculum and accommodations.

Class-wide Peer Tutoring sessions were scheduled twice a week for fifteen minutes. Teachers were asked to form heterogeneous teams that included three students of different performance levels. During the sessions each student played the role of tutor, tutee and observer. The tutor would select a problem or task to be completed by the tutee and the observer provided social reinforcement. The teacher developed assistance procedures.

Multi-element curricula: special and general education teachers worked together to develop instructional objectives for the students with disabilities that focused on a set of abilities within the general curriculum.

Accommodations: special and general education teachers worked together to develop accommodations that would meet the unique learning needs of each student.

Three students with moderate to severe disabilities were observed. In addition, three students without disabilities, one special education teacher and three general education teachers were observed. Observations were carried out during baseline and Class-wide Peer Tutoring sessions.

Findings indicate that for both students with and without disabilities the level of academic responding improved and the level of competing behaviour decreased.

Another study on Peer Tutoring was conducted by Allsop (1997). In this programme, both the staff and the students received training on how to use Class-wide Peer Tutoring procedures. The CWPT procedures included: 1) peer-tutoring skills, 2) transition from regular seating into tutoring-pairs, 3) retrieval and return of materials, 4) practice in tutoring, 5) tutee responding behaviours, 6) error correction procedures, 7) point assignment procedures.

Students in both intervention groups were instructed using *Solving Division Equations*: an algebra programme for teaching students with learning problems (Mercer & Allsopp, 1995). Students in intervention group A autonomously practised their worksheets after teacher directed lessons. Students in intervention group B participated in CWPT, to practice the skills. They used the same worksheets as the students in group A, but an answer key was provided by the tutor to assist his or her tutee in determining correct responses. Students served both as tutor and tutee. Teachers were instructed to monitor student performance and behaviour by circulating through the classrooms.

Findings indicated that, overall, student performance for the CWPT group was not significantly different from the independent practice group. The programme was implemented in the 8th grade (ages ranged from 12-15). CWPT seems to be most effective with 14 and 15-year old students. Although these older students in the independent practice group performed significantly better on the pre-test, students in the CWPT group scored slightly higher on the post-test.

Overall, the findings suggest that the problem solving skills instruction *Solving Division Equations* was effective to both types of student practice.

4.2.2 Co-teaching

Several studies focus on co-operation between general and special education teachers. Quite a few names are used to label such co-operation, for instance team-teaching, co-teaching, or collaborative teaching.

Weigel, Murawski and Swanson (2001) conducted a meta-analysis of data-based articles regarding co-teaching. In addition to the quantitative data that is offered in this article, the authors provided four clear characteristics that identify interventions as a form of co-teaching: general education teachers and special service providers should be working together; the intervention should occur in the same space; an

element of co-planning should be included and the intervention should involve delivering instruction to a heterogeneous group of students, with and without special needs.

Weigel, Murawski and Swanson detect that only a few articles meet the criteria to be included in the meta-analysis, mainly because of the lack of proper quantitative data. Two of the six articles that were taken into account in the analysis focused on programmes in secondary education. Large effect sizes (0.87 - 3.67) were obtained for the one study that focused on kindergarten through third grade and for one that focused on high school level. Differentiation by ability was not possible. Although the studies provide limited results, the authors suggest that co-teaching might be a suitable service delivery option in secondary education.

A study on effectiveness of mainstreaming with collaborative teaching was conducted by Lundeen and Lundeen (1993). The study evaluated a collaborative teaching service delivery model in which special education students were mainstreamed into regular classes. Special and regular teachers team taught the curriculum and were responsible for choosing teaching methods, curriculum formats, learning strategies, study skills and evaluation methods. Fifteen classes joined the programme; eight regular teachers and five special teachers were involved, teaching 318 students. Among the students with special needs were students with learning disabilities, hearing impairments, behavioural disorders, mild mental impairments and students with restricted English skills. Previous grades in reading comprehension scores were analysed, as well as results in the collaborative teaching programme. Comparison by student category, teaching team and grade changes for individual students were made. All students in the programme performed equivalently, despite substantially poorer reading comprehension scores of special education students. All students' grades improved after the programme.

In a qualitative study of co-teaching in secondary schools by Rice and Zigmond (2000), teacher interviews and observations were conducted in Australia and the United States. The 17 teachers were selected because of their experience with co-teaching. They all co-taught classes with 3-8 special needs students. All teachers volunteered to participate. Although this study does not provide quantitative information on students' outcomes, it presents interesting information on the opinion of teachers. Six themes come forward from the data sets:

1. Teachers attributed the success or failure of co-teaching to a school-wide commitment to inclusion and the extent of administrative and collegial support they received.
2. Teachers thought both students as well as teachers benefit from co-teaching. They felt they can learn a lot from each other.
3. The compatibility of teachers seemed to be very important. Teachers thought that nobody should be forced into inclusion or co-teaching.
4. The special education teachers often needed to prove themselves for the partnership. They generally had a lower status in the secondary education hierarchy. Co-teaching could change this status.
5. Teachers were not always equal partners. The authors observed special education teachers performing clerical duties. In most cases, the inequality in roles was explained as necessary because the special education teacher lacked content knowledge.

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6. Implementing co-teaching involved overcoming deep-rooted attitudes and administrative barriers. The most common problems were: negative views toward inclusion, jealousy of the professional autonomy of teachers and rejection of the idea that co-teaching would benefit teachers and their students.

4.2.3 *Learning strategies*

A study by Maccini and Hughes (2000) investigated the effects of an instructional strategy on the representation and solution of problem-solving skills (STAR, Maccini, 1998) regarding integer numbers for secondary students with learning disabilities. Instruction consisted of three levels:

1. Concrete manipulation (manipulating physical objects to represent mathematical problems)
2. Semi-concrete application (pictorial representations of mathematical problems)
3. Abstract application (writing mathematical symbols to represent and solve problems).

Students also learned a strategy designed to cue effective problem-solving strategies. The study was focused on the question whether students can learn a self-instructional strategy to help them monitor their performance, whether the programme would improve their performance and whether students would generalise and maintain the intervention effects. Six students with learning disabilities were selected from a general secondary school. Participants were functioning more than 2 years below grade level. They received part-time support in a resource class. Findings indicated that the programme dramatically improved problem-solving skills involving integer numbers. Students' strategy use also increased over the instructional levels. Intervention effects were proven to be lasting in a transfer/generalisation task. Overall, participants were of the opinion that the programme helped them to become better problem solvers and they felt it had helped them to feel better about their algebra ability. Participants recommended using the programme with other students.

Tralli and Colombo (1996) describe a strategy intervention model. This study examined two case examples of schools that have attempted to include students with mild disabilities successfully throughout the general education programme. Although the study does not provide quantitative figures, authors stated that the inclusion of students with special needs was supported by the use of this model.

'The Strategies Intervention Model' was developed by the University of Kansas Centre for Research (KU-CRL). Three kinds of intervention were used: learning strategy interventions (students were taught various learning strategies), instructional interventions (teachers used content enhancement routines to improve understanding) and empowerment interventions (to stimulate students to do their best and create positive relationships with others in school). Authors stated that the successful inclusion of students with mild disabilities was accomplished by giving teachers considerable time for planning and administrative support throughout the change process. A high level of collaboration between general and special education teachers was needed. The process of building an environment that is conducive to

inclusion takes considerable time and broad based faculty and administrative support and commitment.

4.2.4 *Combined designs*

The same 'Strategies Interventions Model' was part of a study by Rogan and La Jeunesse (1995). The Pennsylvania Department of Education, in response to enquiries from teachers and parents who observed positive results of the Pennsylvania's elementary Instructional Support Programme, developed the Secondary Instructional Support (SIS) project. SIS was aimed at training and guidance in five major areas: collaboration and team building, curriculum-based assessment, instructional techniques and adaptations, student motivation and learning strategies.

The SIS programme incorporated the Strategies Intervention Model (SIM). The emphasis of this model was to shift the responsibility for learning from teacher to student; it taught students when and how to select a strategy and how to use the strategies. In addition, it focused on teaching students how to generalise their use of the strategy.

The study evaluated the results of the programme in one of the initial schools that introduced SIS. The programme was first introduced in the Junior High School. During the pilot year, 1,023 students were enrolled in Junior High, including 78 students with special needs. Two 7th and two 8th grade classes were selected for the study. The English teacher and the special education teacher co-taught two classes. The English teacher taught the other two classes. There were 8 students with learning difficulties (LD) in one co-teaching class of 24 students and 10 LD students in the other co-taught class of 27 students. The other two classes did not contain students with learning disabilities.

The main purpose of the study was to determine whether the programme would help students with LD to succeed in an inclusive English class and whether the programme would create any disadvantage for the non-LD students. All students were expected to achieve all of the course requirements set by the English teacher. Findings suggested that students with learning disabilities could succeed in intermediate English classes when they were provided with strategies training. In addition, the inclusion of students without LD did not seem to have a negative impact on the students without learning disabilities.

Weller (2000) described a revision of the schedule in a school, which had already incorporated an inclusion programme since 1990. Authors stated that the inclusion programme seemed to be highly effective since the school was frequently visited and the programme was recognised as a model programme by the Council for Exceptional Children.

Additional information on the inclusion model of this school was provided by Cole and McLeskey (1997):

“the indispensable aspect of this programme is the collaborative partnerships used to transform classrooms into settings in which the needs of a broad range of students can be met. These partnerships require significantly different

roles for teachers of students with special needs, as well as for content-area teachers. They also require that teachers become equal partners in the education of all students.”

Alongside the introduction of co-teaching, the school revised the curriculum and instruction to meet the needs of all students.

In 1996, a block schedule was implemented in this school. The traditional schedule consisted of six classes per semester, offered daily during 50-minute periods. The new schedule consisted of eight courses per semester, having four periods per day, each lasting 85 minutes. After many meetings, 80% of the staff voted for the implementation of the new schedule.

The study aimed at addressing the question: what are the benefits and challenges that accrue for an inclusion programme when block scheduling is implemented? The authors used qualitative methods to provide a better understanding of the influence of the implementation of block scheduling. Classroom observations and interviews were conducted during the first year of implementation. Participants were 7 teachers of students with disabilities and 7 general education teachers.

Results highlighted the following benefits:

1. Block scheduling facilitated the inclusion of students with high-incidence disabilities and assisted in meeting the educational needs of all students.
2. It facilitated teachers working together to examine current teaching practices and share responsibility for modifying the curriculum.
3. It allowed more teacher-student contact and gave teachers more opportunities to get to know students' learning styles and interests.
4. It enhanced the development of lessons that were more focused on student co-operation and participation.
5. It gave students the chance to take two more classes per semester and gave them more elective time. This provided students with special needs the opportunity to explore interests and undeveloped and overlooked talents. The need for resource time of students with special needs did not increase.
6. It created a more relaxed atmosphere and more flexibility for students and teachers.

In addition, some challenges were evident from the interviews and observations. The new schedule magnified the need for teachers and students to develop effective organisational skills. Block scheduling made it harder for students to keep track of their books and the materials, due dates and exam dates. The implementation increased the need for teachers to keep in contact with each other. Despite the fact that lessons became more student-centred, some teachers felt that the lessons were too long for some students. The biggest complaint was regarding absence. When a student missed two lessons, s/he missed an entire week's work. For students who missed classes, it was hard to find time to meet a teacher; there was no consultation-time built into the schedule.

4.2.5 Assessment

Research on inclusion programmes in primary education is frequently focused on Curriculum Based Measurement (CBM). Although CBM is mentioned in articles regarding secondary education (Rogan and La Jeunesse, 1995), there is no quantitative data available regarding CBM. There are according to many authors however, no reasons to believe that CBM would not be effective in secondary education. Under Curriculum Based Measurement (CBM) conditions, pupil progress is monitored using a computer programme. Performances are tested weekly and results are entered into a computer programme that summarises performance into a graph. Both teachers and students are taught to interpret the graphs. Teachers who use CBM appear to make more instructional adjustments than teachers who do not systematically monitor students' performances. The use of CBM does not directly lead to higher student achievement. To increase performance, the use of a computer programme that provides recommendations about instructional adjustments, appears to be essential. (Fuchs, Fuchs, Hamlett and Stecker 1991; Fuchs, Fuchs, Hamlett, Phillips and Bentz, 1994).

The results of two methods of reading assessment, using computer and paper and pencil are examined in a study by Horton and Lovit (1994). In one condition, students read textbook passages presented on a computer, completed study guides and took 15 item tests on the computer. In the other condition, students read passages from their textbooks, completed study guides, and took 15 item tests with pencil and paper. An equivalent time samples design was arranged, with four computer assessments and four paper and pencil assessments randomly assigned. The 72 students were divided into three groups: teacher directed, dyadic and independent. Two types of test items, factual and interpretative, were examined in this study.

Two classes in middle school science, two in middle school social studies and two in high school social studies participated. In each grade level, one class served as an experimental group and one served as a control group. In the experimental classes 13 students were learning disabled (LD), 16 remedial, and 43 normal achieving (NA), a total of 72 students, 38 males and 34 females. The settings were students' general education classrooms.

The independent measures were nine multiple-choice tests, prepared by the teachers and edited by the research staff. All tests contained 15 questions, 12 factual, 3 interpretative, each with 4 choices. The first author's research staff developed a computer programme. The programme presented 1) directions and instructions 2) a reading passage was presented, taken verbatim from the text, normally consisting of about seven screens of text, and 3) a multiple-choice test.

The results of the group analysis significantly favoured the computer group on factual questions for both the students with and without learning disabilities. Individual analyses indicate few significant differences between the two types of group reading inventories. The results of the group analysis revealed no significant difference on interpretative test items. Overall on interpretative questions, the LD students scored slightly higher with pencil and paper and the NA students scored slightly higher on computer assessments.

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5 COUNTRY REVIEWS

5.1 AUSTRIA

Irene Moser, National Co-ordinator for Austria

“Every child is singular and unique, every child is different, regardless of any disability it may have. Looking upon this diversity as an enrichment, an opportunity for all, is part of our being human and an underlying philosophy of inclusive education.” (Claudia Niedermair).

5.1.1 General information and framework conditions governing integration at secondary level I in Austria

From the very outset, integration was a reform that was spurred on by motivated parents and committed practitioners - in other words a bottom-up initiative that prompted schools into action initially by way of pilot projects. It was only 10 years later that the first school law amendment on integration at the primary level was adopted, followed in 1997 by its transposition to the secondary level. The general framework is characterised by three models, which have already been described in greater detail in the analysis of literature for the primary level (see www.european-agency.org):

1. The *integration model*, in which pupils with special educational needs (SEN) are taught in “integration” classes with several SEN pupils and adolescents in a class together with non-disabled pupils, supported by the presence of a second teacher throughout the entire instruction time
2. The *support teacher model*, in which one or two SEN pupils in a class are supported by specially trained teachers for a few hours per week, and
3. The *co-operation model*, in which special school and secondary general school pupils are taught jointly for selected subjects.

In Austria, parents and pupils decide after the fourth year of primary schooling on continued integration at secondary general school or the lower cycle of a secondary academic school. Both school types apply the same curriculum. At secondary general schools, however, pupil performance is considerably more heterogeneous than at secondary academic schools.

There is, however, a wide discrepancy in student movement (flows) between urban and rural areas. Wherever there is a sufficient provision of secondary academic schools (cities), parents tend to place their children at this type of school rather than at secondary general schools, which are often viewed as reservoirs absorbing underachieving pupils or pupils whose mother tongue is not German. In rural areas, in contrast, the majority of all pupils attend secondary general schools, which allows a later transfer to higher-level schools (upper cycle of secondary academic school, intermediate and higher-level technical and vocational schools).

Most SEN pupils are taught at secondary general schools, because the law allows for greater organisational flexibility (e.g. individual integration) and because the number of pupils per class tends to be lower in comparison to secondary academic schools. With demand exceeding capacity, many secondary academic schools would have to

reject talented pupils in order to be able to admit SEN pupils, even though the law provides for the possibility of setting up integration classes. This has been clearly highlighted by Specht (1997)¹ as follows:

”Apparently, it is difficult to explain that it is possible to support SEN pupils in integration classes, but not ”regular” pupils who lack the capability for schooling at secondary general school.”

Three ability groups (sets) are offered at secondary general schools for German, Mathematics and English in order to more adequately meet the needs of a heterogeneous clientele. By grouping pupils of more or less homogeneous performance, teachers can cater to a defined target group with less effort placed upon differentiation.

External differentiation implies an organisational separation of the class as a whole, as pupils do not remain with their core group, but change to different classrooms for joint lessons with other pupils from parallel classes. In many instances, this has turned out to be a serious disadvantage for the integration of SEN pupils, since social continuity cannot be ensured. External differentiation may be suspended during the year. However, the end-of-year report must indicate for all non-disabled pupils the ability group to which they had been assigned (no longer a school project, but regular practice!).

5.1.2 Publications in Austria from 1995-2002

In this section, publications that include evaluation results from all Federal Provinces will be presented. Three comprehensive studies were initiated or supported by the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Culture (FMESC) and were published between 1995 and 1999

The INSEK Projekt

Individual case studies carried out at 14 sites all over the national territory constitute the core of the INSEK project. The schools were not selected randomly, but nominated by the provincial school boards as – in their view - models for future development. Uniform survey instruments were developed and used by the case study managers at the different sites. Structured interviews with teachers, school heads, parents and school inspectors, informal talks and observations as well as documents that were available at the school were used as a basis for data compilation. (cf.: Specht 1997)².

Autonomy evaluation

When evaluating the autonomy of Austria’s secondary general schools (1997), the project manager Werner Specht (Centre for School Development, Graz) explored how running integration classes affected schools as organisations. 27 out of 197 secondary general schools surveyed had set up school projects on the joint teaching of disabled and non-disabled pupils.

¹ Specht W.: Fallstudien zur Integration behinderter Schüler in der Sekundarstufe, Graz 1997

² Specht W.: Jedes Kind ist Mittelpunkt, Ergebnisse und Gedanken aus der Evaluation der Schulversuche zur Integration behinderter Schüler in der Sekundarstufe 1, in: Behinderte in Familie, Schule und Gesellschaft, 4/97

Are disabled pupils a handicap?

In his study "Behindern Behinderte", Feyerer³ in 1997 was able to respond to the question whether the presence of disabled pupils had a positive, negative or no impact at all on the scholastic performance, self-conception and the condition of non-disabled pupils in integration classes. A total of 651 pupils from 9 integration and 23 parallel classes were interviewed shortly before transferring to working life or higher-level schooling at seven secondary general schools and two secondary academic schools from all over Austria.

5.1.3 Evaluation at provincial level

The search for empirical studies carried out in the provinces proved difficult because many studies have not been published. Despite expert assistance, only a small number of studies could be located which provide information on the core question of "How do teachers at secondary level cope with integrative teaching" on the basis of data surveys.

Pannos 1996, Feyerer 1999, Moser 1998 and Hauer 2000 authored studies on this topic when monitoring projects on integration.

Feyerer published the results of a study on performance evaluation in inclusive classes at secondary level in Upper Austria ("*Leistungsbeurteilung in Integrationsklassen der Sekundarstufe in Oberösterreich*"). A survey was conducted in the school year 1997/98 to identify the motives and the extent to which teachers use different forms of performance evaluation. (Feyerer 1999)⁴

Hauer⁵ surveyed 607 Upper Austrian head teachers and teachers who were acting as special education teachers in integration classes, to obtain an overview of how integration is currently practised at secondary general schools. Specifically, he took a closer look at preparatory activities, classroom work and at co-operation and co-ordination.

Preceding the legal embodiment of integration at secondary level in 1996, Pannos⁶ presented statistics on the development of schools offering integration in Vienna and summarised her experience as a staff member of the integration advice centre with teachers and classroom practice.

In Salzburg, a case study was drawn up (Moser 1998) in the wake of the scientific monitoring of school projects using the qualified research instruments of the INSEK study (1997). The study addressed the integration of adolescents with behaviour problems in the support teacher model.

³ cf: Feyerer E: Behindern Behinderte, Auswirkungen integrativen Unterrichts auf nichtbehinderte Kinder in der Sekundarstufe 1, in: Behinderte in Familie, Schule und Gesellschaft, 4/97

⁴ cf.: Feyerer E.: Leistungsbeurteilung in Integrationsklassen der Sekundarstufe 1, in: Behinderte in Familie, Schule und Gesellschaft, Bd. 1/1999

⁵ Hauer K.: Integration in der Hauptschule, Lehrer/innen-Befragung vom Juni 2000, Arbeitsunterlage für die BSI Dienstbesprechung, Schärding 2000

⁶ Pannos J.: Auf dem Weg zum Ziel, ein Rückblick und eine kritische Bestandsaufnahme schulischer Integration im Sekundarstufenbereich in Wien, sowie Zukunftsperspektiven, in: Erziehung und Unterricht, 10/1996

Niedermaier (2002)⁷ wrote a Dissertation with the topic: "Putting a school for all into practice" (Zur Pragmatik der Vision einer Schule für alle) where she presented the outcome of the scientific monitoring of pilot school projects in Vorarlberg.

5.1.4 Experience reports and theoretic approaches in special education magazines

Reports of practical experience and teaching aids complement the scientific perspective, indicating how individuals live and cope with integration. The topics presented in the following clearly pinpoint the challenges and the problems that need to be solved.

The authors often address the framework required, as well as the need for team work and team teaching, the changing role of teachers (functions and tasks of teachers in integration classes), social learning in an integration class, the scope for designing integrative teaching, supporting pupils with severe disabilities and coping with heterogeneity in the different subjects. The publications focus on innovative assessment methods and the documentation of development as well as on the need to modify teacher-training contents.

(Feyerer 2001: <http://www.pa-linz.ac.at/international/Integer/integerneu.htm>)

Theoretical approaches and motivation reports and practice-oriented studies can be found in the following magazines: "*Erziehung und Unterricht*"⁸, "*Behinderte in Familie, Schule und Gesellschaft*"⁹, and "*Heilpädagogik*"¹⁰.

In addition, several experience reports by experts who either teach in integration classes or support teacher colleagues in their work in a monitoring and advisory function exist. The following publications are of particular interest for readers looking for information on how integration is practically implemented at school: "*Integrativer Unterricht, Beiträge zur Lehrerfortbildung für die Sekundarstufe I*"¹¹, issued by the Federal Ministry of Education and Culture (FMESC), the manual "*Voneinander Lernen*" "*Behördenfibel II*" (an administrative primer by the Styrian province school board), the brochure "*Step by Step*"¹² and the summary of the practitioner's forum.¹³

The FMESC issues a magazine entitled "*Integration in der Praxis*"¹⁴, designed first and foremost as a platform of exchange for and by practitioners on integration work in schools. The Vienna "*Integrationsjournal*"¹⁵ and a Salzburg technical journal "*Der*

⁷ Niedermaier C.: Zur Pragmatik einer Schule für alle, integrative Unterrichtsgestaltung im Spiegel von Theorie und Alltagspraxis am Beispiel der ersten Hauptschulintegrationsklassen in Vorarlberg, Innsbruck 2002

⁸ Erziehung und Unterricht: Österreichische pädagogische Zeitschrift, öbv & hpt VerlagsgmbH & co. KG, 1096 Wien, Frankgasse 4

⁹ Behinderte in Familie, Schule und Gesellschaft: Verein "1% für behinderte Kinder und Jugendliche", Alberstrasse 8, 8010 Graz

¹⁰ Heilpädagogik: Fachzeitschrift der Heilpädagogischen Gesellschaft, Verlag Kaiser 2011 Höbersdorf

¹¹ Integrativer Unterricht: Beiträge für die Lehrerfortbildung für die Sekundarstufe 1, BMUK 1997

¹² Von einander lernen: Ratgeber zur Integration", BMBWK 2000; Behördenfibel II: LSR für Steiermark, 1998 und "Step by Step": Anregungen und Tipps zum gemeinsamen Unterricht in Integrationsklassen der Sekundarstufe I, BMBWK, ZSE 2001

¹³ 10 Jahre Integration in Oberösterreich, Ein Grund zum Feiern?, Linz 2000

¹⁴ Integration in der Praxis: Zentrum für Schulentwicklung, Klagenfurt

¹⁵ Das Integrationsjournal: Integrationsberatungsstelle, Wiplingerstrasse 28, 1010 Wien

*Spitzer*¹⁶ offers readers interesting insights into day-to-day integration at school and on networking with other disciplines that are relevant for special education.

The association “*Integration:Österreich*” publishes the journal “*Betrifft: Integration*”¹⁷ and, with FMESC support, materials on socio-integrative schooling.

5.1.5 Models and methods to cope with heterogeneous pupil groups

The study by the European Agency sets out to explore in detail the attitudes of teachers and the methods applied to cope with class heterogeneity. Specht (1997)¹⁸ describes the requirements teachers in Austria are expected to fulfil:

- Provide the best possible schooling for all pupils, regardless of whether they are disabled or not
- Develop and implement education that is pupil-centred and tailored to the needs of the individual pupil
- Promote social learning, empathy, readiness to help others, consideration of weaker members, social responsibility
- Achieve a system of schooling without segregation, in which even severely disabled and/or mentally disabled pupils find their place without putting non-disabled pupils at a disadvantage or impairing the quality of school and instruction
- Ultimately, that novel forms of teaching in integration classes generate synergies and positively affect the quality of school culture as a whole.

Using a uniform observation instrument, the case study managers in the INSEK study surveyed 28 classes all over Austria, 14 of which were non-integrative reference classes, to determine whether the stakeholders could meet those requirements. They surveyed 275 parents and 596 pupils by way of interviews and questionnaires.

The different models provided the organisational frame for classroom work. The survey design ensured the comparability of the model experiences in the different provinces.

Which is the best possible model?

Although the abandoning of ability grouping is considered as being the more favourable variant in terms of positive social integration processes and the stability of the group of learners, the compilation presented in the INSEK study was unable to provide conclusive answers as to which model would allow the most successful implementation of integration. The study contrasted the situation of secondary general schools in rural areas with and without ability grouping, secondary general schools in urban areas, which had abandoned ability grouping, as well as higher-level schools, which do not run ability groups at all.

Owing to their complexity, the conditions for success cannot be limited to these factors. However, it was clearly established that the positive attitude of teachers and the school community vis-à-vis integration is the primary driving force for successful

¹⁶ Der Spitzer: SPZ für Sinnesbehinderte, Lehenerstrasse 1a, 5020 Salzburg

¹⁷ *Betrifft: Integration: Integration; Österreich und Verein: Gemeinsam Leben- gemeinsam Lernen*, Wurzbachgasse 20/8, 1150 Wien

¹⁸ Specht W.: *ibid* p: 13

integration - whatever model is selected. The innovative momentum generated by those schools can even overcome difficult constraints (e.g. insufficient number of hours allowed for associated monitoring, poorly equipped classes, too many teachers in the team, etc.)

Only one example of a co-operation setting in Lower Austria clearly stood out from the other case studies. Several respondents voiced extensive criticism about the meaningfulness of teaching 22 secondary general school pupils and 7 special school pupils jointly in the creative subjects and in physical education:

"Meagre results are obtained at a considerable investment of organisational effort, with the high number of pupils per class in subjects with joint teaching being just one aspect". (Specht 1997)¹⁹

This feedback adds itself to the list of relatively negative accounts found in international publications on co-operation experiences.

Are there limits to integration?

During the pilot project stage in particular, teachers would often debate the feasibility of integration and voice serious doubts as to whether it makes sense to include pupils with severe handicaps. Interestingly, the fears voiced by teachers that they would be unable to cope with or live up to the new work environment, or were not sufficiently trained (cf. Rutte 1996)²⁰ did not materialise in practice.

Even in classes that presented high-level stresses, the teachers expressed satisfaction at doing something pedagogically useful, as is evidenced by the following statement of a teacher:

"As a teacher, I derive profound satisfaction from open forms of learning. However, I have to invest a lot more time than if I were to work the conventional way" (Niedermair 1997)²¹

Another positive effect was created by the integration of severely disabled pupils, as the non-disabled pupils in these integration classes tended to understand the principle of individualisation much better and feel treated less unfairly than in integration classes with pupils that have learning difficulties. It is evident that the perceived well-being of pupils is another major criterion for successful integration.

Do pupils in integration classes enjoy classes more and can they benefit more frequently from alternative forms of learning than in conventional classes?

The questionnaire used the following categories to find out how pupils perceived the climate in class and whether they experienced a stronger sense of education centred upon pupils: enjoying school, enjoying classes, relationships with peers, trust in teachers, supportive attitude of teachers, possibilities to participate in the design of instruction, unfairness of teachers, lack of order or chaos in instruction, anonymity, clearness of expectations and readiness among pupils to help one another.

¹⁹ Specht W.: *ibid* p 20

²⁰ Rutte V.: "Aber dafür bin ich doch nicht ausgebildet", neue Aufgaben und Anforderungen an den Sekundarschullehrer, in: *Behinderte in Familie, Schule und Gesellschaft* Bd.10/1996

²¹ Niedermair C.: *ibid* p 35

The results demonstrated how intensely the teachers had striven for innovative work methods. The pupils in the pilot classes perceived the school and class climate as being better; they felt better looked after than their peers in conventional classes. In addition, pupils in integration classes tended to participate more actively in classroom activities, they felt that they had a say in more matters; more frequently they were taught in forward-thinking settings which promoted the “soft skills” demanded by the business world (cf: Specht 1997).²² Feyerer (1997)²³ corroborates these findings in a study in which he interviewed pupils about their experience and about forms of learning used in integration classes.

Scientifically monitoring pilot projects on integration, Niedermair summarises her experience of integrative teaching as follows:

”Integrative teaching is an attempt to enable individual learning processes within a heterogeneous group. It aims at designing instruction in a way that all pupils within the class are able to learn in accordance with their abilities and development potentials”. (Niedermair 1997)²⁴

According to Niedermair, integrative teaching includes self-directed study according to a weekly schedule (interdisciplinary and subject-centred self-directed work), project instruction and project-oriented learning, workshop instruction (or *atelier* work) as well as conventional instruction.

In his essay on the situation of social integration at secondary level in Austria, Rutte raises the same topic and postulates:

”Internal differentiation and open, project-oriented instruction is the answer to the problems. This becomes evident in the new draft curriculum for secondary general school. ... we speak of educational theorems like ”the path leading to knowledge supersedes knowledge as such”, ”orientation towards life-long learning”, ”active, self-reliant, autonomous learning” (Rutte 1996)²⁵

In her dissertation, Niedermair (2002) is in line with the practical experiences of her colleagues.

”Teaching with pupil centred methods is highly satisfying for the teachers, but is connected with [an increased] workload and it is time consuming.”
(Niedermair 2002)²⁶

At the pilot schools, integration of theory and practice had already become manifest. The teachers were committed individuals who tried to place the pupils at the centre of all interests. Which new challenges/problems arise out of the need for teacher-teacher co-operation?

²² Specht W.: *ibid* p 19

²³ Feyerer E. : Behindern Behinderte ? in: Behinderte in Familie, Schule und Gesellschaft Bd. 4/1997, p. 43

²⁴ Niedermair C.: *ibid* p 31

²⁵ Rutte V.: Zur Situation der sozialintegrativen Sekundarstufe in Österreich, in: Behinderte in Familie, Schule und Gesellschaft, Bd. 3/1996

²⁶ Niedermair C.: Zur Pragmatik einer Schule für alle, integrative Unterrichtsgestaltung im Spiegel von Theorie und Alltagspraxis am Beispiel der ersten Hauptschulintegrationsklassen in Vorarlberg, page 295, Innsbruck 2002

Taking a close look at team work

It is a fact that integration researchers have given considerable credence to the co-operation of teachers in a team. This issue was taken up and examined in great detail in Austrian publications, e.g.: Pannos and Rutte 2001, Martinz, Lion-Slovak and Lugstein 1997²⁷, and Pannos 1996.

Voluntary behaviour and actions, commitment to the goals of the pilot project on the part of the teachers, small and manageable teams, even if some subjects were taught by teachers without the necessary formal qualifications and the willingness and ability to co-operate between the participating teachers were mentioned as the major elements for successful co-operation (cf: Joppich, Troyer, Feyerer 1997 and Gradauer 1996)²⁸

As a catalyst for co-ordination and/or communication in different processes, specialist teachers (spending most of the classroom periods with the pupils) play a pivotal role in integration classes at secondary general schools. The larger the team of teachers, the more difficult it becomes to fulfil this role of an intermediary, hence the call for the smallest possible teams. Small teams have a positive effect on the social dimension (also for pupils) and the ability to cope with the growing demands for communication. The quality of teaching is bound to suffer if the timetable leaves hardly any room for free periods that could be used for briefings and if joint instruction is planned "on the fly" during breaks, over the telephone or in meetings at the end of the day (cf. Hauer 2000).

Segregation will become more pronounced in the different subjects if the team of teachers does not fully subscribe to joint teaching as an educational approach (cf. Specht 1997 and Knaus 1997²⁹, and Hauer 2000).

This development became clearly evident in the study carried out by Hauer three years after the legal embodiment of integration at secondary level.

"In reality, it is impossible to achieve the balance between conventional and open forms of instruction which the decree issued in Upper Austria speaks of. It follows cogently that SEN pupils are detached from classroom activities to a large extent. Particularly with support teacher classes, this often leads to a spatial segregation as well. ... In spite of the assignment of two teachers, one half of all integration classes spend no more than 5 hours on alternative forms of instruction. 50% of all classes using a support teacher apply this form of instruction one hour per week at most."

²⁷ see Pannos J., Rutte V.: Team/Teambildung- Teamarbeit/Teamteaching in: Step by Step, Anregungen und Tipps zum gemeinsamen Unterricht in Integrationsklassen der Sekundarstufe 1, BMBWK 2001 and Martinez u., Lion Slovak B.: Was ist ein Lehrerteam? Sowie Lugstein H.: Teamteaching in Integrationsklassen, in: Integrativer Unterricht, Beiträge für die Lehrerfortbildung für die Sekundarstufe 1, BMUK 1997

²⁸ see Joppich E.: Fallstudien zur Integration behinderter Schüler in der Sekundarstufe, Bd. 3/1997, p 39, Troyer K.: ibid p 169 and Feyerer E.: ibid. Bd. 2, p 46 and Gradauer E.: in : Erziehung und Unterricht Bd. 10/1996, S 753

²⁹ cf. Specht W.: Fallstudien zur Integration behinderter Schüler in der Sekundarstufe 1, Graz 1997 und Knaus S.: Funktionen und Aufgaben der Lehrer in Integrationsklassen, in: Erziehung und Unterricht Bd. 2/ 1997

In a case study on the integration of pupils in the support teacher model, the headmaster of a secondary general school in Salzburg referred to a special school-teacher as a kind of "yeast that has fermented rethinking in some areas." Playing the role of a fermenting agent does not only imply pupil-oriented planning according to pedagogical principles, but also investing energy in a skills transfer with regard to innovative forms of teaching (social learning, open forms of instruction, project-oriented learning, etc.). If the teachers are not, or not fully, ready for innovation, those who are eager to bring about change will wear themselves out. Burnout is often the result of permanent frustration in the face of intense commitment to work.

Support teachers often have to perform a tightrope walk between meeting the wishes and requirements of their colleagues (filling them in on special content, follow-up on tests or in-depth preparation of school tests) and setting priorities for the most urgent pedagogical needs (special assistance in the field of perception and motor skills, practical life skills, etc.) cf. Moser 1998³⁰

This case study from Salzburg illustrates the difficulties that support teachers encounter when trying to implement reforms in a traditional setting (ability grouping, ex-cathedra instruction, no internal differentiation etc.).

Do non-disabled pupils perform equally well in integration classes as in conventional reference classes?

The various efforts deployed by the teachers to achieve well-functioning co-operation and a climate that promotes learning also aim at achieving good performances from all pupils, with parents and teachers being considerably more concerned about performance at secondary than at primary level. Stakeholders often ask whether the presence of SEN pupils has a positive, negative or no effect at all on scholastic performance, self-perception and the general position of non-disabled pupils in integration classes. Fears are often voiced that SEN pupils would restrain well-performing pupils, making it impossible to maintain overall performance levels.

In his study "*Behindern Behinderte*" Feyerer (1997) refuted this statement. He surveyed pupils from nine integration classes and 23 parallel classes in grade eight and used school tests as a basis for comparing performance in German, Mathematics and English. He reported that:

"...all integration pupils, including the gifted ones, do equally well as their counterparts in the reference classes.... Disabled pupils are hence not an obstacle, the stronger focus on social learning does not impair cognitive subject-matter learning." (Feyerer 1997)³¹

At least in the pilot classes, the concerns of parents and teachers were unfounded. With non-disabled pupils performing equally well as their counterparts in parallel classes, what about disabled pupils? Can the studies (not entirely recent) conducted in Austria furnish an answer to this question?

³⁰ Moser I.: "...warum muss ich mir das zusätzlich noch antun?" oder die besondere Problematik der Integration von Jugendlichen mit Verhaltensauffälligkeiten und sonderpädagogischen Förderbedarf im Stützmodell, Hausarbeit am Pädagogischen Institut Salzburg, 1998

³¹ Feyerer E.: *ibid* p 43

Teachers in Vorarlberg point out that the ‘winners of integration’ are the pupils with SEN and those who are high achievers and very motivated. “Sandwich children” (low achievers and pupils who are not very motivated to learn) are the ones who profit least. (see Niedermaier 2002)³²

Do pupils with special educational needs receive sufficient assistance in integration classes?

International data suggests that pupils with learning difficulties perform better.³³ According to Specht, nobody in Austria would take the trouble to perform a comparative survey of pupils with different degrees of disability in integration and in special school classes. In order to still find an answer to this question, teachers and parents were asked about how satisfied they were about the assistance given to SEN pupils. The INSEK study provides a clear answer to this question:

”The most notable benefits of integration are the improved possibilities of supporting disabled pupils, particularly on the social as well as the cognitive levels ... parents of SEN pupils (N47) likewise were highly satisfied at the level of specific support their own child would receive at school.” (Specht 1997)³⁴

This feedback is encouraging, but there is no hard-and-fast proof of the validity of this statement.

How are pupils’ achievements assessed and which forms of feedback are used in integration classes?

In his article on performance assessment in integration classes, the educationalist Vierlinger, who has been studying performance assessment for a number of years, starts out by clearly demanding the following:

”Teachers who not just tolerate but actively subscribe to the integration of compulsory school pupils must reject traditional systems of marking.” Vierlinger 1995³⁵

Owing to the individualisation of heterogeneous classes, i.e. the adjustment of the teaching content to the different performance levels of pupils, the theoretic model of standard distribution is no longer valid, as Feyerer argues:

”...how are we to establish a just and fair average, by which individual performance is measured, if the individuality of the pupils is used as a basis for teaching activities. Different settings of learning necessitate a wide repertory of methods and individualised learning objectives call for non-comparative forms of assessment.” (1997)³⁶

The pupils in Vorarlberg’s study demonstrate this theory by their achievements. Most of them were highly motivated, showed a positive attitude towards school and clearly

³² Niedermaier C.: *ibid*, page 295

³³ See Haerberlin U., Bless G., Moser U., Klaghofer R.: *Die Integration von Lernbehinderten, Versuche, Theorien, Forschungen, Enttäuschungen, Hoffnungen*, Bern 1990

³⁴ Specht W.: *Jedes Kind ist Mittelpunkt, Ergebnisse und Gedanken aus der Evaluation der Schulversuche zur Integration behinderter Schüler in der Sekundarstufe 1*, in: *Behinderte in Familie, Schule und Gesellschaft*, 4/97, S 17

³⁵ Vierlinger V.: “Die Kollektivnorm unterminiert das pädagogische Terrain” in: *Behinderte in Familie, Schule und Gesellschaft*, Bd. 1/1995

³⁶ Feyerer E.: *Alternative Formen der Leistungsbeurteilung auch in integrativen Hauptschulklassen* in: *10 Jahre Integration in Oberösterreich, Ein Grund zum Feiern?*, Linz 2000, S 138

pointed out that pressure is not the right method to encourage pupils (Niedermaier 2002).³⁷

As in Vorarlberg's study, several pilot projects successfully used portfolios, annotated direct performance targets, development reports, assignment books and other methods of performance assessment and feedback. The school-law amendment on the introduction of integration at secondary level, however, did not set the course for the abolition of the numeric marking system. As the tradition of marks is so strongly rooted in the history of schooling in Austria and hence in the heads of those who sustain the system, the reform was insufficient to prompt a process of re-thinking.

As a scientific advisor for pilot projects on integration in Upper Austria, Feyerer summarised the use of alternative instruments of performance assessment in his province. The Upper Austrian province school board allowed teachers in pilot projects to assess pupils verbally, using learning objective checklists and development books, and to add verbal comments to the numeric assessment, as well as to combine numeric assessment with verbal descriptions.

Some 25% of all schools practising integration used the opportunities offered, although an overwhelming number of teachers surveyed (64.7%) felt it was important that they could use alternative options. The reason might be the strongly rooted system of numeric assessment in Austria, as many teachers and parents stated that marks were more objective and easier to compare. Moreover, the traditional five-grade scale would give the layperson a better overall impression. (cf. Feyerer 2000) Feyerer moreover drew parallels to the organisational setting and found that innovation de facto happens only in the integration class model. Support teacher classes and individual integration (integration of pupils without additional teachers) rarely use alternative forms of performance assessment, because they have to adhere to existing, rigid structures. In this respect, the findings would suggest that integration classes offer a better scope for integrative, innovative forms of assessment.

5.1.6 Summary and outlook

Innovative secondary general schools that practice integration and are open to change do exist. They stand out in the Austrian overall trend compared to other secondary general schools in the autonomy study.³⁸ The requirements that have been defined in the outset were met in a generally positive manner in that an increased frequency of project-type, interdisciplinary and pupil-oriented forms of instruction was identified. Beyond that, the pupils felt more positive, they had a greater say and enjoyed classes more than their counterparts in the reference classes surveyed. Moreover, parents stated that pupils with and without disabilities received adequate assistance and support. At least one quarter of all integration classes in Upper Austria are prepared to use alternative forms of performance assessment.

³⁷ Niedermaier C.: *ibid*, page 296

³⁸ Specht W.: *Integration, Autonomie und Schulentwicklung an Hauptschulen*, in *Erziehung und Unterricht* Bd. 10/1996

Teachers cope with these challenges by increasing team work; they tend to accept the changing role of the teacher more readily if they can work with heterogeneous groups of pupils; they are not only committed to teaching but "take on a more active role in the development process of the school as a whole." (Specht 1996).³⁹

These key statements inspire optimism: integration could be a driving force for school development in general. Specht noted, however, that these changes might affect only the classes concerned. Impetus to reform the overall system of education had been generated, but lacked momentum.

A contributory factor that promoted greater diversity of school programmes in the autonomy schools with integration classes was the increase of financial resources allocated to the pilot schools.

5 years have passed since the data was compiled. During this time, integration at secondary level was enshrined in the law. The study by Hauer identified some negative trends arising from integration being incorporated in mainstream education. Support teachers are often used to give remedial tuition to underachieving pupils; a need to improve work preparation has been identified in particular in classes that have adopted the support teacher system. Mainstream classes tend to neglect the positively described alternative forms of instruction that were frequently used during the pilot phase.

Often, disabled and non-disabled pupils do not work in joint, but in parallel settings. Moreover, serious shortcomings in co-ordination and co-operation have been observed.

Niedermaier's (2002)⁴⁰ conclusions are also very critical. She states that political decision makers probably noticed the outcome of the research, but did not take it seriously enough. The resources are not sufficient and turn out to be reduced each year, especially in secondary schools.

This has an impact on practical implementation of working methods. At the moment 25 out of 38 classes still work with alternative teaching methods, but there is already a strong tendency back towards traditional structures and methods.

Additionally allocated periods were cancelled (such as the team hours which are remunerated separately, or time allocated for the use of several teachers for open forms of learning), scientific monitoring was officially discontinued in 1997, when the poorly funded mandate to support integration passed on to the Special Education Centres. Setting up classes with the minimal staff resources allowed is a source of headache for those in authority. The assignment of a second teacher to all periods in integration classes is no longer a matter of course. From today's perspective, the use of a third teacher (which was possible in many pilot classes in the main subjects) remains an unattainable state of educational bliss.

These deficits are experienced painfully by all stakeholders, as SEN pupils can no longer be assisted at the required level of quality. While integration at secondary

³⁹ Specht W.: *ibid*

⁴⁰ Niedermaier C.: *ibid* page 299

level has reached a state of acceptance, new and pressing challenges have abruptly come to the fore, which drain staff and conceptual resources for new tasks. Young people are crowding onto a labour market, the growing demands of which they are no longer able to cope with un-assisted. Multi-faceted initiatives will be needed now and in the future to be able to master these challenges successfully.

In this scenario, the caution formulated by Specht has lost nothing of its topicality:

”Amongst other things, we need to step up efforts in research and development, whose role appears subordinate when it comes to the design of teaching in educational research at present. This is true in particular for the development of efficient methods of work in integration classes: Excessive responsibility for furthering talented as well as disabled pupils is still placed on the shoulders of individual teachers or small teams and their commitment, initiative and creativity.” (Specht).⁴¹

⁴¹ Specht W.: *ibid*

5.2 FRANCE

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5.2.1 Methodology

The request from the European Agency was to review publications about investigations into inclusive education over the past ten years. The group described as “pupils with special educational needs” refers to two categories of pupils in France: pupils with a disability and pupils experiencing great educational difficulty.

Although the notion of inclusive education and inclusive classes has begun to be more widespread, it still lacks a precise meaning in the French educational system, in which the terms used are “educational integration” (for pupils with a disability) or educational adaptation (for pupils experiencing great educational difficulty).

In order to remain within the framework of the notion defined by the term “inclusive education”, i.e. education of pupils with special educational needs in an ordinary school and class, this section will only deal with the question of educational integration, which involves young people with motor, sensory and intellectual (mental) disabilities (intellectual deficiency, behaviour disorders, communication problems) and excludes the issue of educational/scholastic adaptation.

Indeed, educational support for pupils experiencing great educational difficulty during the first degree (from 3 to 11 years of age) does not exist in secondary schools. The system that has been set up in the “collèges” (secondary schools for pupils from 11 to 16 years old) for “pupils experiencing serious and persistent educational difficulty”, places these pupils in adapted General Education and Professional Sections (SEGPA). These sections function with a great degree of autonomy and even if they are annexed into the collèges, long-lasting education of such pupils in ordinary classes is non-existent. Even though the functioning of these sections has led to remarkable ways of adapting educational practices, programmes and training guidelines are not included in the defined framework.

5.2.2 General observations

What is especially striking in the results of this literature review is the uneven distribution in the volume of publications according to the type of disability. Publications devoted to intellectually disabled pupils and pupils with auditory problems are - relatively - numerous, but publications about pupils with motor and visual disabilities are very few (one for motor disabilities, two for visual disabilities).

When technical resources to help disabled pupils are available (manual or motor chairs, computer equipment, Braille typewriters etc), at least for pupils in secondary school, it seems that schooling raises fewer problems for teachers and therefore leads to fewer questions about educational adaptation.

In order to go deeper for this review, it has been necessary to present unpublished, but relevant material, essentially reports by people receiving training to become heads of adapted or specialized institutions (DDEEAS).

A further observation is that the texts found are mainly published in a small number of very specialized professional reviews. There were no texts or publications aimed at a broad audience of non-specialized teachers - except for the publications of the Minister of National Education – although these teachers are essential participants in educational integration.

Lastly, there are few publications of the type where sometimes a single experiment or investigation resulted in several articles. Structured investigations are rare and the policy of the Minister of National Education concerning educational integration of disabled adolescents in secondary schools has existed for only a few years. Historically, the education of disabled pupils and adolescents in France has been the task of elementary school teachers and inspectors. Secondary school teachers do not receive specific training in the education of this category of pupils. The short historical outline below indicates the basis for this situation and the new French policy orientations in this area.

5.2.3 History of the schooling of pupils with specific educational needs

- 1975: the right of disabled pupils to education in an ordinary environment or if such was impossible in a specialized environment was announced.
- 1982-1983: the integration of disabled pupils was established as a regulatory principle.
- 1990s: development of follow-up services and home care, aimed at making it easier to keep disabled pupils in an ordinary environment.
- 1995: Creation of specialized Educational Integration Units (UPI) to educate intellectually disabled adolescents collectively in secondary school between the ages of 11 and 16 (collège).
- 1999: Report of the General Inspection Services of the Hygiene and Social Affairs Department and of the Ministry of National Education showing that ordinary secondary schools provide education to only a very small number of disabled adolescents, that technical schools educate only a negligible number, and that disabled pupils kept within the ordinary system are essentially good pupils. The less productive pupils are placed in specialized schools.
- In the wake of this report, the “handisco” plan set the objective of returning disabled pupils to an ordinary environment, in particular adolescents to collèges, lycées (secondary schools for pupils 17-18 years of age) and vocational secondary schools.
- 2001: creation of the UPIs for all types of disabilities at every level of secondary school education.
- Training of secondary school teachers was started.
- Creation and development of teaching auxiliary role to support disabled pupils in the classroom.
- Funding by the State of educational tools to address disabilities.
- 2003: in the framework of the European year of disability, the Ministry of National Education announced the strengthening of the creation of UPIs (1,000 in five

years), the increase of teaching auxiliaries and the training of secondary school teachers to educate pupils with specific educational needs.

The schooling of pupils with special educational needs is thus a recent concern for the French school system. This explains the small volume of published material that is referred to above.

5.2.4 What constitutes an obstacle or causes a problem?

It has already been suggested that the schooling of adolescents with specific educational needs is considerably different according to the type of disability. It is apparently simpler for teachers of pupils with motor and visual deficiencies and more difficult for teachers with pupils with auditory deficiencies, i.e. when the deficiency complicates the most frequently used medium in teaching: the spoken word. The analysis of publications, however, has led to the identification of obstacles that regularly appear.

Inappropriate environment or teaching materials

This obstacle appears regularly in publications. Environment and teaching materials are conditions or facilitators of successful schooling. Technical developments over recent years and their funding by the State (teaching equipment) or by territorial authorities (environment) enable a growing number of disabled pupils to stay within the ordinary educational system.

Focus on “material remedies” for the disability

Technical aids (computers, binocular magnifiers etc) and human auxiliaries (sign language interpreters, teaching auxiliaries etc) must not obscure the fact that deficiencies also cause specific cognitive, emotional and social functioning differences, which require educational adaptations.

Concentration of difficulties within the school

The newness and particular situation of pupils with specific educational needs requires major educational reflection and initiative on the part of the team of teachers working in a normal, demanding school environment. For the pupils - in particular those with intellectual disabilities - the way other pupils receive them is an important factor in their inclusion. This inclusion is easier when the other pupils do not have difficulties with social or educational integration themselves.

No observation appears in the literature regarding the number of pupils in classes.

The “ghettoising” effect of collective integration systems or groups of disabled adolescents in the same class

This effect is more strongly felt in the UPIs for adolescents with intellectual deficiencies because the functioning of this type of class is least favourable towards integration. The team of teachers must strike a fine balance between integration in the ordinary class and the need to group pupils with difficulties together for educational as well as emotional and psychological reasons.

Adolescent fatigue

Constantly living in an environment that is extremely demanding for the disabled pupil sometimes leads him or her to prefer to return to a more re-assuring specialized class or school. This return is not an sign of failed integration, but it highlights the need for teachers to observe the pupil's psychological and emotional state carefully and to establish periods during which pupils with difficulties are together.

Integration in a group of adolescents

Adolescence is a difficult time during which one's self-image - developed through the way others perceive you - becomes of acute importance. The socialisation aspect of school integration requires special attention on the part of the team of adults.

Pupils' lack of cognitive skills

The school is above all a place for learning and the teacher's mission is to teach the pupil. The type of integration that aims essentially at socialisation does not easily last for very long. This holds especially true for intellectual difficulties. However, this argument, which may lead to a refusal or a discontinuing of integration, should be used with caution for other disabilities. The report from the Inspection Services mentioned above shows that learning demands are stronger with respect to disabled pupils than non-disabled ones.

Teachers' fatigue or lack of interest

This fatigue or lack of interest is most often due to pupils' limited or slow learning processes, especially for pupils with intellectual deficiencies. To overcome this, regularly re-launched projects and guidance are necessary for teachers.

Lack of training and information

Training and information are the major pre-requisites for success in educational integration. All investigations describe the training and exchanges between teaching, educational and therapeutic teams, parents and pupils prior to initiatives and during integration.

5.2.5 What produces results?

Training and information for the teaching team

Knowing the challenges of integration, the specific details of the disability and their impact on learning, are all types of information essential in eliminating the usual reservations when a team receives one or more adolescents with specific educational needs. Availability of such information prior to the initiative supports creating a dynamic process that favours personal involvement.

Teachers' teamwork

This need is especially obvious at the secondary school level. The large number of teachers involved requires overall consistency and the team can provide support to individual's efforts.

Support and involvement by the head teacher of the school

The integration plan is above all a school plan. In addition to the involvement of the team of teachers, the entire school is involved: perhaps in terms of its architecture and in its day-to-day functioning (travel, transportation of pupils, meals etc).

Partnership with services and structures providing support and care

The education of young disabled people cannot be delegated to the school alone. Educational, therapeutic, social and even wider pedagogical support is necessary.

Support and regular contact and co-operation with the family

School integration is an educational choice that requires the involvement of the family. The family's active support to the young person and its involvement in the plan undeniably contributes added value.

A generally structured integration plan combined with flexible and adaptable individual plans

Even if educational integration is an educational choice supported by European and national policies as well as by associations of parents of disabled pupils, it must not be forgotten that integration demands major efforts from pupils and requires constant vigilance on the part of the teaching team towards the psychological, emotional, social and scholastic well-being of pupils. The temporary, short-term use of more or less integrative or specialized approaches may be necessary.

Finally, it must not be forgotten that the benefit of educational integration is measured at the end of the process by the professionals involved as well as the wider social integration of the young adult who once experienced integration as a pupil.

5.3 GERMANY

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Anette Hausotter, National Co-ordinator for Germany

5.3.1 Background

The integration of disabled and non-disabled pupils in secondary school has increased in Germany during the last 20 years, even if the framework conditions in Germany are partly unfavourable, as a result of the three-sector school system and the special situation of the federal structure in Germany. As a consequence, this has led to the irregular development of German integration policy in relation to secondary level education. The educational-political conviction does not exist to the same degree across the Bundesländer. Although the integration of pupils with SEN is possible within the law as long as these pupils are able to follow the regular curriculum, integration involving a differentiated curriculum in secondary level education is not yet evident in all of the Bundesländer.

Within this three-sector system of secondary schools (four-sectors if special schools are included) integrative classroom practice has developed differently at the different types of schools. Both the comprehensive schools - *Gesamtschule* - and the basic and practical level schools - *Hauptschule* - have developed good classroom practice in integrated education. In some Länder, there is increasing development of integration in *Realschule* (more extensive general education) and in the *Gymnasium* as well.

At the practical level, there are a variety of different forms of organisation - as well as different regional models - where the goal is to identify appropriate forms and methods for individualisation and differentiation in specialised subjects and simultaneously take account of the integrative elements of social learning and behaviour.

This development has been accompanied by the increasing availability of literature, which provides a critical look at theory and ideas. This maybe through empirical research in the form of model or pilot projects, but also through reports of people involved in the change of, for example, school-climate and educational methods.

As this literature review is focused on classroom practice, essays and books prevail, which - apart from a particular overview - are concentrated on ideas and the realisation of pupil centred and individualised instruction in secondary schools in Germany (mainly with pupils who could only be taught in special schools until recently).

Some basic characteristic conditions and elements of common instruction (joint education) are shown in the following information relating to the secondary school.

5.3.2 *Development and forms of common education in the Sekundarstufe I*

The development of common instruction in the *Sekundarstufe I* is now proceeding in a very discontinuous and contradictory manner. On the one hand, the phase of individual school initiatives seems to be gradually replaced by supra regional or nationwide school initiatives as well as measures covering all areas. On the other hand, overall development is quantitatively still very low and some *Bundesländer* make no effort in this direction at all. In some *Bundesländer* integration in secondary school is a part of the school law; in others it is possible with the same curriculum, or as a pilot/model project, and in some *Länder* integration is only accepted in primary schools.

The proportion of SEN pupils in mainstream schools - looking at all pupils with special educational needs - is clearly smaller than in primary school. From all SEN pupils integrated in mainstream schools (68,430) the biggest proportion is in primary schools: 49,768 compared to 18,662 in secondary schools (*Source: KMK statistische Veröffentlichungen, Heft 159, 3/2002*).

It is clear that the multiplicity of models in classroom practice is increasing. Not only are the borders becoming blurred between individual integration and integration classes, but also in the area of the integration class-model, there are great differences in terms of: the frequencies (17 - 25), the number of the disabled in the class (1 - 6), the personnel ratio (60 - 100% two teacher system) and the development of different forms of instruction. However, the model of 20 + 3 pupils is more common in the urban *Bundesländer*, whilst individual and situation-linked provision is found in the *Bundesländer* with a more rural character.

5.3.3 *Establishment of an inclusive pedagogical concept*

The most concrete difficulties lead to the formation of pedagogical concepts that make the common support of heterogeneous pupil-groupings possible. This common or shared instruction and support is achieved through individualisation and internal differentiation of subject based instruction. The sort of working methods linked to this are, for example, are:

- Project work
- Partner and group work
- Table group work
- Self-controlled (or directed) learning
- Learning at stations
- Weekly schedule planning
- Free working periods.

However, the change towards a working repertoire of more methods is still partial, characterised by small steps and being very individual person dependent. Teacher directed, subject specific instruction is still prevalent in the *Sekundarstufe*.

Mostly, the organisational structures of the comprehensive schools (screen plans, narrow compartmentalised subject teacher principles, external differentiation, clear division of teaching and leisure time areas etc) are still not flexible enough to guarantee the necessary scope for pedagogical changes. In the *Hauptschule*, a

greater degree of flexibility exists. Teachers work in a more multidisciplinary way, so that the teaching team is not so large (e.g. in *Gymnasium* it is possible to find sometimes 9 or 10 teachers working with one class). However the composition of the classes is – as a result of the three-sector school-system - usually even more biased towards slow-learners and pupils with behavioural problems.

5.3.4 *Assessment and evaluation*

Individualised support for different pupils within a shared, common instruction framework should be accompanied by corresponding assessment practice. The criteria for performance and evaluation in the graduation orientated *Sekundarstufe* was obvious from the literature. Individual education development reports and IEP's, even in the few reform schools at the secondary level, rarely push for whole class integration. Mostly, pupils get marks from 1-6 ('very good' through to 'not sufficient'). At other times and in some subjects marks are given with a star - in general for those pupils with learning disabilities and in those subjects where the pupil has been taught by with a special or adapted curriculum. Written reports based on verbal assessments are usually the form of assessment for pupils with intellectual disabilities.

5.3.5 *Transition*

The transition phase is being recognised more and more as a relatively new problem. There are a series of projects currently in existence: initiatives with additional occupation based practical courses; projects with working assistants; co-operation with and modification of BB1O courses (special courses in the tenth grade for preparing pupils for transition, implemented in Berlin and Brandenburg); similar projects in other Bundesländer (partly in co-operation with authorities from youth, welfare and job centres); projects involving school level initiatives between secondary schools in co-operation with vocational schools; projects with special schools working with the local economy and companies.

5.4 GREECE

Venetta Lampropoulou, National Co-ordinator for Greece

Integration in Greece with respect to secondary education is a new area for both research and development. According to the new legislation of 2000 (Act 2817) integration is the most desirable placement. However major problems exist and a new organisational structure with support services and flexible curricula has to be designed.

In spite of the problems encountered at the present time, integration programmes have been established in a number of secondary schools throughout Greece. As a result the number of SEN pupils in mainstream settings has been increased, whilst the number of SEN pupils in special schools is decreasing. The few research projects that have been carried out in Greece in the area of integration at secondary level highlight the lack of support services. For example, SEN graduates from schools for deaf or blind students stressed the need for support services and specialised teachers. They also mentioned the inappropriateness of existing educational programmes for SEN pupils and they strongly believe that the establishment of additional services will promote high quality inclusion in Greece.

Another strong argument regarding the necessity of additional services and the importance of new policy in terms of successful integration is the fact that a number of SEN pupils leave school at the secondary level because their teachers do not have the background knowledge to assist them.

A further problem that is underlined by the research findings is the negative attitudes that regular school teachers hold towards SEN students. However, young teachers seem to be more open and positive towards SEN students and their integration.

Furthermore, research reveals that pupils with positive attitudes towards SEN pupils adopt a positive attitude towards school integration as well. This means that there is a positive correlation between attitude towards SEN students and integration in general.

Finally, the results of a study conducted by the HELIOS programme pointed out that factors such as limited funding and restricted use of new technology in classrooms may constitute an immense obstacle for the realisation of successful integration.

5.5 The NETHERLANDS

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Sip Jan Pijl, National Co-ordinator for the Netherlands

5.5.1 Introduction

For several decades the vast majority of Special Educational Needs (SEN) students in the Netherlands attended special schools. During the last ten to fifteen years a growing number of parents have wanted their SEN child to be integrated in regular education. Regulations introduced in 1985 made this possible for a restricted group of SEN pupils/students. These regulations catered for a form of peripatetic teaching in regular schools by special school teachers. In later years these regulations were improved and extended. In 2002, about 3000 or 0.3 per cent of students were integrated in regular secondary education.

New SEN laws and regulations came into force in August 2003. These introduced the pupil-linked budget for every SEN pupil and student that can meet certain special education criteria. This makes it easier for a child with SEN to be integrated into regular education because the new legislation has less restrictions and supports integration.

This short history of Dutch integration implies that research findings on effective inclusive practice, based on research data collected in the Netherlands, is limited. However, the information that is available on this subject has been studied and reviewed here. The literature review considered the following questions:

- What arrangements and factors within the context of the curriculum (classroom practice, teaching methods, educational organisation and so on) are considered essential for helping SEN students in mainstream secondary classrooms?
- What is known about the outcomes of these approaches (at pupil level)?
- What are the main problems (at classroom practice, school organisation and teacher level) in the Netherlands within secondary mainstream classrooms regarding including SEN students?
- Which groups of SEN students cause the most problems within mainstream settings and why?

5.5.2 Methodology

In order to find an answer to the first two questions a search for relevant academic articles and books in the databases 'ERIC 1992-2002' and 'PsychINFO 1992-2002' was conducted. The descriptors 'special needs' or 'disabilities' or 'behaviour problem' or 'handicap' and 'mainstreaming' or 'inclusive education' or 'integration' or 'integrated' and 'secondary education' and 'Holland' or 'Dutch' or 'Netherlands' were used. These (more general) descriptors were chosen because the descriptors in the framework for this classroom practice study were too specific: using these resulted in no matches at all in the literature search.

The searches led to 36 articles or chapters in books. Some of these proved to be irrelevant. Some dealt with inclusive education in other countries, but were selected because the name 'Holland' was used; others were not about (secondary) education, did not address students with handicaps or impairments, or dealt with vocational education. After a first selection phase, 18 articles/books seemed relevant according to the descriptions. However, after ordering and studying the documents it appeared that most of these were far too general and did not actually deal with classroom practice. Finally, there was one book that was relevant on the topic of classroom practice for educating SEN students in mainstream secondary schools, but unfortunately it did not contain outcomes of the approaches.

To find more articles and books about the subject an additional search was carried out in the Dutch Education Data Base (*Pica*) with the descriptors 'voortgezet onderwijs' (secondary education) and 'integratie' (integration). This search revealed two relevant books.

By using the descriptor 'ambulant teaching' two more books were found in the database of Dutch libraries about the subject. The five relevant books have been systematically described and are summarised in the Appendix.

The answers to the last two questions were even more difficult to find. Although in the past decades a growing number of students have been integrated in secondary education, research about the problems and outcomes of integrating such students is limited. In an attempt to complete the data set every article in six professional journals was analysed. The six most relevant Dutch professional journals on special needs education were selected: *Didaktief & School* (1995-2001); *Jeugd, School en Wereld* (1998-2001), *Speciaal Onderwijs* (1998-1999), *Tijdschrift voor Orthopedagogiek* (1999-2001), *Uitleg* (1997-2001) and *Van horen zeggen* (1995-2001). By analysing every article on data about integrating SEN students in secondary education a few relevant articles were found.

5.5.3 Classroom practice and outcomes

This section addresses the available data on classroom practice and outcomes of integrating special needs students in regular secondary schools. Different approaches were used in integrating these students, such as 'peripatetic supervision', 'preventive peripatetic supervision' and 'part-time education' and more general 'co-operation between regular and special secondary schools'. Most of the studies do not focus on the effects or outputs in terms of academic achievement, emotional outcomes or social behaviour of students educated in regular schools, but report on the perceptions of teachers and other staff involved.

Kool and Derriks (1995) studied the relationship between peripatetic supervision (ambulant teaching) and its effects at student level. This situation makes it possible for special school teachers to visit mainstream schools to work with special needs students and to support classroom teachers. Twenty-five secondary schools participated in the study. Within each school one ambulant teacher was selected. Two students and their classroom teachers assigned to each ambulant teacher were asked to participate. A total of 47 secondary education students were selected: 25 students with severe and 22 with mild handicaps. Ambulant teachers and school

directors were invited to complete questionnaires. The findings indicated that most students who received ambulant teaching performed in accordance with, or above, expectations. Compared to their non-handicapped peers, between 54 and 69% of these students achieved an average or above average level in reading, spelling, maths and Dutch language. Concerning social-emotional functioning, no decrease was reported for at least 89% of the students; 87% of students were considered to be motivated. Overall, 89% of students are successfully included. Students who were not successfully included were mainly severely mentally impaired.

Another study about peripatetic supervision was carried out by Oudenhoven and Romijn (1998). This study focused on specific groups of students, namely deaf or hearing impaired and students with severe speech disorders in regular secondary education. 89 students received peripatetic supervision from appropriate special schools. A sample of schools receiving peripatetic supervision was drawn up consisting of 43 secondary schools of which only 17 (1 school with deaf students, 12 schools with hearing-impaired students and 4 schools with students with severe speech disorders) participated. The researchers also took a sample of parents who were involved: 41 parents were in the sample and 29 participated. Data on how schools, teachers, students and their parents perceived peripatetic supervision was collected by telephone interviews. Some findings about the content of the peripatetic supervision were discussed with the schools. According to parents the peripatetic supervision was good; for deaf and hearing-impaired students it was a little better than for students with severe speech disorders. Parents perceived that students had some problems in understanding the lessons, but they hardly had any problems in feeling at home at school, in their contacts with classmates and adults and in their behaviour at school. Generally, students with severe speech disorders seem to experience less problems compared to deaf or hearing-impaired students.

Oudenhoven and Baarveld (1999) studied the way in which integrating handicapped students in regular secondary schools has evolved. They were also interested in the opinion of teachers and support staff on the effects of integration and searched for hindering and stimulating factors for successful inclusion. Sixty-nine school directors and 55 ambulant teachers of 69 handicapped students in mainstream secondary schools completed questionnaires and the ambulant teachers were also interviewed. Most of the schools made special practical organisational arrangements in order to support special needs students in the classroom. In general, no special didactical arrangements were made and 60% of these students used the same materials as non-handicapped peers. Most handicapped students participated in the whole educational and activity timetable. Some of them received extra support from ambulant teachers. Almost all school directors thought that including these students resulted in an increase in a teacher's expertise, but also a greater willingness to integrate handicapped students. According to teachers, students felt accepted in the school and had good relationships, especially with adults. The opinion of teachers towards the behaviour and self-confidence of the students was also positive. Teachers made less positive judgements about academic achievement and social skills. Important factors for integrating handicapped students in secondary schools were personal skills such as an ability to communicate well, being able to eat and drink without support, mobility and intellectual skills.

From 1999 all secondary schools for regular and special education were grouped into regional clusters to co-operate with each other in order to enhance the possibilities for integrating secondary school special needs students into regular education. Before 1999 some schools had already started working together in clusters. Berkenbosch (1997) studied the co-operation of those school clusters and also investigated the effects of this. Documents have been analysed and 66 of the 85 co-ordinators of the regional clusters completed questionnaires. The findings indicate that half the clusters had made arrangements to stimulate the co-operation between regular and special secondary schools.

The most important activities that were started as part of the co-operation between regular and special secondary education included pedagogic-didactic measures i.e. remedial teaching, use of programmes to solve problems (70% of clusters), preventive peripatetic supervision (90% of clusters), part-time regular schooling for handicapped students (59% of clusters), taking courses to improve knowledge about handicapped students (97% of the clusters) and making appointments to refer students (58% of the clusters).

The co-ordinators thought that:

- Both peripatetic and preventive peripatetic supervision led to a higher number of students obtaining a regular certificate (81%), less referrals to secondary special education schools (66%), teachers in regular secondary schools becoming more willing to accept differences between students when teaching (57 and 49% respectively) and a higher number of regular secondary schools having a more specific policy on dealing with handicapped students (54 and 38% respectively).
- Part-time regular and part-time special secondary education resulted in making a switch from special to regular education easier (91%), changing the attitude of teachers towards differences between students in the classroom (46%) and in specifying regular school policies to deal with handicapped students (44%).
- The newly developed placement options in the projects enabled students to attend an appropriate educational setting (86%).
- The effect of co-operation between regular and special secondary schools was that students were not referred to special education schools (41%), that the knowledge of teachers on educating special needs students was enhanced (60%) and that schools changed their policy towards having special needs students (59%).

The *Thema groep 9 (1996)* study report described four Dutch examples of good practice within the framework of grouping secondary schools to enhance co-operation. The first involved three special secondary schools working together with one regular school. Students with learning, behavioural and social-emotional problems were the target group. The project focused on working with IEPs, adapting the curriculum to students' needs, working in small groups and part-time placements in regular schools. According to *Thema groep 9 (1996)* schools succeeded in establishing co-operation between mainstream and special education schools and the reported number of special education referrals had reduced.

In the second example, five special secondary schools collaborated with five regular schools. For students with learning, behavioural and social-emotional problems activities were developed such as support for students referred back from special to

regular schools, remedial teaching, using special teachers in regular classrooms and part-time placements in regular schools. The authors reported that co-operation between the schools in this project was successful too.

The third example included two projects for physically handicapped students that focused on closer co-operation at school level between mainstream and special education and on part-time placements in regular schools in order to integrate special needs students. With the exception of full team involvement, the projects met the targets set.

The last example from *Thema groep 9 (1996)* involved two special secondary schools working with seven regular ones. The project focused on students with dyslexia as well as learning, behavioural and social problems. Project activities consisted of teacher training in special needs subjects. After two or three years of special education the students were integrated in regular schools while being supported by special school staff. The authors report an increase in the number of students integrated in regular schools.

Unfortunately the *Thema groep 9 (1996)* does not contain evidence based information about results in terms of academic achievement, emotional outcomes or social behaviour but included only perceptions of the participants.

Classroom practices and outcomes were also described in professional journals. The next section contains an overview of these.

Three regular secondary schools started to work together in integrating students with learning disabilities, as there was no special secondary school for these students. Every school specialised in different types of problem areas: one in behavioural problems, one in providing students in need of intensive individual support and the third in learning problems. Students participated in the regular education timetable, but were tutored by special teachers, worked in small groups (especially the students with behaviour difficulties) and were offered an adapted curriculum (Schoor, 1995a).

Notebomer (1995) describes co-operation between twelve regular secondary schools and one special secondary school. The aim of the co-operation was to enhance the possibilities of coping with handicapped students and to support them in regular secondary education. To achieve this, they used preventive peripatetic supervision, stimulated development of expertise and made an agreement about referral policies. In daily practice the strategy most used was preventive peripatetic supervision. Two ambulant teachers from the special secondary school supported the students: one in relation to social-emotional problems and the other for didactic issues. According to Notebomer (1995) the results of this policy were positive. Most students with one hour a week preventive peripatetic supervision were able to stay at regular secondary education schools. Only two students in the past five years have been referred to a special secondary school.

Kool & Derriks (1996) are also positive about preventive peripatetic supervision for students in regular schools and peripatetic supervision for students from special schools in regular ones. After one year 88% of the students with peripatetic supervision were integrated well into regular secondary schools. Most of them

functioned as expected or even better, not only with regard to academic skills but also to social-emotional skills.

Another initiative was developed by a special secondary school for learning disabled students. The school took two years to integrate their students into regular secondary schools. During these two years the students attended lessons one day a week at a regular school in the neighbourhood. After these two years students were ready to integrate completely into regular secondary schools (Wevers, 1995).

Schoor (1995b) describes the collaboration between one regular secondary school, one special secondary school for learning disabled students and one special secondary school for mild mentally retarded students. The students attended part-time regular and part-time special secondary education. Students from special schools were offered more job opportunities and students from regular schools took advantage of the extra attention from special school teachers. A negative effect was that some special needs students reacted to part time regular school placement by demanding more attention, being more aggressive, showing more deviant behaviour or by developing a fear of failure.

In 1997 Van den Bosch published an article about co-operation between one regular and one special secondary school (*Living Together Apart*). The schools started part-time regular and part-time special secondary education, peripatetic supervision and complete integrated classes from the special school into the regular one. The effect was that fewer students were referred to special education than before the co-operation.

Bais (1997) reported that a hearing impaired student (17 years) and a physically handicapped student (15 years) were successfully integrated in regular education. The school appointed a mentor and made relatively small changes to classroom practices (more time for tests, communication equipment, asked classmates to support the special needs students).

Without being based on empirical data Selter (1996) addresses factors that may enhance the successful integration of hearing impaired students in regular secondary education. Factors at class level include an orderly and quiet climate, a good atmosphere in the group and individual attention. Factors at teacher level include positive attitude towards handicapped students, the readiness to get to know more about the handicap and the readiness to pay extra attention to the handicapped child.

De Wit-Gosker (1991) divides factors important for successful integration into those at school, class and pupil level. Factors at school level include accessibility, organisation, differentiation, extra teachers, extra materials and school climate. Factors that can influence integration at class level include jealousy, lack of understanding, accepting no help or always expecting everything from classmates. Factors at pupil level include personality and past experiences.

5.5.4 *Problems in regular secondary education*

A thorough analysis of the educational journals provides some insight into the problems associated with integrating special needs students into Dutch regular secondary schools.

In a cluster where 12 regular and one special school worked together to improve the education of special needs students, the target group was limited to students with problems that could be addressed (remedied). In the opinion of the schools it was not possible to integrate students with complex problems because teachers did not have enough time or expertise to cope with these (Notebomer, 1995).

Straathof (2000) was interested in students with Down's syndrome in secondary schools. He foresaw problems in both regular and special schools in integrating these students. In a regular secondary school it takes extra effort to keep in touch with other classmates and integrate socially within the class. For students who attended a regular primary school it is difficult to attend a special school. It is possible that students do not get what they were used to concerning intellectual and social skills and don't develop anymore. To prevent these problems Straathof (2000) mentions factors that influence successful integration in regular secondary education. Students with Down's syndrome that can be successfully integrated are able to read well (technically), are not spoiled by too much personal attention and are capable of working independently. Furthermore, it is important to pay attention to the goals parents have for their child, as sometimes these goals are not realistic. Another problem Straathof (2000) mentioned is that parents sometimes underestimated their contribution to successful integration. At times parents expected too much from the school or have opinions different from the school's. It is therefore considered wise to discuss these expectations before a school admits a student with Down's syndrome.

Sliepenbeek (1995) studied deaf students in regular secondary schools and discovered that not all deaf students and teachers at special schools for deaf students are capable of estimating what requirements are necessary within the different types of regular secondary education. Some deaf students have extensive problems in connecting and communicating with classmates and teachers who aren't deaf.

Data on the types of students with special needs that cause the most problems within regular secondary education is not available.

5.5.5 *Summary: what works?*

In the Netherlands about 450 regular secondary schools have integrated one or more special needs students (Oudenhoven & Baarveld, 1999). Currently, this is a minority of the total group of special needs students. Most students still attend a form of special education. Data on the arrangements used in integration and their effects is limited.

Initiatives that started for handicapped students are based on a combination of part-time special and part-time regular secondary education; (preventive) peripatetic supervision; working with IEP's; working in small groups; adaptations to the

curriculum and on improving teacher expertise. Most of these initiatives take place within co-operation clusters between regular and special secondary schools. Until now little is known about the effects of these approaches at pupil level. The findings from scientific research about the outcomes in terms of academic achievement, emotional outcomes or social behaviour mostly reflect the perceptions of the schools and contain no evidence-based information.

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5.6 NORWAY

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5.6.1 Background

The European Agency's aim with this literature review was to identify possible models for good classroom practice in inclusive settings and to shed light on the effect these have on pupils with special educational needs (SEN). Having reviewed the literature that exists in Norway regarding this field, it proved difficult to discover models that had been tried out and information presented on the effect of these models. The approach used for this literature overview has therefore been adapted to examining literature and the research conducted in the field of good classroom practice and inclusion. This has involved highlighting the characteristics of what works and how this may contribute to the development of good practice using this material as a starting point. By way of introduction, a brief account is provided of the general conditions in the Norwegian school system that are of significance when it comes to good classroom practice and the inclusion of pupils with special needs. The main purpose of this account is to describe the basis that exists for developing good classroom practice that promotes inclusive education. During the 1990s, comprehensive changes took place within the Norwegian school system with respect to this field. This account will also be closely tied in with the information that is covered in the literature overview.

Today, the main aim of Norwegian schools is to provide a school for all with individually adapted and inclusive education. During the 1990s the perspective shifted from integration to inclusion. This development was in line with developments internationally. However, the difference between integration and inclusion in Norway is minimal. This has much to do with the fact that the definition of integration that has been used also implies inclusion. The definition of integration that is used in Norway is as follows:

- The pupil will belong to the group
- The pupil will share in the benefits that being part of the group provides
- The pupil will have joint responsibility for tasks and obligations.

Given that this aim has formed the basis for the integration of pupils with special needs since the early 1970s, Norway is familiar with the concept of inclusion. The work of striving for the goal of inclusive education for all pupils has therefore been ongoing for a prolonged period of time. Meanwhile, the reforms in the 1990s led to comprehensive changes in schools, as far as both content and structure are concerned. This has led to re-organisation that has had consequences for special pedagogical initiatives for pupils with special needs. The special state schools have been closed down and all pupils with special needs should now be included in the mainstream school system and belong to a class. The government has established special pedagogical support services that are intended to provide expert advice and guidance to local school owners (local authorities), pedagogical-psychological advice services, schools and teachers so that they can increase their skills within the field of inclusion and help to ensure that pupils with special needs receive individually adapted tuition in a class context.

Changes to the law have given pupils with special needs distinct rights as part of assisting inclusion in the classroom. What follows is a brief review of the legislation that is relevant as far as inclusion as part of a class for pupils with special education needs is concerned.

Inclusive education and belonging to a class

Pupils with special needs receive tuition at their local school in their home county. Pupils also belong to the class they would otherwise belong to given their age. These legal rights were established by law in 1998 (Education Act, sections 8-1 – 8-2) and mean that pupils should preferably receive tuition in the social context of a class in the area in which they live.

Adapted tuition and special education

When the new Education Act came into force in 1998, it gave all pupils the right to receive tuition specifically adapted for them, within a class context. This means that individual pupils receive tuition that has been adapted to their abilities and aptitudes (Education Act, section 1-2). In addition the right to special education for pupils with special needs was maintained and these pupils thus have a distinct right (Education Act, section 5-1) to special education. This entitlement to special education in the school is triggered if a pupil has a learning difficulty due to a sense related disability (e.g. hearing disability, visual disability, physical disability) and/or a learning difficulty that may be general or specific in nature (linguistic, dyslexia, dyscalculia), a combination of learning difficulties, or behavioural problems. The fact that special education focuses on diagnosis and learning difficulties can present a dilemma and in some cases appear stigmatising. However 'diagnosis' is also necessary in order to be able to plan specific educational programmes, which are adapted to a pupil's need for support.

Individual education plans for pupils with special needs

The entitlement to an individual education plan is established by law in section 5-5 of the Education Act. This section applies to pupils who have received an individual decision in their favour concerning the right to special education based on an expert assessment made on the basis of a medical and/or special pedagogic diagnosis. Examples of such diagnoses are mentioned above.

Inclusive schools that make room for all pupils to participate in and belong to a class, means that Norwegian schools have a wide diversity of pupils. This imposes a responsibility on a school and its teachers to organise tuition for diverse groups of pupils with varying degrees of need for individual adaptation within the framework of a class. The group of pupils can vary as far as the aptitudes of pupils are concerned in different areas, such as, for example:

- Pupils with a range of development profiles from those with particularly good abilities to those with learning difficulties
- Pupils with a need for tuition in different areas of development
- Pupils with different ways of learning and styles of working.

In Norway, a school for all means a pupil's education and development has to be viewed from two different perspectives. On the one hand, the tuition must be individually adapted and on the other hand take place within the context of a class. Inclusion does not necessarily imply that the tuition is adapted to individuals. Most

often, inclusion first and foremost has to do with the fact that the tuition takes place within the context of a class and is thus centred on the learning environment in which the teaching takes place, while adapted tuition is about both organising and following up the individual pupil's learning process and the learning environment in which the teaching takes place. Adapted tuition applies to all pupils in Norwegian schools, including pupils with special aptitudes and those with special needs. In the case of pupils with special needs, individual adaptations should be made during periods of both mainstream education and special education.

Pupils with special needs have precedence over other pupils. The entitlement to an individual education plan can entail a stronger focus on individual adaptation. Such an education plan must be prepared on the basis of a thorough assessment of a pupil's current development and the need to organise things in such a manner that they encompass the pupil's entire education. The inclusion work for pupils with special education needs involves making distinct choices in a number of areas, such as, for example:

When should the pupil receive special tuition? During all or parts of their education?

How should this special tuition take place? Through one-to-one teaching, group teaching, class teaching or different combinations of these?

How can the special tuition be organised to take account of the need for individual adaptation? Areas they master as a basis for ensuring a pupil's development and education.

Which methods are suitable and contribute to a pupil's development? Individual training tasks, problem based tasks, practice related tasks, relevant long-term strategies, process oriented co-operative learning, etc.

Individually adapted tuition in the context of an inclusive classroom has consequences for how teachers organise their teaching in several areas. Here are a few examples of such areas:

- Choice and preparation of syllabus
- Organisation of teaching activities
- organisation of the learning environment
- Forms of work and social interaction.

This background description attempts to shed some light on the situation in Norway regarding the field of classroom practice and the inclusion of pupils with special education needs. Inclusion is based on a school's teaching being adapted as far as possible to an individual's needs and the fact that the tuition should take place in the context of a class. In other words, pupils with special needs form part of the pupils as a whole and the diversity of pupils that a class is comprised of. If a pupil's aptitude for learning and level of maturity do not conform to the curriculum being taught in the year the pupil belongs to given his or her age, this can hamper the work of inclusion. The challenge Norwegian schools face is to create an inclusive school and avoid learning difficulties developing or leading to stigmatisation. This requires a great degree of tolerance as far as accepting differences is concerned. The tolerance of differences, flexibility and variation will have an effect on the degree to which a school and its teachers succeed in achieving the goal of inclusive education and a school for all. Some of the research results that will be looked at more closely in this overview touch upon most of the points presented in this background description.

5.6.2 Data collection methods

The main points mentioned in the background description are very relevant when it comes to the research into good classroom practice and inclusion that is occurring in Norwegian schools. The choice of areas for data collection for this literature overview was linked to these main points. Based on the Norwegian schools system, the 11-14 years old age group that this literature overview covers is located in the transitional stage between the upper primary and lower secondary stages. It is difficult to focus exclusively on this age group due to the way the education system is organised in Norway: first and foremost because this age group is in the transitional phase between two stages, but also because primary and lower secondary education are dealt with by the same laws and legislation. Most of the research that has been conducted has not been associated with specific age groups, but with primary and lower secondary education in general. Most of the research reports dealt with the entirety of primary and lower secondary education, but also selected a phase of primary and lower secondary education as well, e.g. lower secondary school.

The themes that are natural to emphasise vis à vis the data collected are those associated with the fields that have been the focus of research during 1990-2002. The aim of collecting the data was to obtain the results of these research programmes, which were often initiated by the Ministry of Education. Comprehensive assessments were made of the school reforms during the 1990s in order to gain an insight into the development that had taken place due to the reforms. The research topics that it was important to collect data about in connection with these were:

- Inclusion that contributes to participation in the class with a focus on what promotes an individual pupil's learning and development
- Classroom practice that contributes to adapted tuition for pupils with special needs
- Pupil adapted and inclusive tuition in the class associated with learning difficulties and various types of difficulty
- Individual education plans and their significance in relation to the development of well-adapted and inclusive tuition for pupils with special needs.

The aim of collecting data for this literature overview was to obtain Norwegian literature about these fields that contained research about the 11-14 year old age group in Norwegian primary and lower secondary schools. Two methods were employed to obtain the data: searches in Bibsys and references from specialists.

Bibsys search results

The first phase of the data collection involved searching Bibsys (the database for the universities and university colleges in Norway). Searches were performed for the following subjects: inclusion, adapted tuition and classroom research. However, these provided less than satisfactory results. The database contained little information both when it came to tuition for all pupils and for pupils with special needs. Most of the literature found proved to be textbooks and it was difficult to find research-based literature. A more advanced search provided better results. This involved other subjects and sub-subjects associated with this field. This required familiarity with the field, relevant researchers, research environments and research programmes. Employing more advanced searches on authors' names that were

known from the author's own research in this field provided subtler, more varied and research based results.

In this context the relevant research programmes were those programmes that were associated with the re-organisation of special education and the primary and lower secondary school reforms. Three of these are especially relevant in this context. These are:

- Evaluation of the Reorganisation of Special Education Project 1993-1996 (*Evaluering av prosjektet omstrukturering av spesialundervisningen 1993-1996*)
- The development of special pedagogic knowledge and measures 1993-1999 (*Spesialpedagogisk kunnskaps- og tiltaksutvikling 1993-1999*)
- Evaluating reform 97 (*Evaluering av reform 97*)

References from specialists

Following the search using Bibsys, the next phase involved obtaining data through people who were familiar with this field. Here, other research colleagues who had researched this field were used. Their familiarity with the field gained through being a researcher and participant in one of the special pedagogic research programmes on special pedagogics provided us with access to a number of research reports from the period 1995-1997.

Data was collected about inclusion/integration, classroom research, special education and pedagogics, individual education plan work, adapted tuition, learning and learning difficulties, specific difficulties that hamper learning and development, behavioural difficulties, etc. This provided a broad spectrum of literature to choose between and most of it related to inclusion within a classroom context.

5.6.3 Summary of the results

The main focus of this summary of the results will be on what works. The research that was conducted in Norway in the 1990s into good classroom and the inclusion of pupils with special needs was mainly concerned with how the re-organisation of special education has contributed to a greater degree of inclusion. Various general areas of education in schools to do with pupil adapted tuition and learning environments are also focused on. A relatively concerted effort has been made as far as research is concerned and this has formed the basis for shedding light on various aspects of behavioural problems in schools, while less attention has been paid to specific aspects of the inclusion of pupils with special education needs linked to different types of difficulties. One of the weaknesses of much of the research is that it is based on teacher assessments and takes little account of users' experiences and incidents. Few of the projects are based on pupils' assessments. The idea behind this literature review was to bring to the fore a variety of research projects and an attempt has been made to provide a varied description and draw correlations in order to contribute to creating as best an overall picture as possible of classroom practice and the status of inclusion in Norway. The main areas that have been selected in order to highlight good classroom practice and the inclusion of pupils with special needs in this literature overview are:

- Good inclusion practice that contributes to participation in the class and encourages an individual pupil's learning and development

- Good classroom practice that contributes to adapted tuition for pupils with special needs
- Good pupil adapted and inclusive tuition in the classroom associated with learning difficulties and various types of impairment
- Individual education plans and the importance of the development of well-adapted and inclusive tuition for pupils with special needs.

5.6.4 What encourages good inclusion practice in the classroom?

In this section the inclusion of pupils with special needs and participation in the classroom, focusing on what encourages individual learning and development is examined.

The “Evaluating special education” (*“Evaluering av spesialundervisning”*) project (Skårbrevik, 1996), which was conducted in connection with the decision to close down state run special schools, highlights the importance of the re-organisation on inclusive classroom practice in schools. Here the results of two comparative surveys undertaken at two different times - 1993 and 1996 - were available. Skårbrevik highlighted the degree to which there had been an improvement in the work of inclusion as a consequence of the re-organisation of special education. Skårbrevik found significant changes and improvement with respect to the fact that during the course of this period more pupils received adapted, local tuition of equal worth. The results showed a positive development with respect to providing pupils with special needs with adapted, locally based tuition of equal worth. An increase of 10% occurred during the period 1993 - 1996.

As far as the organisation of the tuition on offer and the benefit pupils got from it are concerned the results were positive. Key aspects of adapted and inclusive tuition for pupils with special needs were considered in order to consider the degree to which these were being satisfied. Below is a list of the areas that were surveyed and the percentage that answered yes:

Sufficient scope of special tuition	48%
Adapted to pupil’s education needs	60%
Resources available for tuition conform with expert assessment	70%
Pupil benefits from the tuition	78%
Teacher has sufficient skills	53%
Tuition makes it possible for pupils to participate in what is going on in the class	62%
The class environment encourages social integration	52%
The teaching offered encourages the pupil’s personal growth	67%

A majority support the idea that pupils with special needs receive and benefit from adapted and inclusive tuition in the class. It is important here to emphasise the high percentage (78 per cent) who believe that pupils benefit from this tuition because this is a significant factor when it comes to assessing whether tuition has been adapted for an individual.

Parents’ assessment of pupils’ progress is positive. A majority (67.2 per cent) believes it is good and a minority (14.5 per cent) believes it is poor. As far as the level

of enjoyment is concerned, 92 per cent of the parents believe that it is good or very good. The results indicate that the parents' assessment is that schools are making better progress with respect to social inclusion than with academic progress.

It would also be relevant in this context to look at "An assessment of whether the introduction of L 97 has led to schools developing inclusive practices: academic, social and cultural" (*"En vurdering av om innføringen av L 97 har ført til at skoler har utviklet en inkluderende praksis, faglig, sosialt og kulturelt"*), a project conducted by Skogen, Nes & Strømstad. The project is now in its final phase and the final report is not yet available (the final report will be printed in 2003). However, a number of unpublished preliminary reports exist and these have been used for this literature review. The results from these so far indicate that:

- The main players in schools, school managers, teachers, etc, do not have a uniform and common understanding of the term inclusion
- Classroom practice varies greatly
- Inclusive practice is undergoing gradual development
- The degree to which the reform (97) has influenced this development is unclear.

As far as succeeding with inclusion is concerned, it would appear that the following factors are decisive. Successful inclusion requires a great degree of:

- Adapted tuition within three areas: academic, social and cultural
- Good pupil/pupil and pupil/teacher relationships
- A sense of belonging
- Participation
- Influence
- Co-operation between pupils
- Co-operation between teachers and pupils
- Co-operation between teachers.

The main conclusion from this project is that inclusive practice in the classroom is developing. Academic, social and cultural pupil adapted tuition are key factors when assessing good classroom practice. Central to this is also ensuring that all pupils experience good relationships and a sense of belonging, pupil participation and influence and good conditions for working together in order to assist the development of good classroom practice.

In the "School and interaction difficulties" (*"Skole og samspillsvansker"*) project (Nordahl and Sørli, 1998) the correlation between relational conditions in the class and the significance this has for pupils' academic skills is examined. This was done on the basis that education is not exclusively a question of the communication and acquisition of academic knowledge. This means that the school is an arena for personal development through an active process of interaction between people. The development of a good learning environment and a good relationship between the pupil and teacher is deemed to be an important aspect of inclusion in a class. It was thus expected that relational factors would also be of significance for academic learning. The results from the survey showed however that there was little correlation between whether pupils did well or poorly academically and whether they had a good or poor relationship with their fellow pupils or teachers. On the other hand, there were clear correlations when it came to poor self-confidence and poor relationships in the

school and between positive self-esteem and positive relationships. There was a moderate correlation between how pupils assessed their social skills and their relationships with fellow pupils and teachers. Consequently self-image and relationship building seem to be key to a teacher's development of good classroom practice for all pupils including pupils with special needs.

This study also looked at how significant pupils' positive or negative view of a school was in relation to teaching. Here pupils differentiated between their social life at the school and how they enjoyed the teaching. The results showed that *the teaching situation bored many pupils. Whilst the majority of pupils liked being at school and enjoyed it.* However, in the pupils' opinion there was a correlation between the teaching in a school, enjoyment at school and their attitude to school and teaching. Pupils who did not enjoy being taught and who did not view school and teaching as important had a clear tendency to display problematic behaviour at school. One of the main challenges therefore is to organise the teaching situation in such a manner that it is perceived to be meaningful for the pupils and so that pupils do not develop behaviour that hampers their academic development.

Sørli (1997) found, among other things, in the same project "School and interaction difficulties" that problem behaviour in school is linked to individual and contextual factors. Individual factors are here linked to pupils' aptitudes, for example self-image, academic and social skills. Contextual factors are linked to things such as the class environment, the content of teaching and ways of working, participation in decision-making and the clarity of rules. Socio-economic factors associated with the environment in which pupils grow up in appear to have little significance when it comes to how pupils behave at school. The participation of pupils in decision-making and the clarity of rules did not appear to be greatly significant either. Problem behaviour is related to both pupils' skills level and structural and qualitative factors relating to academic and social teaching factors.

In another research project about "Pupil behaviour and learning environments" (*"Elevatferd og læringsmiljø"*) Ogden (1998) found that academic underachievement was more common than behavioural problems in schools. 83 per cent of teachers had one or more pupils who underachieved academically, while 58 per cent had one or more pupils with behavioural problems. He also discovered that teachers' assessments of pupils' classroom behaviour were less positive than assessments regarding their motivation, effort and enjoyment, but more positive than assessments regarding ability, maturity and academic achievements. One of the consequences of these findings could be to organise the learning situation in such a way that all pupils develop their academic skills.

5.6.6 Which aspects of good classroom practice contribute to pupil adapted and inclusive tuition?

In this section, the various aspects of good classroom practice that contribute to adapted and inclusive tuition for pupils with special needs will be looked at. The "Pupils' experience of school" (*"Elevenes opplevelse av skolen"*) project will be the starting point. In this project - which forms part of the "Special pedagogic knowledge and measures" (*"Spesialpedagogisk kunnskaps- og tiltaksutvikling"*) (1993-99) research programme - Skaalvik (1998) concentrated on pupils' experiences of

school, seen from a teacher's perspective as well. The results indicated that schools were not managing to cope with the natural variation in pupils' abilities, aptitudes, interests and backgrounds.

Skaalvik examined the need for social support. The level of support needed proved to be lower than academic support was needed. A majority of the pupils who needed academic support were also deemed to need social support. In the 7th grade (12 years old) this was true for 68 per cent of the pupils who needed social support. When the need for social and academic support are looked at together, approximately every fourth pupil needs support of some kind or another. According to the schools' assessment around every fourth or fifth pupil needs specifically adapted tuition. Less than 59 per cent of the variation in the assessment of pupils' need for adapted tuition can be explained by pupils' academic levels. Around every third pupil who, in the opinion of the school needs specifically adapted tuition, receives no such educational offer. The fact that so many pupils are deemed to need special education may indicate that it is difficult for non-specialist teachers to include and provide individually adapted tuition for pupils with special needs.

The results also showed that schools thought that 21 per cent of pupils needed academic support measures. Of these, teachers thought that 13 per cent had needs that could be met through ordinary support measures i.e. without expert assessments from the pedagogic psychology service (PPT) or individual education plans (IOP). The remaining 8 per cent needed special education based on expert assessments by the PPT and individual measures regarding special education. The main reason for the school's assessment of which pupils needed special education was based on the various types of difficulties they had and were categorised as follows for the 7th grade (i.e. 12 years old):

General learning difficulties	52%
Reading and writing difficulties	46%
Maths difficulties	19%
Sense related/physical handicaps	4%

Here general learning difficulties should be considered a broad term. It also includes pupils who are developing slower than would be expected for the year they should belong to on the basis of their age.

Adapted and inclusive tuition means that one has to look at organisation from the perspective of both the individual and the system. This formed part of Skaalvik's survey and the results showed that the organisation of special tuition for pupils with special needs in the 7th grade was as follows:

- 44% lessons alone
- 50% as groups
- 25% with two teachers in the class, and
- 10% with a class assistant.

These figures included some pupils who receive special tuition organised in more than one of these ways, which explains why the total is more than 100 per cent. These results indicated that relatively few pupils with special needs received organised special tuition in the context of a class with two teachers. The great

majority received teaching on their own or as part of a group. There may be several reasons for this. One reason may be that the pupils' learning difficulties are of such a nature that the pupils needed someone with specialist skills and to be taught alone or as part of a smaller group. Another may be that the teachers and special teachers did not possess sufficient skills to create a specially adapted syllabus that can be taught in the class.

The main conclusion of this research report indicates that differentiation and individual adaptation does not characterise all teaching, but it does characterise group tuition in the class. Several earlier research results support these results (Skaalvik & Fossen 1995, Skaalvik & Skaalvik 1996). In this context the number of pupils who need specially adapted tuition will be high. The schools' perception that they are not mastering differentiation and individual adaptation may influence their assessment and as a result produce a higher number than the number really is - this may "create" pupils with special needs. Good classroom practice is characterised by individually adapted and differentiated tuition. A lack of expertise among teachers vis à vis differentiation and individual adaptation in classroom teaching can thus create pupils with special needs. In other words, schoolteachers need better skills so that they are better able to implement pupil adapted and inclusive tuition within a classroom context.

The results of another research project "Quality schooldays for pupils with movement disabilities" (*"Kvalitet i skolehverdagen til elever med bevegesvansker"*) (Siri Wormnæs, 1995) indicate a number of areas that are key with respect to what encourages inclusion and adapted education for pupils with movement disabilities. These are: the experience of mastering something which builds up self-image; social interaction; well-being, touchiness and sensitivity; adapted tuition in the class; use of computers.

Wormnæs' findings concerning what teachers thought was important to emphasise during the work in these areas were:

The experience of mastering something which builds up self-image

The results indicated that teachers were interested in integrated identities and good self-images. They emphasised providing pupils with situations in which they could experience mastering something and which contributed to the development of an environment where pupils respected and included each other in all of the school's activities.

Social interaction

Here the results indicated that in the lower secondary phase there was less physical activity during breaks and that pupils talked with each more. Pupils with movement disabilities were less left out and experienced more social interaction with the other pupils than during primary and middle phases.

Well-being, touchiness and sensitivity

The results in this area indicated that most pupils with movement disabilities seemed to enjoy themselves, though according to teachers they were touchier than others were. This was linked to the feeling of not being able to manage what others could and being different.

Adapted teaching in the class

Here it appeared as if most schools chose models for organising classes in which pupils were not taken out of them very much. The selection of models seemed to have little to do with the pupils' various needs. Practices varied when it came to whether individual education plans should be developed for these pupils. The reason for this may have been that these pupils did not necessarily have learning difficulties, but perhaps needed assistive technology and a greater degree of practical support.

Use of computers

It was striking that only two pupils used computers and their use was not particularly integrated within the rest of their tuition given the fact that this aid is well suited to pupils with movement disabilities.

One of the main conclusions from this survey was that there seemed to be a need for more expertise, awareness and exchanges of experience concerning how various measures can encourage or hinder pupils' social integration. Making physical disabilities seem normal seemed to lead to them becoming invisible. The ambivalence in terms of "equal and unequal" required people to be made aware. Here too, developing self-image and relationships proved to be key to the development of good classroom practice.

5.6.7 Learning difficulties and their consequences for good inclusion practice in a classroom context

The findings from the "Evaluating special education" (*"Evaluering av spesialundervisning"*) project (Skårbrevik, 1996) showed that pupils with more pronounced general learning difficulties and more pronounced reading and writing difficulties have the greatest problems receiving tuition of equal worth in a class. Skårbrevik found that there was little correlation between how pupils functioned socially and various types of learning difficulties. There was a difference at the lower secondary level where pupils managed less well with respect to functioning socially than pupils at primary and middle levels. In general there was a difference between light, moderate and more pronounced disabilities in that the problems associated with social inclusion were greater the more pronounced the disabilities were.

As far as academic achievement is concerned, it can be seen that one third of the pupils who received special education received separate tuition in Norwegian, mathematics and English, while for other subjects the figure is just below 10 per cent. As far as these pupils who did receive separate tuition, around 20 per cent participated in mainstream tuition with little benefit. However, many also participated in mainstream tuition and benefited well from this. This was true for 40 per cent of pupils in the case of mathematics. As far as this subject was concerned, 40 per cent of the pupils received individually adapted tuition. Other subjects in which pupils benefited from participating in mainstream tuition were physical education, domestic science and art. The majority of pupils with special needs displayed academic progress when they received separate tuition and support tuition. In most of the subjects, more than 70 per cent of pupils who received special tuition displayed very good or good progress. These results indicated that in some subjects it is easier to develop individually adapted tuition than in other subjects and that where individual tuition exists, inclusion in the class functions well.

In the “Quality of tuition of pupils with intellectual disabilities” (*“Kvalitet i opplæring av elever med psykisk utviklingshemming”*) research project, Rognhaug (1997 & 1998), Rognhaug examined how pupils with more extensive general learning difficulties (PUH) are included in the class. She conducted several case studies within the 11-14 years old age group. Inclusion in the class for pupils with special needs most often had to do with following the centrally laid down curriculum for the subject as for other pupils. If a pupil’s maturity and learning aptitude was far below the average level for the class, this became another form of inclusion to that which the majority of pupils required. The results from Rognhaug’s survey indicate that the less significant the extent of intellectual disability, the greater the chance there was of fitting in with the centrally laid down framework along with the majority of the class. The greater the intellectual disability, the greater the need for tuition that is based on achieving other educational goals than those laid down in Curriculum 97 and the academic work that takes place in the class. In this context, it is about content and methods from a perspective where the tuition provided should have a functional value in and for the pupil’s life.

5.6.8 Individual education plan work and its significance when it comes to the development of good inclusion in a classroom context

In this section an examination is made of the extent to which individual education plans (IOP) are important for inclusion when viewed from two different perspectives: individual adaptation and participation in a class.

Nilsen’s (1993) doctoral thesis sheds light on two aspects of individual education plans for pupils with special education needs. One aspect was the intention, which is the formal, ideological curriculum, while the other aspect was the practical aspect, which is the perceived and implemented curriculum. Nilsen examined teachers’ attitudes to adapted and inclusive tuition and what correlations this had with the adaptation of tuition and perceived and implemented curricula. He found some common traits in the attitude profile of teachers and that the degree of adaptation to the general tuition was tied to this. The common traits were as follows:

- High degree of approval regarding the intentions of adapted tuition
- High degree of confidence about the implementation and the achievability of the intentions
- Positive caring attitude
- Positive attitude to integration/inclusion.

The results indicated that a great majority of teachers agreed with the intentions that have been laid down. Teachers felt obliged to follow these up in their teaching. At the same time they believed that it was only possible to achieve this to a certain degree and that this meant the necessary changes to how they taught were not being made. The responses to the question about what teachers thought about inclusive education for all pupils within the ordinary class indicated a very broad range of views. The results were as follows:

- 11 per cent fully agreed
- 48 per cent somewhat agreed
- 24 per cent somewhat disagreed
- 17 per cent did not agree at all.

Even though the majority (69 per cent) fully or somewhat agreed, a relatively high percentage (41 per cent) somewhat disagreed or did not agree at all. If one does not agree with the intentions of inclusion, this may prove to be a factor that hinders practice being changed. The results indicated that even if teachers had the right attitudes this did not necessarily mean that they would change the way they taught. It can thus be concluded that teachers' attitudes are important when it comes to initiating inclusive education, but that it is not enough for teachers to have the right attitudes for teaching to change.

In another research project Nilsen (1997) examined teachers' views about the value of individual education plans (IOP) in inclusion work. The results can be summarised as follows:

- Teachers who teach pupils with special needs and participate in the process of developing an individual education plan can encourage mutual reflection and contribute to a common database of information and common attitudes and strategies. This in turn has consequences for the education provided and thus for the *clearer picture from the perspective of the pupil's overall education*
- Individual education plans can contribute to the *individual pupil's needs being focused on to a greater extent*, the tuition consciously being based on a familiarity with the pupil's abilities and aptitudes – both resources and difficulties – and being adapted on the basis of these
- When an *individual education plan contrasts with the class's plan*, they can contribute to both *inclusion* and *differentiation*, so that a pupil receives adapted tuition within the context of a class
- The use of such plans can *contribute to an ongoing and systematic evaluation of a pupil's development and the tuition a pupil is receiving* and provide a basis for the adjustment of methods and tuition.

In their research project "Survey of the tuition pupils and youth with special needs receive in primary and lower secondary school and upper secondary school" (*"Kartlegging av undervisning til barn og unge med særskilte behov i grunnskolen og den videregående skolen"*) Moen and Øie (1994) found that in 1994, 46 per cent of the pupils who received special education had an individual education plan prepared for them. When the positive results from Nilsen's survey regarding the value of individual education plans are considered, the fact that the right of pupils with special needs to an individual education plan is now established by law seems promising for the future. This may contribute to the work of preparing such plans becoming a central means of achieving better classroom practice characterised by individual adaptation and differentiated tuition in the classroom.

5.6.9 Main factors that characterise good classroom practice and inclusive education

By way of conclusion a brief summary is provided of the main points that have been brought to the fore through this literature review. Factors that can contribute to the implementation of good classroom practice with as much adapted and inclusive tuition as possible for pupils with special needs include:

- Teacher attitudes that support the concept of inclusion
- Common understanding among teachers and school managers of what inclusion means

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- Extent of teachers' skills (knowledge and skills)
 - Extent of inclusive tuition in the class
 - Extent of individually adapted tuition in the class
 - Extent of academic, cultural and social adaptation
 - Extent of variation and differentiation in the tuition and work methods
 - Teacher co-operation vis à vis the preparation of individual education plans
 - Relationship work and development of self-image in the class between pupil/teacher and between pupils
 - Degree of well-being and sense of belonging to the class
 - Degree of participation in decision making, activities and involvement
 - Degree of motivation relating to academic learning
 - Extent of meaningful tasks seen from the perspective of mastery
 - Extent to which things are organised to allow individual subject tuition and assignments in the class
 - Adaptation of individual education plans to pupil's abilities and aptitude for learning and educational needs.

5.7 SPAIN

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5.7.1 Introduction

The integrating process in high school started – experimentally - in Spain in 1992-1993, as a consequence of the introduction of the educational system reform, driven by the General Regulation Law for the Educational System, 1990 (1). This law promoted schooling students with special educational needs in mainstream centres. As a result of the law, each student now has the right to receive education that responds to their personal needs and characteristics, in their nearest school. In addition, the law did not foresee the complete disappearance of special education centres, but kept some with the objective that they serve as a bridge towards situations of higher levels of integration whilst promoting students' quality of life, physical, psychological and social welfare. Currently, about 4% of students with special educational needs are schooled in this kind of centre.

High school education includes a compulsory phase (compulsory high school) from 12 to 16 years of age and a post-compulsory phase, from 16 to 18. Students' heterogeneity is quite remarkable in compulsory high school: this is due to a combination of students' school history of success and failure, cognitive and emotional relationships, the very fact of learning prompting a certain self-perception and self-esteem, expectancies regarding success or failure in school learning, etc. This heterogeneity has a decisive influence, not only in the meanings students build about their school experience, but also in the sense they attribute to their own learning process.

Therefore, an appropriate response to diversity in compulsory high school, essentially involves structuring sufficiently varied and flexible learning-teaching situations, so as to allow the highest possible number of students to achieve the highest level of skills as indicated by the objectives for this educational phase framework. More specifically, it involves preparing and structuring in high school centres, ways of organisation, design, development and follow up of the most diverse school activities and tasks possible, offering students different entry and transfer points, that allow for their full involvement and participation (Onrubia, 1993). In summary, responding to diversity implies offering educational experiences adjusted to the individual characteristics of all students, providing a common culture that considers individuality and adopts methodologies that support an individualised learning-teaching process.

It should be pointed out that students with special educational needs linked to sensory and motor problems are the learners who more frequently enter post-compulsory high school, unlike students who have cognitive problems - particularly if they have associated disabilities.

Alongside the whole schooling process in the high school phase, the Orientation Departments (psycho-pedagogic counselling) existing in each education centre pay

special attention to identifying students' educational needs, following up the educational process and facilitating the necessary support for teachers.

In order to meet the special educational needs of students, the Regulation Law for the Educational System proposed to set up a series of ordinary and extraordinary measures such as:

Ordinary

A space for choice or opt-in areas, allowing response to different interests and motivations.

Tutorial action providing individualised follow-up of students.

Plans for Professional Academic Orientation aimed at facilitating students' decision-making processes.

Pedagogic reinforcement as a set of educational activities complementing, consolidating and enriching the mainstream educational action.

Extraordinary

Curricular Diversification programmes consisting of adaptation to the compulsory high school's curriculum in line with the individual needs of certain students and offering an organisation that is different from the general programme

Curricular adaptation or adjustments made to elements of the mainstream educational provision, to respond to the special educational needs of certain students as a continuation to addressing diversity

Social Guarantee Programmes fundamentally aimed at providing basic and professional education to students, so as to allow for their incorporation into active professional life or to follow specific vocational training

Special Vocational Training aimed at students with special educational needs that cannot benefit from some of the measures outlined above.

In spite of these measures, schooling students with special educational needs is not generalised to all centres - in practice, students with special needs are mainly placed in certain high schools concentrating necessary resources. It is expected that this situation will be modified according to the consolidation of the educational system reform.

5.7.2 Methodology

The literature review completed has focused on the examination of recent publications issued in the sphere of attention to diversity (inclusive education) in Spain, particularly selecting – after analysing – those articles referring to studies on inclusive practice and observed results.

The sources consulted were mainly organisations having relevant databases: Real Patronato Library (SIIS), bibliographic resources from different Spanish universities, publications from the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports, as well as consultation documents on research and experiences, conducted in the different Autonomous Communities.

The descriptors used were: *high school education + school integration, inclusive education, special educational needs, attention to diversity, curriculum and multi-cultural.*

The results showed that there was a higher number of papers relating to theoretical statements rather than empirical research or presenting practical experiences. Maybe this is due to the fact that inclusive education in compulsory high schools in Spain is not visible in every centre yet. Therefore, literature is focused on exposing and illuminating issues relating to how to pay attention to diversity, rather than presenting results about the development and evaluation of real experiences.

Similarly, specific areas of focus are not evident in equal proportion: there are many more studies about those subjects relating to sensory problems (mostly auditory), than any other kind of disability. The emerging literature relating to provision for minority cultural groups has been considered, due to the high influx of immigrant students during the last years in Spain.

5.7.3 *Inclusive practice and results at the cognitive, emotional and social level*

The inclusive education movement involves new ways of researching educational practice from a more natural context and considering environmental dimensions, as well as from a consideration of subjective values, thoughts and interpretation of the protagonists of inclusion. This conceptualisation allows for the identification of the needs of students', teachers' and schools', in their own working context. The aim of this identification is to thoroughly understand the situation and setting in order to identify corresponding improvement. These studies analyse – from an interpretative, social and critical approach - the integrative process as a socially constructed process that requires analysis of singular and idiosyncratic problems and situations.

Recent studies conducted by Molinuevo, Grañeras *et al.* (1999) highlight the current changes in the interest about inclusive research in Spain: interest is becoming more and more focused on the study of schools as a whole. In particular, these changes are based on the options of educating every student in mainstream schools, as well as still striving for excellence and quality. This statement underlines the idea that instructional problems cannot be divorced from the whole school context and it is necessary to plan research work about improvement and change in educational organisations or schools. It is clear that students' learning problems are not exclusively derived from their disabilities, but also from the way schools are organised and the features of educational responses in classrooms that are a direct result of school organisation.

Therefore, in the literature reviewed it is evident that cognitive, emotional and social results are directly related to organisational and curricular aspects of school life. In fact, it has been demonstrated that the educational response to minority cultural groups, to populations at social risk and to students presenting different disabilities, requires, on the one hand, the design of a *school educational and curricular project* based on the students' characteristics and shared values and, on the other hand, a *work proposal* within the regular classroom, focused on the design of a flexible curriculum that provides each student with the opportunity to learn in the most natural environment. Therefore, if, in regular classrooms, individualised teaching processes are provided for students, academic performance, social and emotional development and self-perception can improve.

The methodological strategies used in mainstream classrooms attended by students with special needs have highlighted that there are different effects according to the type of educational needs and the programmes' objectives. For example, in the variety and apparent effectiveness of the strategies used to improve social skills of individuals, the diverse research work concludes that variables such as the number of students, the teachers' attitudes and training, are more important than the kind of specific techniques employed. Thus, most research work agrees that the main variables that define a strategy's success or failure are teachers' training and attitude. Therefore, the strategies used by teachers (social skills, programmes implementation, etc.) will mostly depend on their attitude (acceptance, tolerance, stimulation, etc.) regarding the presence of students with special needs and on the kind of behaviour they show in class.

It has been shown that, in theory, there are many teachers that accept integration, but the actual presence of students with difficulties in their classrooms is a completely different thing: in such situations their attitude becomes less positive (Arnaiz *et al.*, 1999-2000). Research from this perspective considers schools are bureaucratic organisations, where teachers face diversity individually, so that it is necessary to look for solutions to the problems centring on co-operation among teachers. Regarding support teachers, it is observed that success in inclusion is closely related to the availability and level of experience of the support teacher. It is also related to the number of support teachers in the school, their professional training and supervision, their level of co-operative work and whether their teaching methods are appropriate to the students' needs (Arnaiz and Castejón, 2001). Therefore, teacher's training is crucial for educational practice to become more and more inclusive.

Other experiences point out that inclusion in regular classes, with support adjusted to the students' special needs in the group context, has a positive influence in their learning process, self-esteem and self-conception and, at the same time, improves their relationship with their class peers.

5.7.4 *Main problems and groups causing most difficulties*

The new organisational and curricular structure of the current educational system has remarkably improved the existing situation regarding school integration. It is possible to highlight the existence of a unique educational system, one unique curriculum, shared goals for all the students, etc. Nevertheless, the implementation of the educational system reform Spain is still experiencing has not been free of difficulties and challenges, particularly in the secondary education phase.

One of the main problems schools currently have centres upon the idea of providing for "diversity", whilst this concept is still closely related to the classical model of characterisation of special education: the medical-psychological model. This viewpoint legitimises a view of special needs as something that exists outside of the class context, imprinting a particular social perception of SEN on everyone involved. This practice is conducted from an individualistic point of view, characterised by the perception of impaired students as the focus of attention and leading to *different, special, segregated* instructional processes that are always directed to the impaired student. Within this scenario, it is very easy to find in classrooms that the work produced by students with special educational needs is outside of the context of their

group/class and to see how these students generally receive support outside the classroom, together with other students of the centre who also have difficulties.

Even though it is true that not every school works the same way – neither do teachers – there is a trend towards this way of thinking about integration. Several studies conducted in León by Díez (1999) - in contrast with others carried out in Castilla in 1997-1998 and 1998-1999, and by Arnaiz and Castejón (2001) in the Murcia Area in 1999-2000 - point out that 86% of the time during which students with special educational needs receive support, it is carried out outside the regular classroom. The reasons that “justify” this reflect the fear some professionals feel in working in a co-operative way in the classroom; the organisational structures of the classroom that prevent simultaneous work of two teachers together; the requirement for inter-professional co-ordination; professionals’ inactivity and stress placed upon learning instrumental knowledge rather than socialising knowledge.

These results indicate that in many contexts, under an integration “banner”, a subtle *disintegration* and segregation is occurring:

“...it seems that some teachers are learning too easily to ‘segregate’ our students; to consider that ‘these’ students belong to the support teacher, the orientation professional, they are the ‘specials’..., that are to be [the responsibility] of other ‘specialists’” (Díez, 1999).

Undoubtedly, the push for inclusion will continue and it is evident that change is not that easy - it should be noted that the Integration Experimental Plan only started in primary school in 1985. Practice coming from the most traditional sphere of special education developed in specialised schools and is strongly rooted. This has undoubtedly influenced the educational practice in mainstream schools. It must be acknowledged that that any change in school takes time, particularly when considering that providing an educational response adjusted to the diversity present in high schools as proposed by the General Regulation Law for the Educational System, requires an organisational and curricular change in the school as well as in teachers’ attitudes, thoughts, and therefore, in their practice. The fact that secondary education is characterised by imposing an excessively academic curriculum on a - wrongly considered - homogeneous group of students, makes it difficult at present to establish curricular adaptation processes for evidently heterogeneous groups of students.

The concept of *inclusive education* means introducing a wider understanding of what has been represented by the term *special education* - it should not be forgotten that not long ago this term exclusively referred to impaired students. Today, the use of the term diversity has a wider meaning - cultural, linguistic diversity, accessing knowledge diversity, social, gender diversity, diversity bound to intra and interpersonal factors or to special educational needs associated with disability and above-normal intelligence - that can help to understand educational action focused exclusively on special students and special schools. Moreover:

“diversity cannot be unilaterally defined, underlining the difference as determined by only one condition (gender, ability, learning rhythm, place of origin, ...), but as the result of a complex peculiar combination of internal and external conditions that cumulate in each individual” (Mir, 1997, 45).

How is this new conception of diversity applied in practice? Even though, on the one hand, a new horizon has opened, on the other hand, many educational practices that are implemented may seem to question everything. The question can be posed: can human heterogeneity and diversity, be assimilated into the concept of special educational needs? Criticism about the use of the concept *special educational needs* is growing every day. Maybe this is due to the sense and connotation that the word “special” imposes to this concept.

It is true that an acknowledgment of the Warnock Report (1978) implies – at least in a theoretical sphere - not employing other more deprecating terms that have previously used. However, it is also true that the connotation of “special” in the meaning of the special educational needs concept is very strong and many people think that it reproduces and perpetuates the meaning of the more classical “special education” concept. This is why critics of the concept demonstrate how it is still trapped within a medical and psychological approach. Students represented by it are still “special”, as the practice they require is “special” and, although the responsibility is shared among tutors and support teachers, there is still a greater responsibility placed upon support teachers.

It could be argued that even though the concept of special educational needs is associated with a new vision of diversity and this is reflected in Spain’s legal framework (General Regulation Law For The Educational System, Royal Decree 696), its practical application is, in many circumstances, not far from the medical model based on deficit, labelling and classification. As in other international contexts, the concept of special educational needs in Spain has become a new category for identifying special students, as it supports:

“...the perception of those pupils ... as a homogeneous group, focusing on the generalisation that they are special” (Vlachou, 1999, 47).

The fact that this concept - at least initially - has been used in bureaucratic, legal, educational and administrative debates related to disability, contributes to the present perception. Moreover, it has been defined as a “disability”, although that is not manifested. This is the reason why integration is often perceived as a practice exclusively bound to impaired students and, consequently, this concept’s inaccuracy facilitates the projection of incoherence related to the development of politics that perpetuates difference and inferiority, promoting exclusive practices.

Some authors explain this conflict referring to the existence of a dual system inside the regular system. A “normal” form of education considered appropriate for the majority of students is perpetuated, alongside a “special” form of education that tries to satisfy those needs supposed to be different in a minority of students.

Many students, due to the fact that they are classified as students with special educational needs are “supposed” to have a disability when they do not actually have one. It can be considered that integration has become a very controversial notion, being absolutely necessary that we identify those barriers that disable even more than the disability itself, with the aim of overcoming them. Maybe this is the reason why the application of integration policies has not developed neutrally; as some authors state; it has, instead, developed within a cultural and political framework of discrimination against the disabled.

This statement highlights the meaning behind the concept of integration: for many teachers it implies that those individuals referred to are considered (and they consider themselves) different and inferior, as they are continuously segregated from mainstream practice. Therefore, as long as “diversity” highlights the idea in teachers’ minds of different students, with different needs requiring different responses from specialised teachers, exclusion processes will remain. At the same time, effort will be spread in a direction that is probably not the most profitable, or the most integrating.

This is why thinking about heterogeneity as a normal situation for the group/class and starting educational planning accordingly, will allow teachers to use diverse instrumental and attitude levels as intra and interpersonal resources that benefit all students. However, the success of high school teachers in providing support for students requiring special attention is still limited. This appears to be due to their lack of training and qualifications and the lack of tradition and experience in this subject matter. Teachers in this educational phase state that they do not have useful or appropriate information to deal with these students.

Another conflicting aspect that makes the educational response harder centres upon high school teachers’ attitudes towards these kinds of students. Many times, because of their lack of knowledge, uncertainty arises; teachers distrust this process and they think the attention given to these students greatly disturbs their work and has a negative effect on their commitment to the other class members.

Therefore, inclusion requires an institutional approach within which general and special education constitute a unitary model for action. Considered in this way, attention to diversity will become a task and responsibility assumed by all and will thus be considered a process of improvement for the whole school and not a closed educational response aimed at a group of students who are assumed to be “special”.

A final issue for consideration here is support: in many circumstances support is considered as a form of delegation and separation instead of a co-operation process of shared responsibilities that guarantee equity principles (Parrilla, 1996; Parrilla and Daniels, 1998). This process is one where teachers should not be:

“... performing another important function: separating normal students from conflicting ones, delegating the latter to technicians and working with the rest, more and more similar to each other, who can follow him better in the more traditional activities” (Díez, 1999, 5).

Situations in which the implicit idea that if students are different they have to attend a different class because they cannot share the class experiences, should disappear.

With regards to those groups of students who are perceived as causing more problems in classroom, it should be pointed out that in general they are those who do not follow the curriculum established by the school and require some process of curricular adaptation. Within these circumstances are those students with special educational needs associated with disability, in particular those who present a significant cognitive delay; those foreign students whose mother tongue is not Spanish and require a specific learning-teaching process; a wide group of students in compulsory secondary education, whose distinguishing characteristics are linked to

de-motivation, school failure and behaviour problems in most cases. These students often present a significant problem for the teacher, as they disturb the normal development of classes and they do not achieve the expected objectives. Very often, teachers lack support, information and training to face such situations and they encounter the responsibility of having to immediately solve difficult situations affecting the whole class. This is a fact that negatively influences teachers' attitudes regarding inclusion. Teaching which takes account of the diversity represented by students is a complex task that requires a high level of training and knowledge of certain teaching strategies. It also requires close co-operative work on the part of the educational community as a whole.

5.7.5 *Summary: what works?*

In conclusion, inclusive practices do not depend exclusively on students' intelligence levels, but on such variables as the number of students per class, behaviour of peers, the learning potential of students, the kind of specialised support provided outside and inside the classroom, co-operative work, teacher training and organisational aspects, among others. It is necessary to re-think curricular content and the use of spacing and timing according to students' interests, motivation and needs; starting from previous knowledge and generative topics that give sense to practice and work in the classroom; working with wide, flexible projects and organising the school so that autonomy and co-operative work is supported.

This is why, if schools want to go farther in the supporting the heterogeneous characteristics of students, it is necessary that they consider such aspects as their organisation and performance, the existence of co-ordination and co-operative work among teachers, the co-operation of the whole educational community, the use of resources and educational practices. According to Giné (1994), the lack of responsibility some teachers show and the limited flexibility in teaching systems focused on conceptual contents, all build up barriers to an inclusive process.

A culture of co-operation, considering education as a responsibility to be shared by everybody and a certain degree of leadership are required in the school. It is not enough that students are integrated in the centres, which supposes a process that is just concrete and "physical" and therefore inadequate. In fact, it is necessary that students with special educational needs are included in the school's life, in the local neighbourhood, that they are recognised and represent a challenge for that school and its educational response. A different integration culture is required (López Melero; 1990) that is the recognition of a school for all (García Pastor, 1993; Arnaiz, 1996). In summary, a change in values and attitude towards individuals who are different.

Different experiences show that when co-ordination, co-operative work and awareness of students' diversity exist, the school centre is capable of offering a learning-teaching process according to the students' educational needs. The response to students with special educational needs is a matter for the school; it is not an exclusive task corresponding to the responsibility of the Orientation Department or the specialised teachers. It must involve the whole school as a collective. This is why it is necessary that the school's educational project - as previously discussed - should consider diversity as just one subject amongst many. Within the curricular project of the school, a

range of subjects need to be considered in order to be able to make the corresponding adaptations and adjustments to educational provision for each student in general and for students with special educational needs in particular. The greater the collective responsibility in the high school, the better the educational response towards these students. A collective awareness about students' difficulties is more effective than the personal goodwill of many teachers that are concerned with providing an appropriate response to their individual, particular situations and issues.

The Orientation Departments in high schools play a decisive role. They are heterogeneous and diverse departments in terms of their members' training and origin and regarding the complexity and multiplicity of departmental functions and tasks - diagnosis and assessment, intervention, teaching, counselling, co-ordination with parents, teachers, students and administration.

Satisfying the needs of a class where students' academic level and behaviour are varied can be a particularly huge challenge for high schools. As high school teachers work with many students everyday, the contact between teachers and students is often limited. Also, the standard requirements for student entrance to other educational phases, admission to university and vocational education can have a significant impact regarding the strain high school teachers feel. The educational emphasis is to be aimed at "processes". As a result, high school teachers need to teach not only content, but also the necessary strategies to make learning significant and transferable.

Consequently, the flexible organisation of spacing, timing, student grouping, student-teacher ratio reduction, as well as the use of different methodological strategies (educational reinforcement measures, curricular adaptation, complementary support, co-operative learning techniques) and strategies for evaluation of classroom programming, all improve students' cognitive and emotional development, their social skills and integration.

These strategies have been shown to lead to a decrease in absenteeism and desertion and a lower rate of school failure. In addition, from a more academic point of view, there is an improvement in knowledge acquisition in the different curricular areas, particularly in mathematics and language. In the case of immigrant students and students with certain problems associated with different disabilities, learning to read, write and communicate supports integration in the school and the wider social environment, prevents co-existence problems and opens academic and professional opportunities.

5.8 SWEDEN

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5.8.1 Background

In Sweden, pupils in need of special support historically have been taught in special classes, in groups, or individually outside the ordinary classroom. Requirements to support pupils in need of special support in the classroom were introduced in the 1960s. In 1968 all pupils, no matter what kind of intellectual or physical disability they had, were required to receive at least nine years of education.

The National Curriculum 1980, introduced a radical change for pupils in need of special support. Attention was directed to the possibilities and obligations of schools to compensate for pupils' difficulties by changing ways of working (SOU 1997, p 53). A diagnosis of a pupil's difficulty was no longer regarded as sufficient to understand his or her needs. In the National Curriculum 1980, pupils' difficulties were supposed to be seen as relative (Ahlström, Emanuelsson & Wallin, 1986).

Today the law regarding comprehensive schools states that everybody at school should help and support pupils in need of special support. This support should mainly be given within the class or group to which the pupil with a disability belongs. However, there is a conditional paragraph stating that, if there is a special reason, such support may be given in a special educational group. Although in the latest National Curriculum, Lpo 94, the terms special education or special educational approaches have disappeared. Instead the guidelines of Lpo 94 state that everybody who works in school should be able to help pupils in need of special support. However, special education in small groups outside the ordinary classroom to a large extent still exists, not only as a form of support, but also to indicate a form of organisation (Skolverket, 1999; Haug, 1998).

During the 1990's the view on special education broadened and deepened. It meant that special educational research started to challenge the circumstances, processes and values taken for granted in ordinary school settings, where dilemmas arose (Haug, 1997; Emanuelsson, 1998b; Persson, 2001). Research on this relational perspective is increasing in Sweden although the more individual related - the so-called categorical perspective - is still dominating. It maybe said that inclusive classes have not yet been fully realised in education in Sweden (Emanuelsson 1992, 1995, Emanuelsson, Persson & Rosenqvist, 2001).

5.8.2 *The view on special support in the National Curriculum of today*

Sweden has the same National Curriculum for all pupils between 6 and 16 years old. The National Curriculum (Lpo 94, 1998) prescribes an equivalent education for all, independent of gender, class and ethnicity. In addition, education should be adapted to each pupil's circumstances and needs. The school is said to have a special responsibility for pupils who for whatever reason have difficulties in reaching educational goals. The school should strive and ensure to help all pupils in need of special support (Lpo 94, 1998, p. 6). Based on the pupil's background, earlier

experiences, language and knowledge, it should promote the pupil's further learning and acquisition of knowledge (p. 7).

The head teacher has the overall responsibility for making sure that the activity of the school as a whole is focused on attaining the national goals. S/he also has the responsibility to ensure that pupils have access to guidance, teaching material of good quality as well as other assistance (p. 23). Special concern is given to pupils in need of special support:

“Remedial measures are adjusted to assessments made by teachers of the pupil's development” (p. 24).

Pupils' rights to special education are prescribed in Government decrees as well. If a pupil is presumed not to reach the goals, she or he has a right to special education. Special education is preferably given in the pupil's ordinary class or group, but if there are special circumstances the support might be given in a special group.

The Government decrees also prescribe the head teachers' task in ensuring that an individual education plan is made for pupils in need of special support. The plan should be made in co-operation between teacher, pupil and his/her parents. The plan should make clear what should be done, how it will be done and who is responsible for the work and activities. Also evaluations should be continuously made.

5.8.3 Results of the literature review

The research within the field of special education for older pupils in compulsory schools often focuses on analysing disability, handicaps and different forms of deviation (Haug, 1998, Helldin, 1998, Emanuelsson et al 2001). Except for this categorical paradigm, there are in Sweden a few studies starting out in an inclusive setting and focusing upon the relational paradigm. (Emanuelsson et al 2001). Some studies have involved investigations and evaluations, but more seldom on content and ways of working (Ahlberg, 1999, Haug 1998). As with the studies of younger pupils, not many classroom studies of older pupils focus on inclusive education i.e. ordinary education including pupils in need of special support.

One study looked at for this review, addressed inclusive education for pupils with learning disability (Eriksson, 1998). Collection of data was made by observations of 17 pupils included in 11 classes and by interviews with teachers. Of these classes two were made in grade seven in an inclusive setting. During the observation of education, notes were taken on the activity of the child with a disability, on what level he or she participated and how the interaction between the child, teacher(s) and classmates worked out.

Another study addressed the adjustment, temporal structures and the assistance provided in school for pupils with physical disability in ordinary classrooms (Hemmingsson, 2002). The study was the result of five minor studies and information was collected through quantitative data, semi-structured interviews and field observations. Altogether the studies included 89 pupils with physical disabilities, some of them from senior level in compulsory school (see table below from Hemmingsson, 2002, p 22).

<i>Students</i>	<u>Study I</u>	<u>Study II</u>	<u>Study III</u>	<u>Studies IV-V</u>
Total	45	45+3	34	7
<i>Compulsory school</i>				
Junior level	-	-	-	2
Intermediate	-	-	16	2
Senior level	-	-	16	3
Upper secondary School	45	45+3	2	

The aim of the third study, conducted by Jakobsson (2002), was to describe and analyse school situations in which pupils with a syndrome diagnosis participated. Of special interest were pre-requisites and conditions, context and relationships in the school situations for these pupils. However, Jakobsson also looked at what function the diagnosis had and if there was a difference between diagnoses. School situations of 50 pupils representing four different syndromes were studied¹. Data was collected through participant observations and interviews.

These studies all in different ways focus upon inclusive settings. In the following sections, firstly the essential factors within the context of helping pupils in need of special support found in the studies will be discussed. Secondly, the focus will be upon the different outcomes: social, cognitive and emotional. Finally the main problems within the contexts are discussed and some remarks are made.

5.8.4 Which factors within the context of the curriculum are essential for helping pupils in need of special support in mainstream classrooms?

Eriksson's overall aim was to describe inclusion for pupils with learning disability in eleven classes. As only two of the settings looked at older pupils, the focus here will be on these two examples. In one of the classes there were always two teachers in the classroom, where four pupils with learning disabilities received all their education together with 18 other pupils, although these four pupils were sometimes "prepared" in a small group. A special arrangement with a small group room close to the ordinary classroom was made. The curriculum was arranged to suit these pupils with theoretical subjects in the morning and subjects of a more practical kind in the afternoon.

In the other 7th grade class, there were no extra resources although there were many "weak pupils" and one pupil with a learning disability. However, the class used a special teacher for some lessons to make smaller groups. The special teacher had

¹ The chosen syndromes were: 1. CDGS with symptoms during infancy and childhood as failure-to thrive, floppiness, growth retardation, severe psychomotor and mental developmental delay, stroke-like episodes, frequent occurring infections, weakness of legs and sometimes visual inattention and squinting. 2. FAS with signs as growth deficiency, psychical abnormalities and central nervous system dysfunction often resulting in learning disability, poor impulse control, deficits in language and mathematical skills and problems with social interaction, attention and judgement. 3. CATCH 22 with symptoms such as physical impairments, developmental delay in areas of cognition, speech and socialisation resulting in difficulties in learning, speech, motor function, perception, attention, activity level and social relations. 4. Turner Syndrome pupils have an incomplete pubertal development, a particular neuro-cognitive profiles with normally developed language abilities, but impaired visual-spatial and/or visual/perceptual abilities. They often have difficulties in spatial ability causing mathematical, motor control, co-ordination, emotional, and social problems. (Jakobsson, 2002, s 209)

half of the group in Swedish and the subject teacher the other half. The groups were made alphabetically and the special teacher taught the group with the disabled child. Both teachers had only just a minor course qualification in special education.

Hemmingsson's overall study aim was to identify and explore aspects of the school environment that influenced the participation of students with physical disabilities. Of the five minor studies covered by Hemmingsson the last three studies are of interest for the purpose of this review. In study III Hemmingsson, identified the environmental barriers in mainstream schools by investigating the personal perspective of pupils with physical disability. Older pupils experienced significantly more barriers in school than younger ones. Hemmingsson also found that problems were not related to diagnoses and mobility, but more to school activities and organisation.

In study IV Hemmingsson tried to understand how sequential structures in the school setting influenced the daily schoolwork of pupils with disabilities. Of great influence for pupils' participation in daily schoolwork was the teaching style. In study V, Hemmingsson described and tried to understand how assistance was provided and how pupil assistants influenced participation for pupils with disabilities.

In Jakobsson's study (2002) one factor in the context of education of importance for pupils with syndrome diagnoses that causes physical disability was the physical environment. For all the pupils with a syndrome diagnosis the atmosphere in the school was important. For example, the pupil's participation in groups and planning of activities seemed to be of importance for the pupils, as well as their ability, the way the school worked and communicated, the teacher's behaviour and relationships between individuals and groups. However, Jakobsson stressed the complexity of education for these pupils with a syndrome diagnosis by describing these factors as co-existent, where the context is also important.

Essential factors in Ericsson's study

In the class with four pupils with disability, inclusion was said to be good for all as the education became more varied and the class was allowed to be a little smaller, 22 pupils, than the parallel class, which had 28 pupils. The special teacher was in the classroom most of the time and she prepared texts for the pupils with disability by preparing questions, which many of the other pupils found interesting and also used. To use illustrated material was a necessity for these four pupils, which many of the other pupils also found helpful. The individual educational plan was also seen as important for these four pupils with disability.

In the class with one pupil with disability the special teacher thought that the pupil was more stimulated and actively included in an ordinary class. As there were more "weak pupils" in the class, this pupil with a disability became just one of many. The pupil with a disability was cognitively doing as good as many of these other weak pupils. The best aspect for the pupil was said to be his social life and the teachers thought he was totally included. The teachers were a little bit afraid that the pupil's development in different subjects was perhaps suffering a little as the teachers did not think that they adapted the education especially well for the pupil with a disability.

Essential factors in Hemmingsson's study

Hemmingsson's study showed attendance in regular classroom decreased with increasing age for pupils with physical disabilities. They seemed to have chosen an upper secondary programme below their academic achievements, although they left compulsory school with above average grades. The organisational aspect was one reason for the limited participation of the older pupils. Although the majority of pupils were satisfied with physical admittance, the older the pupils got the more difficult they found the physical environment. Hemmingsson suggests that to help these pupils it is important that teachers have appropriate knowledge of the specific physical disability and that they have an awareness of the environment. There is a need for a development of a more coherent schedule, for example a home classroom.

The relationship with the pupil assistant was a complex issue. The assistant often seemed to prioritise the pupil's participation in schooling, whilst the pupil prioritised social participation with peers. Pupils had difficulty in positively influencing the intervention of the assistant in relation to social participation. Hemmingsson suggests that peer interaction in school is of even greater importance for pupils with these disabilities because of their limited out of school contact with peers.

Instead of one assistant, the pupils seemed to prefer a pool of assistants, which gave the pupil increased autonomy. To promote this self-determination was of great importance for these pupils, as their physical independence would never be realised. Therefore it was important to give these pupils opportunities to make choices and decisions that concerned their own existence. It is argued that the assistant should give practical support, but not interfere in the decision-making of the pupil. Similarly, it appears to be of great importance that the pupil with physical disability learns how to negotiate, make decisions and collaborate, as she or he in the future will need these competencies, as physical independence may never be realised.

Even the teachers' working style (conductor style, dialogue style, the group work style and the individual task style) had impact on the opportunities the pupils with disabilities had to participate in the classroom². The best option for the pupils appeared to be when the teachers' teaching style did not require all pupils to keep to the same pace, did not involve several rapid changes of activities and allowed room for communication between pupil and assistant. Of great importance was the fact that teachers were able to give these pupils enough time for different tasks and examinations.

The final findings of the study were that for different forms of support to pupils with physical disability to be optimised, support had to be seen within a social context not only in relation to the single student. Possibilities to use the proposed arrangements were also dependant on teachers', assistants' and peers' influence on the pupils.

Essential factors in Jakobsson's study

Diagnosis of disability was of great importance for the understanding, security and behaviour of parents and school staff. However, the diagnosis did not guide the teacher in their educational work - the work in school did not change because of the diagnosis itself. What seemed to be important for education was the degree of

² These styles are more carefully described in Literature Review in Classroom Practices I, Sweden.

disability and the fact that the diagnosis had to be complemented with statements about consequences for the educational context.

Another finding in Jakobsson's study was that communication between different actors in the educational situation around the pupil with a syndrome diagnosis was of utmost importance. The quality of communication, relationships and co-operation in all contexts that influenced possibilities for learning and socialisation were vital. What was happening in schools was more dependant on the context and circumstances around the individual than the National Curriculum. That meant that the pupil's participation in school was dependant on the participation of school staff, parents and other individuals around the pupil. When the communication between different actors failed in schools at whatever level, it had consequences for the pupils in complex situations.

5.8.5 Remarks and main problems

Inclusion in schools can be understood as a form of developmental processes within groups aiming at democratic goals (Emanuelsson, 1998a). Inclusion directs schools and teachers to make existing differences between individuals seem normal. Of course, there are a lot of challenges for schools and teachers to create and develop participation for all.

In these three studies the main problems relating to participation for pupils with disabilities were:

- The complexity of schooling in a social context
- The quality of communication, relationships and co-operation in all contexts and with all actors around a pupil with a disability
- The physical environment if the older pupil is disabled physically
- The diagnosis
- The class assistant.

In Sweden two perspectives on differences and on special education in practice are presented by Persson (1999) and used in Emanuelsson et al (2001). The perspectives are the *categorical* and *relational*. The authors argue that outcomes of special education are dependant on what perspectives schools and staff have.

The two perspectives are:

	Categorical perspective	Relational perspective
Ontology of special needs	Special needs refer to actual characteristics of individuals	Special needs are social constructs
Approach to difference	Differentiating & categorising	Unifying
Major contribution	Mapping and systematising the field	Problematising and deconstructing the field
Disciplinary basis	Establishing special education as a 'scientific' discipline	Establishing special education as a social scientific discipline
Implication for provision	Special provision	Integrated / Inclusive provision
Understanding of special	Superior support directly	Superior support for

educational competence	related to diagnosed difficulties among students	incorporating differentiation into instruction and content
Reasons for special educational needs	Students <i>with</i> difficulties. Difficulties are either innate or otherwise bound to the individual	Students <i>in</i> difficulties. Difficulties arise from different phenomena in educational settings and processes

(Emanuelsson et al, 2002, p 22)

If these two paradigms were used to look at the three studies, it could be argued that they all start out from the categorical perspective, as the approach to difference is to start by categorising the pupils. However, in actual fact the findings and the implications for provision are inclusive as, at least in two of the studies (Hemmingsson and Jakobsson), the importance of the social context, communication, relationships and co-operation are in one way or another stressed in the results - although these are related to the pupils with disability not to the whole group. The findings then imply a more relational perspective. As Emanuelsson et al (2001) state:

“...the two paradigms are not [mutually exclusive to] each other” (129)

and

“...neither of the perspectives are complete” (133).

In the three studies examined, there is one aspect that is stressed: that is communication on all levels and between all actors. As Ahlberg (1999) argues, schools must develop arenas for reflection on all levels. She suggests that many meetings in schools today do not contribute to the teachers' knowledge about daily work in classrooms. This is an aspect that Hemmingsson's and Jakobsson's studies also show as being important. Ahlberg highlights the importance of counselling meetings, where the special teacher and the class teacher or team of teachers meet and discuss daily work, which is of great value for visualising learning, social relationships, social justice, equity and pupils' choices. To communicate on these issues is of real importance for the whole group of pupils, including pupils in need of special support.

To focus on the relational perspective means to start in ordinary education and study the processes, norms and values of organisation, planning and curriculum that exclude some pupils. Within these processes power is expressed (Persson, 2001, Emanuelsson et al, 2001). As Booth (1996) says:

“Inclusion implies change... It comprises two linked processes: it is the process of increasing the participation of students in the cultures and curricula of mainstream schools and communities: it is the process of reducing the exclusion of students from mainstream cultures and curricula” (p 89).

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5.9 SWITZERLAND

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5.9.1 Introduction

In Switzerland, concepts or guidelines for integrative schooling at the elementary level have been developed in almost all of the cantons. These concepts are concerned mainly with pupils and adolescents with difficulties in school (learning disabilities or behaviour disorders), pupils and adolescents with speech and sensory impairments and sometimes pupils with physical disabilities as well. Pupils and adolescents with mental disabilities still attend special schools for the most part. Some individuals are integrated into kindergarten and primary school through the great commitment of the person involved, but they remain the exceptions.

The literature or research reports included in the discussion here primarily deal with the integrative schooling of adolescents with school difficulties (in the following sections referred to as school pupils with special education needs or SEN).

The secondary I level follows primary school. In most cantons, it begins with the seventh year of school (about age 13) and ends with the ninth year of school. In Cantons Basel City and Vaud, it begins with the fifth year (about age 11); in Cantons Aargau, Basel-Land, Neuchâtel, and Ticino with the sixth year of school (about 12 years of age). The school situation at the secondary I level appears to be different in many respects from that of the primary school. Besides the different ages and the learners' difficulties, which change to some extent, these levels differ primarily in terms of their organisational form. In almost all of the cantons, the sixth year is divided into various school types, differentiated according to achievement, with differing objectives and curricula. The school types are treated differently in the cantons. Three structural models may be distinguished in general terms:

- Separate tracks: the school types are taught in separate buildings or in the same school building with clear segregation
- Co-operative tracks: the school types are taught in the same school building with greater inter-change
- Integrative classes: there are no traditional school types; instruction takes place for the most part in integrated groups; achievement groups are formed in individual subjects.

The pupils are normally taught in classes by age group. In only two cantons, Jura and Ticino, are all the achievement groups taught in integrative classes. Integrative forms of schooling are conducted in Switzerland principally in kindergarten and at the primary level (first through fifth/sixth school year). The transition between the primary and the secondary I levels has often not been clarified.

The ambiguity of Swiss school organisation is evident in the variety of models. It is not possible to discuss only one model in this report, as different models are implemented in all of the cantons that practice integrated education at this level. In this regard, cantonal educational policy in Switzerland often operates by providing models that may be implemented in the individual communes. However, the canton

itself does not assume responsibility for a particular model. This openness is based on the geographical differences within the cantons, which means that individual solutions must be possible (Siegen, 1997). There is no (educational policy) specification that prevails throughout Switzerland.

In Switzerland, the complex structure of financing is an additional complicating factor for integrative schooling, which is scarcely dealt with as a central theme (Bless 1995, among others) in the literature that has been examined (see below). To begin with, it is important to note in this context that disability insurance (Invalidenversicherung or IV) only supports pupils with SEN if they are entitled to one of the recognised special education measures in the regular school. The IV undertakes the schooling of pupils with disabilities if they are schooled in special institutions. At present, a re-organisation of financing in Switzerland is under discussion.

5.9.2 Methodology

To answer questions formulated within the scope of the European Agency study, literature and research reports were included from the following sources:

- Research databank of the Swiss Co-ordination Centre for Research in Education (SKBF)
- SIDOS (Swiss Information and Data Archive Service for the Social Sciences) research databank
- Documentation of the Swiss Institute for Special Education (SZH)
- Documentation of IDES (Information and Documentation on Education in Switzerland).

The focus of the search was research projects and documents that deal with integrative forms of schooling for pupils and adolescents with SEN as a central theme, according to their special education relevance for the secondary I level – with the exception of the integration of migrants, which, with regards to the subject of integration, attracts a high proportion of the research interest. Research projects and literature were selected that dealt exclusively with Switzerland. The research projects in the databanks provided the following details:

- Project head and collaborators
- Sponsoring institution and principal
- Project financing
- Brief description of the research project
- Descriptors
- Publications
- Methodology (research methods and instruments)
- Applicable geographical territory.

Altogether, only ten documents and research projects could be included in the assessment and discussion for this report. The descriptors used for the research were extracted from the project description of the European Agency and adapted to the Swiss situation. As an example of this adaptation, the descriptors that were used for the concept “special needs education” should be cited here: special education or special education support; special education supplementary instruction or support service instruction; ambulant special education; integrative schooling; integrative instruction; instruction for special education needs or scholastic needs; and their

translation in part into French and Italian. During the research, documents were excluded that made no relevant statements about the questions formulated as well as research projects that had deposited no results in the databanks, which are still in the planning stages, or have just commenced without having published relevant data for this study. Some of the documents or research projects not included should, nevertheless, be mentioned. Results of the TIMMS and PISA studies were omitted, because they did not include pupils with SEN to a satisfactory degree or did not include them at all. At the University of Fribourg, several projects on individual aspects of integrative schooling are being investigated, which include, amongst others, the practice of school year repetition that is widespread throughout Switzerland and is treated in the investigation as a phenomenon running counter to integration.

From the number of documents included, it is apparent that the research status on the subject of the report may be described as meagre in Switzerland. Empirical research is scarcely carried out and if it is, then it consists of qualitative research endeavours or evaluative designs, which end in case studies or secondary analyses.

For this reason, the first of the two fundamental questions can be answered only in a rudimentary manner. *What arrangements and factors within the context of the curriculum (classroom practices, teaching methods, educational organisation and so) are considered essential to help pupils with SEN in mainstream secondary level classrooms?*

The second question (*What is known about the results of these approaches (at the pupil level)?*) cannot be answered from the Swiss point of view. Nevertheless, a certain overview of the situation in Switzerland has been attempted on the basis of an in-depth analysis of the documents at hand – whilst remaining aware of the fact that there is still much to learn and gain from the overall literature review report and the experiences gained in the European sphere.

5.9.3 Classroom practices and outcomes

As in Switzerland the few available research results that deal with marginal instructional situations investigate in a focused manner school organisational aspects for the most part, statements will be made here regarding instruction in a contextual situation (school organisation). The possible connections between the instructional and the contextual levels may be discussed from the system perspective.

School Organisation and Environment

Within the scope of a secondary analysis of rather limited empirical research results, Dubs (in Bürli, 2001) comes to the conclusion that the effects of school organisational measures are generally over-rated. More important apparently is the quality of the school, the general attitude of the teachers towards the pupils, the school climate and the support from the parental home. Siegen (1997) also comes to this conclusion and his chief finding, after the investigation of various (integrative and separate) schools at the secondary I level, is that differences within schools are greater than those between schools. In addition, in his investigation, the differences between boys and girls are significant whilst those between pupils with SEN who are schooled inclusively or are excluded, are not. Integrative schooling may become a catch-all for

all the possible 'difficult' cases of regular teachers – the school special education teachers thus become problem-solvers, without genuine co-operation and a corresponding flexible organisation occurring within the special education programme. This result has been found in various papers (Leuthard, 1995a; Dozio, 1995; Steiner, 2002).

An integrative model that is practiced in Canton Ticino is presented here, with beginnings underway in other, mainly French-speaking, cantons.

The Ticino Model

The Ticino secondary school (scuola media) builds upon a model that unites (almost) all pupils in the same course of training. Only pupils who receive disability insurance benefits are placed in special classes, which are housed none-the-less in the buildings of the secondary schools. Ticino has a special education pupil quota of about 1.5% – and thus the lowest percentage in Switzerland. In order to do justice to the great heterogeneity of pupil needs, the so-called Servizio di sostegno pedagogico – the education support service – was created and established by law. The Servizio has assumed the task of co-ordinating all of those involved in order to be able to react flexibly to the SEN of the pupils through programmes inside and outside the classroom. Intervention in the area of cognitive school achievements is a primary task field of the Servizio, although these are not infrequently connected with emotional and social aspects, which may be also approached individually through the Servizio. The Servizio is organised regionally and consists of a group leader (capo gruppo), the school special education teachers of the sostegno and other specialists in pedagogical-therapeutic measures (e.g. speech therapy). It is integrated into the individual schools and can operate directly on site (Dozio, 1995).

The benefits of this model are clear: with a variety of specialists in place, one can react flexibly to the SEN (Dozio, 1995). All pupils go to school in one place where special needs education belongs to the programme and thus operates in a less stigmatising manner; there is scope for all involved to develop improved living and learning conditions.

The difficulties of this model are also apparent: the idea of the “curability or reparability” of scholastic difficulties leads to pressure on the teachers or to frustrating experiences; the range of intervention possibilities is often complex and results in the school special education teachers often using their favourite method repeatedly, which, however, does not necessarily lead to success. (Dozio, 1995)

Scholastic Environment

For individual schools, the fact that many problems that originate in the context of society are carried over into the schools is an additional burden: too many problems from outside the school are transferred to the school. In order to handle this, the policy level must provide supportive measures. At the secondary I level, however, concrete implementation guidelines exist in only a very few cantons for the continuance of the integrative form of schooling after the primary level.

In the study by Müller-Stump and Rossi Marty (1994), it proved to be important that all the participants (pupils, teachers, parents and authorities) were ready to assist in the integration process and in designing it in a positive manner.

In Riedo (1999), the family situation is shown to have a central influence on the pupil's school career. Psycho-social stress within the family has a negative effect on the school situation. Yet, it is precisely in stressful school situations where the family is seen as the decisive provider of support. Here too, the co-operation between school and parental home is shown to be the deciding factor in difficult school situations.

Transition from the Primary to the Secondary I Levels

As has already been mentioned, the ages 11 to 14 of the study target group coincide precisely with the transitional phase from the primary to the secondary I level, with only the schooling of adolescents with SEN being examined here. The transition from the usually integrative schooling at primary level to the generally segregated secondary I level may be regarded as the decisive selection moment in pupils' careers. The transition from the more integrative forms of schooling within a class to the division into achievement groups leaves its mark on the remaining time spent in school – in addition, pupils with SEN cannot simply set aside their 'baggage' from the time spent in primary school, but bring it along into this sharply segregated form of instruction.

Usually secondary I level schooling begins with probation or a probationary period. In those models in which not only integrative (e.g. special education instruction and team teaching) but also segregated forms (e.g. special classes and workshop classes) exist next to one another, the probation time is experienced as unsettled and stressful, since rejection threatens and the classes may possibly have to be re-organised or pupils will experience a re-assignment (Leuthard, 1995a).

It can happen that the school special education teacher is the same person as at the primary level, which eases the transition for the pupils with SEN. In a study by Steiner (2002), the school careers of individual pupils were investigated. Pupils with mild mental disabilities, who had been supported in an integrated manner, all changed in the course of the compulsory school term to an outside special school.

5.9.4 Co-operation, role, and tasks of teachers

All specialists and teachers (pedagogical-therapeutic specialists, regular teachers, and school special education teachers) are compelled to work together for the education of adolescents with SEN. This is the central factor that is emphasised again and again (Leuthard, 1995a). How this co-operation is organised depends ultimately on the participating parties. Basically, as is shown in the study by Müller-Stump and Rossi Marty (1994), good collaboration is indispensable. Their study also gives concrete indications as to how the teachers themselves describe the quality of the co-operation:

- The teachers involved must want to teach together
- The ability to work as a team is necessary; personal animosities cannot influence relationships between teachers
- Class teachers and school special education teachers must be able to accept that they are not always "the greatest" for everyone and that a pupil may seek more contact with one teacher
- The teachers must have sufficient self-confidence; they must be able to endure criticism and to contribute constructive criticism

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- Teachers must remain true to themselves and maintain their personal instructional style
 - Agreement on higher goals is, however, necessary.

Some points, which are dealt with as a central theme in the studies during the implementation of integrative schooling, include:

Separate support: schooling within the class is not yet widespread; often the adolescents with SEN are supported outside the class individually or in groups (Leuthard, 1995a; Siegen, 1997; Steiner 2002). The school special education teachers, however, are a clear part of the teaching team of a school (Leuthard, 1995a).

Team-teaching: the instructional form of team-teaching by regular teachers and school special education teachers offers many advantages. The pupils remain in their class without having to leave it for special education measures. Even the other pupils can profit from and become acquainted with the special education teacher. Both of the teachers can profit from one another professionally, support one another mutually in difficult situations and derive personal gain from it (Leuthard, 1995b).

Pedagogical concepts of integrative schooling: in the investigation by Steiner (2002) the teachers had no common conception and, in this sense, also no common special education understanding about support for pupils with SEN. Yet, the basic conviction that integration is “good” was present for the most part. Müller-Stump and Rossi Marty (1994) also refer indirectly to this opinion when they indicate in their study that agreement about the higher goals (with reference to instruction) by the participating teachers was a factor in successful integration.

Number of classes supervised: school special education teachers encounter limits if they have to work with too many adolescents, classes, and teachers (Müller-Stump and Rossi Marty 1994). This is connected with the organisation of the integrative schooling at that particular school. If a school special education teacher is responsible for all age-group classes and all pupils in the school building (which is to be expected at small schools), then naturally the heterogeneity of the individual difficulties and support programmes is correspondingly greater than if a school special education teacher at each level could work at an integrative higher level, where all of the classes are mixed (Leuthard, 1995a).

5.9.5 *Curricula, teaching materials, teaching methods, evaluation*

Curricula, Teaching Materials

There is practically nothing in the literature reviewed about specific instructional practice. That ultimately has to do with the fact that the curricula of the secondary I level also applies to pupils with SEN and that they are taught with the same educational materials, yet it is left to the school special education teachers to organise the methods in a more differentiated and individualised fashion. What makes it more complicated for the school special education teachers is that there are only curricula for regular school education – individualisation must occur based on the regular school curriculum. They cannot draw upon reliable information from the area of special needs education or from curricula for special schooling, since these do not exist. Likewise in Switzerland, there is no basic investigative research with regards to inclusive didactics or curricula for special educational needs.

The school special education teacher proceeds from the individual abilities of the pupils and works with them, as a rule, on a tailor-made individual educational plan (Bürli, 2001; Leuthard, 1995a; Schweizerischer Nationalfonds, 2001; Steiner, 2002). The demand for differentiated forms of instruction in integration classes may be found in various documents and is also shown to be a successful opportunity for dealing with special educational needs (Leuthard, 1995a/b; Riedo, 1999; SKBF 98:065; Steiner, 2002).

In German-speaking Switzerland, the core subjects, mathematics and German, are mentioned as special education subjects (cf. Leuthard, 1995a). However, there are regional differences and often an expansion of the subjects or special education lessons (Steiner 2002). In addition, support in the social and emotional areas is also identified as important (Dozio, 1995; Leuthard, 1995a/b; Steiner, 2002).

Teaching Methods

In the long-term study by Riedo (1999), the pedagogical-didactic abilities of the school special education teachers appeared to be of decisive significance for the evaluation of the effectiveness of integrative schooling in the eyes of pupils with SEN. An especially strong commitment of the teachers was valued positively and, in the case of a particular success, was also credited to them. In connection with the didactics, supportive and committed leadership, individual teaching and learning methods and definite yet adapted performance requirements were positively valued (Riedo, 1999).

The teachers must agree on content. Thus, it can be confusing for the pupils if two teachers in one class provide differing explanations. Specifically, pupils with SEN sometimes have limited possibilities for understanding and assimilating differing procedures or approaches (Müller-Stump and Rossi Marty, 1994).

Evaluation

An individual procedure is just as necessary for adequate evaluation as well as for instruction. Although in most of the cantons individual written evaluations are already dispensed at the primary level, from the fifth class on and at the secondary I level as well, numerical grades are usually utilised once again.

The degree of difficulty of the instruction is not adapted in integrative forms; it is neither higher nor lower than in the average secondary classes in structured schools (Müller-Stump/Rossi Marty, 1994). What changes is the higher level of inner differentiation and an individual adaptation to the learning achievements of all of the pupils. As a rule, the adolescents with SEN work according to an individual programme, tailor-made to their own possibilities, within the regular class (Leuthard, 1995a). Basically, they are measured according to general standards.

The forms of evaluation should be seen in close association with curriculum development and with the experiences already gained with integrative forms of schooling. In this regard, there is without question a need for development in Switzerland.

5.9.6 *Effects of integration on the pupils with SEN*

Preliminary note: the quantity of data with regards to the achievements of pupils with SEN in integrative forms of schooling at the secondary I level is very limited. In this respect, no statements can be made for Switzerland. With regards to other aspects of the effectiveness of integration, representative statements can scarcely be made. In this sense, the following statements have an exemplary character only.

General

Pupils with SEN, who benefit from integrative schooling, successfully demonstrate the foundations for entry into vocational life than those schooled in special classes (Fonds National suisse de la recherche scientifique, 1998; Schweizerischer Nationalfonds, 1998).

In the investigation by Leuthard (1995a), the school special education teachers were unanimously of the opinion that it is possible for adolescents to remain in regular classes with the help of integrative schooling. Advances in achievement were seen primarily in work conducted or in the social-emotional area.

As a central result, the long-term positive effect of integrative schooling can be cited from the study by Riedo (1999):

“Long-term, segregation leads to institutionally conditioned self-disqualification processes, especially at the secondary I level, when the search for an identity becomes a central theme for adolescents. They believe themselves to be less capable.”

Cognitive

As a result of the state of research in Switzerland, no statement can be made concerning the effects of integrative schooling on the intellectual achievements of pupils with SEN.

Emotional/Motivational

In his investigation into the connections between school organisation and affective factors, Siegen (1997) came to the conclusion that emotional variables are hardly associated with school organisation, but depend upon smaller units within the school at the class level. The only significant change in his investigation referred to the enjoyment of school, which, on the one hand, remained at an average to high level in the integrated secondary level, but which, on the other hand, reduced during the course of the school year in the segregated school. The factors leading to this result are not further explained in Siegen's paper (1997). In retrospect, this result may be connected with the result of Riedo's study (1999), in which pupils with SEN considered the commitment of their teacher to be important.

Integrated pupils with SEN perceive their presence in a regular class as an elevation of their status and give their all in order to satisfy the new demands of the secondary I level (Leuthard, 1995a).

In the study by Steiner (2002) instruction was rated well by the pupils with SEN – they felt involved and are interested. They felt under more pressure in the subjects in which they were supported. Identified as most stressful were the demands of natural

science subjects. Pupils would rather have had fewer assignments or less material. The integrative support was well received by pupils; it enabled them to better understand the school material and to learn at their own pace.

“Mainstreaming” (i.e. temporary segregation into a special class with subsequent mainstreaming in the regular class) was considered successful by adolescents (Riedo, 1999). The pupils with SEN in the study by Müller-Stump and Rossi Marty (1994) had a feeling of well being in their classes and assessed their achievements realistically.

School special education teachers see a great advantage in the complex school organisation of the secondary I level. Since the pupils are accustomed to attending different and various learning groups, the input from the school special education teachers has no special significance value, but belongs to the learning programme of the secondary I level like all other courses (Leuthard, 1995a). In this sense, pupils do not feel “special”, but they learn just like their comrades in the regular base classes.¹

Social

Looking back, the experiences of the school leavers in the long-term study by Riedo (1999) may be divided into various dimensions. The greatest importance is assumed by the social dimension, which, through negative experiences, extends far beyond the time at school and, through positive experiences, gives rise to relationships and friendships and thus to a stable social environment that has a positive effect on an individual’s well-being. Looking back, adolescents mention the relationships to individual teachers as being decisive.

The social integration of pupils with SEN in the study by Steiner (2002) turned out well: they clearly felt socially integrated in the class and were also perceived as such by the teachers. According to the statements of the teachers however, understanding for the weaker learners may be greater among the pupils. That is also expressed in the statements of the pupils with SEN when they expressed a desire for more normal treatment and more support from their classmates.

In the study by Müller-Stump and Rossi Marty (1994) the feeling of “we” was emphasised within the class, which promoted the social integration of all pupils. In addition, there had to be sufficient situations available in which the pupils could really work, experience, and learn together – too much segregation made the sense of community impossible. The sociogram developed by the researchers showed all pupils with SEN in inconspicuous positions, with the exception of pupils with severe behaviour disorders.

The pupils with SEN in the study by Siegen (1997) felt more accepted in the integrated secondary I level than those who are schooled in the lowest class track in the segregated school.

¹ German: “Stammklasse“, a class to which a group of students is assigned upon entry into the school and in which they receive most of their instruction in the coming years.

5.9.7 In Summary: which setting leads to which success?

In summary, the same headings will be used again as for the previous comments. In addition, Leuthard (1995b), on the basis of his research, has formulated some pre-requisites for integration to be successful. These pre-requisites are assigned to individual areas and marked with the reference in the literature.

School Organisation and Environment

Empirically, school organisation does not make any great difference in the performance of the pupils. Correspondingly important is that pupils with SEN be supported competently – independent of the school organisational model – that the inter-changeability of the models is high and that pupils with SEN can complete regular school without being segregated.

Transition from the Primary Level to Secondary I Levels

The transitional situation is the central crossroads in a child's school career. It is necessary to organise this transition carefully and with consideration for individual achievements. With regard to the general situation in Switzerland, it may also be said here that how the transition is made from the primary school, which tends to be integrative, to the secondary I school, which tends to be segregating, has a decisive influence.

Co-operation, Role, and Tasks of Teachers

Clear role structures: co-operative leadership and well-established bodies that are responsible for the mutual design and development of the integrative school, ease working together for all participants (Leuthard, 1995b).

The *broadest possible consensus* of all participants with regard to the possibilities and suitability of instruction for pupils with SEN and others together, forms the essential basis for success. Integration must be supported by the *whole team*, not just by individuals who have decided to teach in an integrative manner (Leuthard, 1995b).

A strong commitment by the teachers, linked to adapted objectives, teaching and learning methods matched to the individual and a supportive climate, is the central point for the success of integration.

Team-teaching demonstrates various advantages. Through working together in the same room, a genuine integrative situation arises among the participating teachers as well. The pupils with SEN have less of the feeling of being especially 'different', since they are not schooled separately in single or group lessons, unless it is really important for the individual pupil. The common knowledge that may be used during interdisciplinary work increases the resources for mastering the complex integration situation (conflict situation, high individualisation, etc.).

Curricula, Teaching Materials, Teaching Methods, and Evaluation

For adolescents with SEN, a *supportive school climate*, *differentiated instructional practice*, and an *individualised handling* of their SEN are especially important (Leuthard, 1995b). When the teachers work closely together with one another, exchange their pedagogical opinions and thereby also mutually learn from one

another, then the *individual care-planning* used by everyone will, firstly, be carried out and, secondly, will be individually planned by all participants and thereby be effective. In addition, binding forms of co-operation between the school special education teacher, the regular teacher, and other specialists are needed.

The *instructional organisation* must be designed so that pupils with SEN attend the lowest possible proportion of segregated special lessons (Leuthard, 1995b).

Effects of Integration on the Pupils with SEN

The *class environment* is an important factor in whether or not the pupils with SEN are happy or not. They must experience acceptance and understanding for their difficulties and within the class a feeling of community. To that end, situations are needed in which pupils can encounter one another at different levels and in different contexts (learning, field trips, projects, etc) and in which teachers promote such a climate.

5.9.8 Main problems in Switzerland concerning the issue of classroom practice within mainstream classrooms that include pupils with SEN

The Current State of Research

In Switzerland the current state of research concerning integration at the secondary I level is quite limited. This is one of the chief difficulties in Switzerland. In this regard, one can follow seamlessly from the first Swiss report on Classroom Practice at the Primary Level, whose statements are still valid here.

To summarise briefly:

- There are few studies of classroom practice in Switzerland; rather, what is available are comparative investigations of organisational forms in schools
- There are no didactic instruments for integrative forms of schooling; the teachers are compelled repeatedly to re-invent the wheel
- An examination of support services outside the school is practically non-existent
- Only with regard to Canton Ticino can the investigation of the effects of integrative instruction be described as somewhat satisfactory. Otherwise, there is a lack of studies concerning the support situation within the class.

In conclusion, due to the current dearth of research in this area in Switzerland, nothing concrete can be said about the effectiveness of integrative support of pupils with SEN at the secondary I level.

Organisation and Environment

School organisation: The organisation of the secondary I level into different performance groups and at various levels complicates a meaningful form of integration. The co-operation amongst teachers becomes more complex and time-consuming. The assignment of pupils to various base classes and classes by level fundamentally make it simpler for care-planning; however, the assignment of pupils to individual learning levels or learning groups often demonstrates uncertainties and the transition points are not transparent.

Probation: At the beginning of the secondary I level, there is usually probation or a probationary period, after which the adolescents are assigned to new levels or once

again to special instruction. This creates great unrest and pressure at the beginning of the secondary I level.

Transition from the Primary to the Secondary I Levels

Expectations of failure: A particular difficulty of the secondary I level lies in the fact that the pupils with SEN are already saddled with quite a long school history, which for them is associated with predominantly disappointing experiences. In the course of their school careers, pupils with SEN frequently develop a clear expectation of failure. Dis-interest, school fatigue, crises, achievement denial, problems of self-esteem, introversion, or aggressive behaviour are frequently the consequences of such developments and are expressed especially intensely in connection with difficulties related to puberty (Leuthard, 1995a).

Gaps in material: Even if the primary school pupil who has enjoyed integrative schooling manages the transition to a regular class at the secondary I level, the gaps in certain subject matter are enormous. What is interesting in this regard in the study by Steiner (2002) is that all pupils supported in integrative settings with mental disabilities had to change to a special school in the course of their period of compulsory schooling.

Co-operation, Role and Tasks of Teachers

Regular teachers: In the study by Steiner (2002), the regular teachers noted that on their own they are over-burdened supporting pupils with SEN, that they are not successful enough with individualising and differentiating within the framework of integrative forms of schooling to do justice to the needs of the pupils. This also comes from the fact that regular teachers tend to acquire very little useful knowledge of special education during their training and are poorly trained for the situation of co-operating with specialists.

Special education teachers in schools: In combination with the regular teacher, the school special education teachers or the support situations may become a “dumping ground” for “difficult cases” (Leuthard, 1995a; Dozio, 1995).

Lack of personnel: There is a lack of trained special education teachers in Switzerland. Therefore, regular teachers are frequently employed to support pupils with SEN, for which supplementary training in special education is supposed to compensate.

Regular teacher – special education teacher co-operation: Teachers in Switzerland are still not used to working together.

Inter-level work by special education teachers: In part, special education teachers may work not only at the secondary level but also with younger pupils at the primary level (cf. Leuthard, 1995a). This repeatedly complicates the organisation of support instruction and has as its consequence an increase in the number of regular classes with which the special education teacher must work.

Curricula, Teaching Materials, Teaching Methods, and Evaluation

Since there is a lack of curricula, teaching materials and forms of evaluation for pupils with SEN or integrative instruction at the secondary I level in Switzerland, there are also no studies of them to be found.

Teaching methods: If the teachers do not work closely together and have not agreed on their concepts, educational plans, etc, confusing and less than constructive situations will result for the pupils with SEN. (cf. Leuthard, 1995; Müller-Stump/Rossi Marti, 1994; Riedo, 1999).

Effects of Integration on the Pupils

Once again only representative statements can be made (cf. above also: state of research). One of the difficulties of the integration of pupils with SEN is the effect of stress in the subjects in which they receive support (cf. Steiner, 2002). Since the curricula and evaluation forms can scarcely be adapted to individual special needs, enormous pressure arises to demonstrate performance by pupils within the framework of the established curriculum.

5.9.9 Groups of pupils with SEN that cause the most problems within mainstream classes

The few instances of research refer principally to pupils with difficulties in school (learning disabilities and mild behaviour disorders); other disabilities have not been investigated (except for e.g. Steiner, 2002: pupils with mild mental disabilities). For this reason, at this point almost no statement can be made on the basis of the documents and research projects analysed. There are isolated references that “severely behaviour disordered pupils” (Müller-Stump and Rossi Marty, 1994) would disrupt the integrative framework if the special education teacher collaborates for only some lessons in the classroom. Specifically mentioned, are those pupils who are a serious threat to themselves and others. The regular class with integrated support does not provide sufficient shelter where they can learn quietly or by themselves or can be closely supervised.

5.9.10 Summary: what works?

Basically, it first must be stated that the results of the analysis of the literature presented here show largely episodic evidence. They are far from being empirically grounded and only partially established theoretically. In this sense, the concluding thoughts formulated here in summary are more to be understood as *desiderata* and less as empirically validated statements. They refer to various levels and under no circumstances concern just the classroom and the forms of instruction. From a systematic perspective, the levels of the school, the commune (local conditions), the canton, educational policy, or the training of the participating professions exert an influence on the favourable contribution of instructional practice to the successful integration of adolescents with SEN.

In summary, what makes inclusive educational settings work:

- Consensus of all participants that integration is *do-able* and to be striven for (teaching and specialist personnel, parents, authorities, etc.)

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- Commitment of financial and personnel resources to a regular school that knows how to handle heterogeneity (endowments, cultures, strata, and genders)
 - Flexible organisation of participant co-operation on the basis of a fundamental understanding that a school understands itself to be a whole team. Special education teachers belong to the team and interdisciplinary work is part of everyday responsibilities
 - Re-thinking of segregation into achievement groups at the secondary I level
 - As few outside services by special education teachers or other specialists as possible, as much support (through team-teaching) inside the classroom as possible
 - A high level of commitment and support by all participating teachers and specialists
 - Individualising and differentiating forms of instruction, adapted learning objectives, and appropriate forms of evaluation
 - Making the various differences of the pupils with SEN and regular pupils a central theme, thereby also including all pupils in the support.

5.10 UNITED KINGDOM

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The present study for the European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education focuses on literature from 1990. As an introduction, it might be worthwhile briefly outlining the shape of the literature on inclusion since the early 1980s when it began to be a national issue in the UK. The range of literature on inclusion embraces many questions, of which classroom practice is but one. It included: national and local policy, human rights, macro-level processes of social development, the relationship between researcher and researched. However, it is not possible to consider the whole gamut and so the focus here will be on practice.

One of the earliest research studies (Hegarty *et al.*, 1981), sponsored by the government following the Warnock Report (DES, 1978) presented case studies of school practice. The potential of what was going on in individual classrooms with innovative teachers gradually developed into an awareness (fostered by practical examples) that all teachers should take responsibility for pupils with special educational needs, that these pupils were not 'someone else's problem' (Moore and Morrison, 1988), that mainstream schools were capable of providing in the same way as special schools (Dessent, 1987) and that this was a 'whole school' issue involving the curriculum in its widest sense. Studies highlighted the way in which the 'whole school' approach was implemented, showing that it was not straightforward (Bines, 1986; Croll and Moses, 1985).

Towards the end of the 1990s, the national picture was outlined by Lee and Henkhousens (1996) and the elements of 'best' or 'most innovative' practice was charted by Clark *et al.* (1995). The latter, with reference to secondary schools, were summarised within the following categories:

- Embedding provision for the full range of pupil diversity within ordinary classrooms and in the context of an entitlement curriculum, underpinned by notions of individual difference and supporting the learning of all pupils
- Flexible resource management to maximise the learning of all pupils
- The effective management of change and of roles within the change process
- The critical nature of the professional development of all staff to enhance their capacity to respond to pupil diversity
- Collaborative working in order to build capacity and effectiveness.

(Clark *et al.*, 1995, 74)

Insider accounts of individual cases involving schools and their local education authorities were represented by Gilbert and Hart (1990), Jordan and Goodey (1996) and Thomas *et al.* (1998). Although the case studies showed variations in understanding of 'inclusion', expected outcomes and the process needed to get there, there was consensus that inclusive practice necessitated whole school reform, the elimination of the concept of 'remedial teaching' and curriculum development by way of content and presentation. There was also consensus in the literature that the challenges were great, that the dynamic was such that inclusion was 'a process' rather than a state and that tensions were very evident.

Alongside these qualitative case studies were studies of 'integration statistics', which continue to this day. These examined the relative proportion of segregated placements in each local education authority and calculated the year-on-year change in relation to the number of pupils educated by that authority and the numbers of pupils with statements of special educational needs in that authority (e.g. Swann, 1992; more recently, see: www.inclusion.uwe.ac.uk/csie/stats02.htm).

While such studies continue, they are limited. Firstly, they say nothing about the profile of the quantitative data themselves - for example, individual pupils' movement in and out of placements, the use of short-term placements, pupils on the roll of one school but spending a substantial amount of time in another and, even, dual registration (DfES, 2001). Secondly, they do not comment on the appropriateness or effectiveness of any of those statements or analyse the types of needs for which they provide. Thirdly, they tend to assume that segregation, *per se*, is undesirable (see also, for example, Barton (1997) and Oliver (2001), both of whom, *inter alia*, present ideological arguments, based on human rights issues, for the undesirability of segregated provision) and mainstream placements, *per se*, desirable.

This holds little water in the light of qualitative studies that show that a young person *can* be more isolated in a mainstream classroom than in a special school classroom. In these figures there is no indication of the policy supported in the government's Green Paper at the end of the 1990s (DfEE, 1997), which promoted the use of special schools as resource centres. While this is highly problematic and, to date, there has been little guidance as to what such resource centres might look like (though it is likely that a government paper will be forthcoming), it shows the weakness in judging inclusion merely by doing head counts of numbers on roll in different establishments. Farrell (2001) questions whether developments in inclusive education have resulted in enhanced provision in services to pupils and families: he concludes that the position is mixed with an improvement in attitudes, but a persistent degree of conceptual confusion and some inhibiting bureaucratic procedures.

The recent literature relating to inclusion in the lower secondary phase of education (11-14), with which the present study is concerned, chiefly focuses on inclusive schools rather than inclusive classrooms. There are two reasons for this. First, while in the UK, as in other countries in Europe, pupils of primary school age (in the UK 4/5 - 11) generally work with one class teacher for most of the day (or a morning - different patterns are emerging in England), pupils at secondary school generally move around and experience teaching from a range of subject teachers: it is these teachers who are responsible for the education of all pupils in their classes. Thus there need to be structures to ensure that a pupil can be included throughout the curriculum although Florian and Rouse (2001) point out that the subject based training of secondary school teachers in the UK leads to distinct subject cultures so there are likely to be considerable inter-departmental differences within any single secondary school unless efforts are made to encourage a whole-school ethos. Second, as a general rule, secondary schools are larger, more complex organisations than primary schools (though the largest primary schools in England can be larger than the smallest secondary schools). The management challenges of inclusion, which research shows largely centre round school reform and reconstruction, have to be met within the larger organisation where communication

and leadership take a form different from than in a smaller organisation where there is a simpler communication structure. Third, the ‘gap’ or ‘perceived difference’ among pupils widens as pupils grow older and thus the central challenge of inclusion - to embrace difference and provide for a range of individual needs - becomes greater.

Yet even the focus on inclusive schools is problematic. Clark *et al.* (1995) argue that the methodologies for investigating inclusive schools have developed in response to greater understanding, but that greater understanding involves a greater awareness of the complexity of inclusion — not a greater certainty as to how to achieve it. For example, attention has shifted from practices per se to practitioners and to their values and any factors that may impinge on those values and accompanying practice. For example, is diversity regarded as a resource or as a problem to be minimised (Booth and Ainscow, 2000). (The focus on attitudes and values underpins the work directing the Index for Inclusion, CSIE, 2002).

The particularities of complex interactions between practice and values may be unique to that organisational context and are useful merely to highlight principles. Empirical examples may have a transformational value for other contexts. Similarly, the greater understanding has revealed the danger of the domination of any single line of enquiry— for example, ‘the whole school approach’ or ‘support teaching’ or the psycho-medical paradigm. This is, of course, further strengthened when inclusion is conceived as a political process (Armstrong, Armstrong and Barton, 2000), shaped by a range of policies, not just those marked by and for ‘inclusion’.

While there are rhetorical, ideological and descriptive accounts, *critical* case studies of inclusive practice are rare in the UK: many UK commentators used the international literature, especially that from the US (Rose, 2002) — covered in the international review for this project. Notable exceptions are Thomas *et al.* (1998) and Dyson and Millward (2000). The latter present case studies of four schools but then, importantly, offer a critical analysis of the schools’ successes and failures in terms of organisational theory (the management of change, leadership styles, the micro-politics of the school) the wider socio-political context of national policy and, further, sociological theory.

They have no difficulty in identifying the common ‘surface’ features of inclusive schools; these reinforce what other studies suggest. A composite list is:

- Strong leadership, commitment and advocacy from the principal, with supporting and competent leadership from elsewhere in the organisation at either senior or middle management level
- The dismantling/deconstruction of traditional structures typifying special needs provision and their replacement with flexible, dispersed responses to diversity
- The availability of relevant staff development to empower all teachers
- An extension of the range of pupils provided for.

The accompanying assumptions are that:

- All teachers will have a range of pedagogical approaches and take responsibility for deploying them appropriately within their classroom
- The core special education principle of addressing individual needs will be extended to all learners in the school rather than just pupils with special educational needs as traditionally/formally defined

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- 'Problems' regarding pupil needs will be solved collaboratively (hence departmental development of differentiated schemes of work, support assistants and special teachers working in the classroom)
 - Staff development will equip teachers with the technical skills to meet pupils' needs
 - Pupils will normally be in ordinary classrooms (rather than withdrawal situations).

Other features of inclusive schools are characterised by the formalisation of strategies which support pupils with learning and behavioural difficulties – strategies which might otherwise be implicit and/or unnecessary but, once made formal/explicit are, arguably, of benefit to all pupils. These would include:

- Buddying schemes/peer mentoring
- Whole school behaviour policies (often 'assertive discipline')
- The formal celebration of a range of achievement throughout the curriculum.

The criteria of inclusiveness which emerge from empirical studies in the UK literature reflect those from the US literature (see Lipsky and Gartner, 1997 and discussed in Chapter 4, the international review).

Using the theoretical frameworks of Skrtic (1991), who wrote of the 'adhocratic' school (see Chapter 4) and Ainscow (1999) (whose influence is not confined to the UK - see 1994 and other work for UNESCO, also covered in Chapter 4), who wrote of the 'moving' school, Dyson and Millward (1998) draw attention to the fact that there is a link between 'effective' schools and 'inclusive' schools insofar as they depend on effective management to move them forward. While all their case study schools had committed leaders with a strong vision (albeit variously, and sometimes not totally coherently formed), these leaders had different capacities for sharing this vision with their staff, implementing innovation and managing change.

An essential element of 'moving forward' is self-assessment and constant critique of practice. In England, this approach has been promoted through the *Index for Inclusion* (CSIE, 2002 2nd edition), a self-assessment instrument for schools to evaluate their own degree of inclusiveness. Emerging from empirical research in English schools, this has been influential within Europe and farther afield. The approach echoes government policy and statutory expectations of schools. Inclusiveness is now an area scrutinised in the formal school inspection system in England (Ofsted, 2003a and b), while government policy (DfES, 2001) states that a primary function of local education authorities in England is to promote autonomous schools that have the capacity to reflect critically on their own practice, produce their own solutions from within their own resources and make their own decisions regarding the purchase of external services.

In their empirical research, Dyson and Millward found that where principals' managerial abilities were not so mature, the schools did not move as far and the barriers to inclusion were not removed. In all cases, the principals had a strong vision of the general direction in which they wanted the school to go, but no detailed map of how to get there. In management terms it is not entirely clear that they could have had a map. Dyson and Millward draw attention to the fact that the vision had to be interpreted in the harsh realities of everyday life in the classroom, which had its own history and depended on actors who each had a set of beliefs and professional practices.

It is in their analysis of the change process that Dyson and Millward contribute significantly to the study of inclusion: the literature establishes the ideal features of inclusive schools. What it does not do is to remark on how to establish these. Dyson and Millward suggest that the path is filled with difficulties to an extent that 'inclusion is a process not a state' takes on a new meaning. They pointed out that the situation in all the case study schools was ambiguous insofar as there remained 'un-deconstructed' organisational features that militated against the embedding of inclusive practices. For example, they identified, *inter alia*, the setting (grouping) of pupils by attainment, a separate team of special needs teachers, a low-status special needs co-ordinator, a separate curriculum for low-attaining pupils, and withdrawal for basic skills work. Interestingly, they assume, rather than argue, that these are necessarily antagonistic to 'inclusion' but that is probably because their own concept of 'inclusion' shifts. As regards behaviour, they observed from analysis of case study data that the more a pupil threatened the *status quo*, the less likely was the school to generate a problem-solving response. The pupil would be 'managed' or 'removed' or excluded.

They attribute the tensions and un-reformed areas to the problems in delivering the 'technology' of inclusion (support in the classroom, differentiation, new role for the special needs co-ordinator). Not only is the technology delivered by a great variety of professionals in a vast array of contexts but there are significant external pressures arising from the UK policy context. Some of these create tensions and may be incompatible with inclusion - for example, competitiveness between schools, stress on raising standards of achievement (and there is some evidence that there is a shift from a focus on individual pupil progress in lower secondary education to a focus on group performance in upper secondary education - Florian and Rouse, 2001 - (see Slee and Weiner (2001) and Norwich and Lunt (2000) for explorations of the tension between inclusion and school effectiveness) and the need for a positive public image. Furthermore, while there are notable exceptions, there is generally a gap between supply and demand so there is a tendency to put in support where there are problems, with the result that it becomes to be seen as troubleshooting. They claim that there is negligible empirical evidence in the literature that having classroom support changes teacher practice (evidence here may be in hard-to-access records; there are action research projects which suggest otherwise).

The analysis of Dyson and Millward is in line with other empirical studies which reveal tensions within an apparently inclusive environment: for example, restricted cultural references, low-risk teaching approaches, low level of expectations and challenge. Add to this teachers' own lack of confidence as regards their own skills and competence, particularly in the light of other professional demands (for example, Croll and Moses, 2000) and the fact that approaches to meeting needs are often contested (for example, there is no one approach to behavioural or learning difficulties) and it may well be that there are limits on inclusion (see also Wilson, 1999, 2000) insofar as it can be practised universally.

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APPENDICES - CRITICAL LITERATURE REVIEWS

Appendix A: International Review

Author and Title - Allsopp, D. Using classwide peer tutoring to teach beginning algebra problem-solving skills in heterogeneous classrooms.

Publication Details - Remedial & Special Education, V 18, nr 6, p 367, 1997.

Language - English.

Country of Origin - USA.

Type of Research - Quantitative.

Methodology - Both the staff and the students received training on how to use the Classwide Peer Tutoring procedures. The CWPT procedures included: 1) peer-tutoring skills, 2) transition from regular seating into tutoring pairs, 3) retrieval and return of materials, 4) practice in tutoring, 5) tutee responding behaviours, 6) error correction procedures, 7) point assignment procedures. Students in both intervention groups were instructed using *Solving Division Equations*: an algebra programme for teaching students with learning problems (Mercer & Allsopp, 1995). Students in intervention group A independently practised their worksheets after teacher directed lessons. Students in intervention group B participated in CWPT, to practice the skills. They used the same worksheets as the students in group A, but an answer key was provided by the tutor to assist his or her tutee in determining correct responses. Students both served as tutor and tutee. Teachers were instructed to monitor student performances and behaviour by circulating through the classrooms.

Sample - 262 students in 8th grade, in 14 mathematics classes in three middle schools participated. Ages ranged from 12 to 15 years. There were 4 teachers who volunteered to participate. 99 students were identified as 'at risk' of failure in maths.

Method of Research - Instruments included a pre-test, a post-test, and a maintenance test measuring basic algebra equation and word problem-solving ability.

Main Findings - Findings indicate that, overall, student performance for the CWPT group was not significantly different from the independent practice group. However CWPT seems to be most effective with 14 and 15-year old students. Although these older students in the independent practice group performed significantly better on the pre-test, students in the CWPT group scored slightly higher on the post-test. Overall, the findings suggest that the problem solving skills instruction *Solving Division Equations* was effective to both types of student practice.

Evaluative Commentary - Two intervention groups were compared, no control group was used.

Author and Title - Horton, S; Lovitt, T, A comparison of two methods of administering group reading inventories to diverse learners.

Publication Details - Remedial & Special Education, V 15, nr 6, p378 Nov. 1994.

Language - English.

Country of Origin - USA.

Type of Research - Quantitative.

Methodology - The level of agreement between two methods of administering group reading inventories, computer and paper and pencil was examined in this study. In one condition, students read textbook passages presented on computer, completed study guides, and took 15-item tests on the computer. In the other condition, students read passages from their textbooks, completed study guides, and took 15-item tests with pencil and paper. An equivalent time samples design was arranged, with four computer assessments and four paper and pencil assessments randomly assigned. The 72 students were divided into three groups; teacher directed, dyadic and independent. Two types of test items, factual and interpretative, were examined in this study.

Sample - Two classes in middle school science, two in middle school social studies, and two in high school social studies participated. In each grade level, one class served as an experimental group and one served as a control group. In the experimental classes 13 students were learning disabled (LD), 16 remedial, and 43 normal achieving (NA), a total of 72 students, 38 males and 34 females. The settings were students' general education classrooms.

Method of Research - The independent measures were nine multiple choice tests, prepared by the teachers and edited by the research staff. All tests contained 15 questions, 12 factual, 3 interpretative, each with 4 choices. A computer programme was developed by the first author's research staff. The programme presented 1) directions and instructions, 2) a reading passage was presented, taken verbatim from the text, normally consisting of about seven screens of text, and 3) a multiple choice test.

Main Findings - The results of the group analysis significantly favoured the computer group on factual questions for both the students with learning disabilities and their normal achieving peers. Individual analysis indicated few significant differences between the two types of group reading inventories. The results of the group analysis revealed no significant difference on interpretative test items. Overall on interpretative questions, the LD students scored slightly higher with pencil and paper and the NA students scored slightly higher on computer assessments. The placement of students in three instructional groups was identical for each type of group reading inventory in 72% of individual comparisons.

Author and Title - Lundeen, C.; Lundeen,D; Effectiveness of mainstreaming with collaborative teaching.

Publication Details - Paper given at the Annual Convention of American Speech Language Hearing Association, Nov. 1993.

Language - English.

Country of Origin - USA.

Type of Research - Programme evaluation.

Methodology - The article evaluates a collaborative teaching service delivery model in which special education students were mainstreamed into regular classes. Special and regular teachers team taught the curriculum and were responsible for choosing teaching methods, curriculum formats, learning strategies, study skills and evaluation methods.

Sample - The programme was implemented at a high school in West Virginia. Fifteen classes joined the programme; eight regular teachers and five special teachers were involved, teaching 318 students.

Method of Research - Previous grades results in reading comprehension scores were analysed, as well as results in the collaborative teaching programme. Comparison by student category, teaching team, and grade changes for individual students were made.

Main Findings - All students in the programme performed equivalently, despite substantially poorer reading comprehension scores of special education students. All students' grades improved after the programme.

Author and Title - Maccini, P. and Hughes, C. - Effects of a Problem-Solving Strategy on the introductory algebra performance of secondary students with disabilities.

Publication Details - Learning Disabilities Research & Practice, V 15, nr 1, p 10, 2000.

Language - English.

Country of Origin - USA.

Type of Research - Quantitative.

Methodology - The effects of an instructional strategy on the representation and solution of problem-solving skills (STAR, Maccini 1998) encompassing integer numbers for secondary students with learning disabilities was investigated in this study. Instruction consisted of three levels: 1) Concrete manipulation (manipulating physical objects to represent mathematics problems); 2) semi concrete application (pictorial representations of the mathematics problems); 3) abstract application (writing mathematical symbols to represent and solve problems). Students also learned a strategy designed to cue effective problem-solving strategies. The study was focused on the question whether students can learn a self-instructional strategy to help them monitor their performance, whether the programme would improve their performance, and whether students would generalise and maintain the intervention effects.

Sample - Six students with learning disabilities were selected from a general secondary school. Participants were functioning more than 2 years below grade level. They received part-time support in a resource class.

Method of Research - Data collection consisted of think-aloud protocols, audio taping students, visual inspection and analysis of results. Percentages correct on problem representation, on problem solution and answer, and on strategy-use were measured. Maintenance measures were conducted after 10 weeks. Attitudes were measured using a survey.

Main Findings - Findings indicate that the programme dramatically improved problem-solving skills involving integer numbers. Students' strategy-use also increased over the instructional levels. Generalisation of intervention effects was evident in a far-transfer generalisation task and over time for multiplication and division of integers. Overall, participants strongly agreed that the programme helped them to become better problem solvers and they felt it had helped them to feel better about their skills. Participants recommended using the programme with other students.

Author and Title - Mc Donnell, J; Mathot-Buckner, C; Thorson, N; Fister, S; Supporting the Inclusion of Students with Moderate and Severe Disabilities in Junior High School Education Classes: The Effects of Classwide Peer Tutoring, Multi-Element Curriculum, and Accommodations.

Publication Details - Education and Intervention of Children, vol 24, no 2, May 2001, p141-160.

Language - English.

Country of Origin - USA.

Type of Research - Multiple probe across subjects design.

Methodology - The project was focused on increasing the amount of time students with disabilities spent in general education classes, and improving the quality of the instruction they received in these classes. Dependent measures focused on the levels of academic responding and competing behaviours of students with and without disabilities. Key members in each department received in-service training to introduce strategies for supporting students with severe disabilities in general education classes (response adaptation, curriculum overlapping and multi-element curriculum, and developing natural supports in the classroom). In addition, some members received on-site technical assistance to develop educational programmes for students with intense educational and behavioural needs.

The study was conducted in a pre-algebra, a physical education, and a history class. The experimental conditions for students with disabilities consisted of Baseline and the instructional Package, the conditions for the students without disabilities consisted of Baseline and Classwide peer tutoring. During baseline instruction, the students with disabilities focused on their own IEP objectives. The instructional package for students with disabilities consisted of Classwide Peer Tutoring, multi-element curriculum, and accommodations.

- Classwide Peer Tutoring sessions were scheduled twice a week for fifteen minutes. Teachers were asked to form heterogeneous teams that included three students of different performance levels. During the sessions each student played the role of tutor, tutee, and observer. The tutor would select a problem or task to be completed by the tutee and the observer provided social reinforcement. The teacher developed assistance procedures.

- Multi-element curricula: Special and general education teachers worked together to develop instructional objectives for the students with disabilities that focused on a subset of skills within the general curriculum.

- Accommodations: Special and general education teachers worked together to develop accommodations for each student that would meet their unique learning needs.

Sample - The study was conducted in a junior high school in a large urban school district. Measures were executed on the results of three students with moderate to severe disabilities, three students without disabilities, one special education teacher, and three general education teachers. The three students with disabilities were selected randomly from eleven students in the school, with moderate to profound mental retardation or multiple disabilities. The three students without disabilities were

selected randomly from the pool of peers and were performing at or above average in the class.

Method of Research - Observations were carried out during baseline and Classwide peer tutoring sessions. Data were recorded on laptop computers using the MS-CISSAR software.

Main Findings - Findings indicate that for both students with and without disabilities the level of academic responding improved and the level of competing behaviour decreased.

Evaluative Commentary - Measures relate to a small number of students.

Author and Title - Rice, D. and Zigmond, N. - Co-teaching in secondary schools: teachers' reports of developments in Australian and American classrooms.

Publication Details - Learning Disability Research & Practice, 2000, V 15, I. 4, p. 190.

Language - English.

Country of Origin – USA and Australia.

Type of Research - Qualitative.

Methodology - The aim of the study was to investigate co-teaching approaches that provide support to students with special needs in mainstream secondary classes. Teacher-interviews and observations were conducted in America and Australia.

Sample - 17 teachers from 10 public schools In Pennsylvania (USA) and Southeast Queensland (Aus) were interviewed and observed. These teachers were selected because of their experience with co-teaching. They all co-taught classes with 3-8 special needs students. All teachers volunteered to participate.

Method of Research - Observations and interviews were conducted.

Main Findings - Six themes emerged from the data sets.

- Teachers attributed the success or failure of co-teaching to a school-wide commitment to inclusion and the extent of administrative and collegial support they received.
- Teachers thought both students as well as teachers benefit from co-teaching. They felt they could learn a lot from each other.
- The compatibility of teachers seemed to be very important. Teachers thought that nobody should be forced to implement inclusion or co-teaching.
- The special education teachers needed to prove themselves for the partnership work. They generally had a lower status in the secondary education hierarchy.
- Teachers were not always equal partners. The authors observed special education teachers performing clerical duties. In most cases, the inequality in roles was explained as necessary because the special education teacher lacked content knowledge.
- Implementing co-teaching involved overcoming deep-rooted attitudes and administrative barriers. The most frequent concerns were: negative views toward inclusion, jealousy of the professional autonomy of teachers, and rejection of the idea that in-class support of a special education teacher would benefit them or their students.

Evaluative Commentary - Student results were not examined; no control group.

Author and Title - Rogan, J. and La Jeunesse, C. - Facilitating inclusion: the role of learning strategies to support secondary students with special needs.

Publication Details - Preventing School Failure, Spring 1995, Vol 39, Issue 3, p 35.

Language - English.

Country of Origin - USA.

Type of Research - Quantitative.

Methodology - The Pennsylvania Department of Education, in response to inquiries from teachers and parents who observed positive results of the Pennsylvania's elementary Instructional Support Programme, developed the Secondary Instructional Support (SIS) project. SIS provides high schools with training and guidance in five major areas: collaboration and team building, curriculum-based assessment, instructional techniques and adaptations, student motivation, and learning strategies. The SIS programme incorporated the Strategies Intervention Model (SIM) developed by KUCRL. This model aims at a shifting responsibility for learning (from teacher to student), teaches students how to select a strategy and when, and how to use the strategies. In addition, it focuses on teaching students how to generalise their use of the strategy.

Sample - The Seneca Valley School District was one of the initial participants in SIS. The programme was first began in the Junior High School. During the pilot year, 1023 students were enrolled in Junior High, including 78 students with special needs. Two seventh and two eight grade classes were selected for the study. The English teacher and the special education teacher co-taught two classes. The English teacher taught the other two classes. There were 8 LD students in one co-taught class of 24 students and 10 LD students in the other co-taught class of 27 students. The other two classes did not contain students with learning disabilities.

Method of Research - The main purpose of the study was to determine whether the programme would help students with LD to succeed in an inclusive English class and whether the programme would create any disadvantage for the non-LD students. All students were expected to achieve all of the course requirements set by the English teacher.

Main Findings - Findings suggest that students with learning disabilities can succeed in intermediate English classes when they are provided with strategies training. In addition, the inclusion of students with LD did not seem to have a negative impact on the students without learning disabilities.

Author and Title - Tralli, R and Colombo, B. - the Strategies Intervention Model: A Model for Supported Inclusion at Secondary Level.

Publication Details - Remedial & Special Education, Jul 1996, V 17, Issue 4, P 204.

Language - English.

Country of Origin - USA.

Type of Research – Case Study.

Methodology - This study examines two case examples of schools that have attempted to successfully include students with mild disabilities throughout the general education programme. Authors call the interventions developed through this research 'the Strategies Intervention Model'. They describe three kinds of interventions: learning strategy interventions (students are taught various learning strategies), instructional interventions (teachers use content enhancement routines to improve understanding), and empowerment interventions (to stimulate students to do their best and create positive relationships with others in school).

Sample - Since 1988, the model had been implemented in the Wethersfield school: 864 high school students, 10% students from minority groups; 10% disabled students; 80% of the students attend colleges and universities after graduation. The other case example is Clayton High School; 800 high school students, 25% students from minority groups; 10% disabled students; 95%% of the students attend colleges and universities after graduation. It is not clearly stated in which year this school implemented the model.

Method of Research - Case study.

Main Findings - Successful inclusion of students with mild disabilities was accomplished by giving teachers considerable time for planning and administrative support throughout the change process. A high level of collaboration between general and special education teachers was needed. The process of building an environment that is conducive to inclusion takes considerable time and broad base faculty and administrative support and commitment.

Evaluative Commentary - Case study, measurement of dependent variables is not specified. No control group.

Author and Title - Weichel Murawski, M. and Lee Swanson, H. - A meta-analysis of co-teaching research.

Publication Details - Remedial and special education, V22, nr 5, Sept/Oct 2001.

Language - English.

Country of Origin - Various.

Type of Research – Meta analysis.

Methodology - The rationale of this article was to synthesise data based articles regarding co-teaching between general and special education personnel.

Sample - To be included in the analysis, articles had to include sufficient quantitative data to calculate effect size for the intervention, the co-teaching intervention had to last more than 2 weeks, not including pre and post testing period, and the studies had to include four characteristics that identify the intervention as a form of co-teaching:

- General education teachers and special service providers were working together
- The intervention was occurring in the same space
- An element of co-planning was included
- The intervention involved delivering instruction to a heterogeneous group of students, with and without special needs.

Only 6 articles met the criteria for selection in this meta-analysis.

Method of Research - Dependent measures in which effect size could be calculated were coded. Dependent measures varied in terms of grades, attitudes, minimum competency results, achievement scores, and social outcomes.

Main Findings - Large effect sizes (0.87-3.67) were obtained for the one study that focused on kindergarten through third grade and for one that focused on high school level. Although the studies provide limited results, the authors suggest that co-teaching might be a suitable service delivery in secondary education. Differentiation by ability was not possible.

Author and Title - Weller, D: Block scheduling and inclusion in a high school.

Publication Details - Remedial & Special Education, Jul./Aug. 2000, V 21, I 4, p209.

Language – English.

Country of Origin – USA.

Type of Research - Qualitative, teacher perceptions of benefits and challenges.

Methodology - A new schedule was introduced in the school. The traditional schedule consisted of six classes per semester, offered daily during 50-minute periods. The new schedule consisted of eight courses per semester, having four periods per day, each lasting 85 minutes. After a lot of meetings, 80% of the staff voted for the implementation of the new schedule. The study was aimed at the following questions: 1. What are the benefits that accrue for an inclusion programme when block scheduling is implemented? 2. What are the challenges for an inclusion programme when block scheduling is implemented?

Sample - The inclusion programme of Eleanor Roosevelt High School was started in 1990 and is recognised as a model programme by the Council for Exceptional Children. 1,360 students are enrolled in grades 9-12. Ninety students are labelled as having disabilities, which is 6.6% of the student population. Participants were 7 teachers of students with disabilities and 7 general education teachers.

Method of Research - The authors used qualitative methods to provide a better understanding of the influence of the implementation of block scheduling. Classroom observations and interviews were conducted during the first year of implementation.

Main Findings - *Benefits:* Block scheduling aids the inclusion of students with high-incidence disabilities and assists in meeting the educational needs of all students. It facilitates teachers to work together to examine current teaching practices and share responsibility for modifying the curriculum. It allows for more teacher-student contact and gives teachers more opportunities to get to know students' learning styles and interests. It enhances the development of lessons that are more focused on student co-operation and participation. It gives students the chance to take two more classes per semester and gives them more elective time. This provides students with special needs the opportunity to explore interests and undeveloped and overlooked talents. The need for resource time of students with special needs did not increase. It created a more relaxed atmosphere and more flexibility for students and teachers.

Challenges: The new schedule magnified the need for teachers and students to develop effective organisational skills. Block scheduling made it harder for students to keep track of their books and the materials, due dates and exam dates. The implementation increased the need for teachers to keep in contact with each other. Despite the fact that lessons became more student-centred, some teachers felt that the lessons were too long for some students. The biggest complaint was regarding absence. When a student missed two lessons, s/he missed an entire week. It was hard to find time to meet a teacher for students, who missed classes, there was no consultancy time build into the schedule.

Evaluative Commentary - Based on teacher opinions. No measurement of student results. No pre-test, post-test, control group.

Appendix B: AUSTRIA

Author and Title – Feyerer, Ewald: Do the handicapped handicap? Inclusive education at the lower secondary school.

Publication Details - 3-7065-1321-8.

Language – German.

Country of Origin – Austria.

Type of Research - Qualitative and quantitative research.

Methodology - 651 pupils of nine integrative school classes and 23 regular classes were interviewed a few months before the children transferred to higher secondary education. Achievement was measured by using tests in the subjects *German*, *English* and *Mathematics*. Personal and family determinants such as intelligence, orientation at the beginning of the lower secondary school, characteristics of the family situation and social integration into peer groups were statistically controlled before the mean factors were compared. In the same way self-concept, the feeling of well-being at school and school environment were analysed.

Sample - Inclusion of children with special educational needs at the lower secondary school generates a lot of multi-layered questions: What is possible at all? What not? Which effects can be observed? This book gives answers to these questions in four different approaches: First the concept as well as the development of inclusive education in Austria is described. In the second part one gets an insight in the concrete daily school life of an inclusive class. Thirdly the results of the Austrian study “Do the handicapped handicap?” are presented: this study mainly gives an answer to the question “Is the achievement, the self-concept and the well-being of non-handicapped pupils in integrative classes the same, more or less than in regular classes?”

Main Findings - According to the results of the study *all* non-handicapped pupils in integrative school classes, as well as highly gifted students, know the same as the pupils in regular classes and develop a higher achievement-self-concept such as a better emotional self-image. Furthermore they feel significantly better in school, have better relations with teachers and peers and a more individualised school environment. Therefore handicapped pupils do not handicap; the emphasis on social learning is positive for the academic achievement of non-handicapped pupils in mainstreaming classes. The author draws conclusions for an inclusive educational policy.

Author and Title - Werner Specht, Jedes Kind ist Mittelpunkt:

Ergebnisse und Gedanken aus der Evaluation der Schulversuche zur Integration behinderter Schüler in der Sekundarstufe 1.

(“Every child is in the centre” Findings and conclusions of the evaluation concerning the integration of children with disabilities at secondary 1).

Publication Details - Article in: Behinderte in Familie Schule und Gesellschaft.

Language – German.

Country of Origin – Austria.

Type of Research - Qualitative and quantitative research.

Methodology - 1st study: sites are described in the case studies.

2nd study: comparison between secondary schools with and without inclusion.

Sample - 197 schools were asked about innovations arising from autonomous developments. 27 schools with inclusive classes.

Main Findings - Teachers who are experienced in working with severely disabled children are convinced that these children can be included. Although the burden and workload is sometimes quite high, generally satisfied feelings were predominant, because of the meaningful work. After some time, teamwork with colleagues is felt to be a relief (if co-operation works well). Teachers who answered the questionnaires state that integration contributes to increased understanding and to a reduction of prejudices and fears concerning children with disabilities, and this does not happen at the expense of achievements of children skilled in the subjects. Parents of children with SEN express high satisfaction with the support for their own child by the school. School and class climate in inclusive classes are experienced more positively than in parallel classes. Included pupils have more enjoyment of school and highlight more interest in instructions. From the children’s point of view, order and discipline do not suffer. There are no references that children in mainstream classes like each other better than in the compared classes. Parents of children with SEN estimate the social inclusion of their children more negatively than parents of non-disabled children. When severely disabled students are in the classes, non-disabled children are more likely to accept the principle of heterogeneous teaching and individualising education compared with classes where children with learning disabilities take part.

The mechanism of integrative classes can trigger synergies in the school, which promotes the development of a school as an organisation and increases the quality of provision. The change of learning and teaching methods via a holistic approach, pupil orientation and developed co-operation are the most important observable effects in schools with inclusive classes. These classes do not harm the image of the general secondary schools.

Author and Title - Specht Werner (publisher)

Fallstudien zur Integration behinderter Schüler in der Sekundarstufe 1

Band 1: Hauptschulklassen ohne Leistungsgruppen im großstädtischen Bereich

Fallstudienleiter: Emmerich Gradauer, Ingrid Haidmayer, Barbara Huemer, Peter Kienast

Band 2: Hauptschulklassen ohne Leistungsgruppen im kleinstädtisch-ländlichen Bereich

Fallstudienleiter: Ewald Feyerer, Karl Hauer, Ernst Joppich, Ewald Ritter

Band 3: Hauptschulklassen mit Leistungsgruppensystem

FallstudienleiterInnen: Ernst Joppich, Franziska Lach-Rabl

Rainhard Mathes, Klaus Troyer, Irene Moser

Band 4: Integrationsklassen an allgemeinbildenden höheren Schulen

Fallstudienleiter: Gerald Horn, Emmerich Gradauer, Armin Matt, Ulrike Zartler.

Case studies about integration of children with SEN in secondary schools:

Issue 1: Secondary schools without streaming (ability levels) in big cities (all children learn together and are not separated in different classes all the time, according to their abilities)

Issue 2: Secondary schools without streaming in small cities and urban areas

Issue 3: Secondary schools with streaming (children are organised in learning groups according to their ability in Mathematics, German and English. In all other subject, students are taught in one class)

Issue 4: Integration in grammar schools (children are supposed to be intelligent, therefore the curriculum provided can be compared to the top stream in secondary schools).

Publication Details - Reports published by the Centre for School Development and Ministry for Education and Cultural Affairs, Graz.

Language – German.

Country of Origin – Austria.

Type of Research - Qualitative and quantitative case study.

Methodology - All instruments for gathering data were produced by the project manager Werner Specht, supported by a group of experts.

The sites were chosen by the inspectors of the Federal school boards in the Federal Provinces of Austria.

Sample - 14 sites (28 classes: target groups and control class mainly the 6th grade).

Method of Research - Questionnaires for students of the target group and for students of the control class, interviews for parents, teachers, heads and inspectors and observation sheets for documentation of teaching methods, communication between several participating parties. All reports were structured in the following way:

- Main aspects of the site, special features of the school as viewed by parents, teachers and students
- Positive and negative conditions in the school concerning inclusion, co-operation of teachers, position of the special teacher, teaching methods and

organisation, co-operation with parents, position of the pilot project in the frame of the whole school, Inclusion from the parents' perspective, Inclusion as perceived by the children

- Summarised analysis.

Main Findings –

- Inclusion is possible, also in secondary schools, if people want to include children with SEN.
- Children with SEN demand a lot of flexibility, pedagogical imagination and creative, unconventional measures that require ample scope to enable heterogeneous teaching and enrich the daily school life. Students with SEN bring out innovation and overcome boredom.
- In those classes where teachers suffer from workload and difficult situations because of insufficiently equipped classes or missing resources, satisfaction with their work is obvious.
- The charisma of teachers who want to establish innovative concepts is still very high and parents tend to support their commitment. The argument that parents hinder innovation in school, especially a “school for all” is, in a global sense, not correct.

Evaluative Commentary – This study is very useful for teachers who intend to start with inclusive classes in secondary 1 as a basis for their reflections. They can read about all sorts of circumstances and environments.

However, two main questions cannot be fully answered by this study: the first is what is the best organisational concept for inclusive classes in secondary schools and the other one is, if students with SEN benefit from inclusive measures if they are supported sufficiently in a class for all. The methodology used for the research was not able to answer these questions.

It is still up to the team of teachers to create their own inclusive class according to the needs of the pupils with SEN.

Author and Title – Niedermair, Claudia: Zur Pragmatik der Vision einer Schule für alle. Integrative Unterrichtsgestaltung im Spiegel von Theorie und Alltagspraxis am Beispiel der ersten Hauptschulintegrationsklassen in Vorarlberg.

Publication Details - University of Innsbruck, 2002.

Language – German.

Country of Origin – Austria.

Type of Research - A mix of qualitative research.

Methodology – Action Research.

Sample - 6 inclusive classes, 6 teams of teachers, Parents; Langzeitstudie über 6 Jahre.

Method of Research - Team development, observation of lessons, interviews, questionnaires, written and oral feedback from teachers, students and parents.

Main Findings – Reflection on documentation of teaching concepts and methods developed by secondary teachers to facilitate joint education of children from 10 -14 in a school system not supporting basic concepts of inclusive pedagogy because of subject oriented teaching.

The field tested methodological repertoire consisted of weekly work plans, project, topic and pupil oriented teaching, based on modules with diverse group-settings as well as individual support for children with severe disabilities.

Through their work, all teams confirmed that internal differentiation and learning without exclusion does not affect non-disabled pupils concerning achievements.

To implement such teaching concepts, small teams are a necessity, but do differ a lot from the subject-oriented system in secondary schools.

In another part of the dissertation, conclusions are drawn: it is demonstrated how these teaching methods for inclusive education are assessed by teachers, pupils and parents.

The findings are extremely different from site to site, despite similar teaching concepts: they range from high satisfaction of all concerned parties to explicitly expressed disappointment at one school - despite positive achievements – and from high acceptance of children with SEN by their peers with several communication means to ambivalent behaviour and individual refusal.

Overall, the social integrative processes were perceived positively by all concerned actors, despite individual unexpected difficult conflicts during adolescence, but this developmental period is frequently impaired by bouts of intolerance not solely affecting the gap between the disabled and non disabled.

Evaluative Commentary - The focus of this dissertation is on inclusive teaching methods. Other factors which influence learning systems, e.g. co-operation between school and parents or team development are not dealt with explicitly

Appendix C: FRANCE

Integration and inclusive education

Author and Title - Garel, Jean Pierre: Integration and physical and sports education in secondary school.

Publication Details - In « Le courrier » of the Suresnes Centre national d'études et de formation pour l'enfance inadaptée (CNEFEI National Centre of Studies and Training for Handicapped Children). Dossier: educational integration in secondary school. l'intégration scolaire dans le second degré.
N° 68 Pages 56 to 65, 1996.

Language – French.

Country of Origin - France.

Type of Research - Analysis of national surveys.

Methodology - Analysis of the state of educational education in Physical and Sports Education, obstacles and prospects for development.

Sample - All disabilities. Secondary schools and collèges (secondary schools for pupils from 12 to 15 years of age) France.

Main Findings - The integration of handicapped pupils is quantitatively very different according to the type of handicap and the degree of deficiency. The specific teaching strategies, the feeling that the teacher is incompetent, security, and the difficulty in relating to the other pupils are the main obstacles observed. Proposed development includes support on official texts (suggested teaching approaches), better information about pupils' potential, promotion of appropriate educational methods.

Auditory handicap

Author and Title - Guide for teachers who teach a pupil with a hearing disability.

Publication Details - Ministry of National Education, Teaching Division, 2001.

Language – French.

Country of Origin – France.

Type of Research – Teaching Guide.

Methodology - This guide is aimed at non-specialized teachers who teach hearing handicapped students in primary and secondary schools and seeks to develop the awareness of teachers to key questions and to propose adaptations in teaching.

Sample - Hearing handicapped students in ordinary classes.

Main Findings - The apprehension and concern caused by the arrival of a deaf pupil in a class are usual. Communication with the deaf pupil is quite possible if certain steps are taken.

Evaluative Commentary - This very concise guide presents the technical and medical aspects of deafness, and then describes technical and later pedagogical adaptations, most of which are easy to put into practice.

Author and Title – Barrero, Christiane: The integration of hearing disabled students in the CES of Buclos.

Publication Details - CNEFEI (training course in LSF), 1993.

Language – French.

Country of Origin – France.

Type of Research - Description and analysis of an integration experiment over 10 years.

Methodology – The author, a sign language teacher, describes her teaching practice with deaf students in a collège, the reactions of these students and of teachers, on the basis of analyses of interviews and questionnaires.

Sample - Hearing deficient adolescents in a collège offering a bilingual programme and an oral practice programme with LPC (Langage Parlé Intégré – Integrated Spoken Language).

Main Findings – Integration cannot be reduced to purely educational integration. A plurality of teaching approaches, dialogue with parents, and acceptance of the teaching team are all required ingredients for success. When LSF (Langue des Signes Française – French Sign Language) is not present, integration is difficult whereas bilingual teaching is experienced as a positive factor of integration. The presence of two deaf pupils in a class contributes to the well-being of these two adolescents.

Evaluative Commentary - The point of view of an LSF teacher and the methods of the survey are original and rich in lessons. The practical aspects (co-ordination between LSF and the subjects of the lessons) and emotional aspects (deaf adolescents' vision of their own schooling) should be taken note of.

Author and Title - Boulandet, Agnès: Deafness and higher education: from school to the work world.

Publication Details – Glossa / Les cahiers de l'Unadreo n°76 of June 6, 2001
Pages 10 to 27.

Language – French.

Country of Origin – France.

Type of Research – Analysis of survey.

Methodology – Survey of the results on the Baccalaureate, higher education, and professional integration by analysis of statistical results and questionnaires.

Sample - Survey conducted of 112 deaf people who had attended courses at the Lycée Jules Renard of Nevers from 1978 to 1997.

Main Findings - The Lycée J. Renard in Nevers was the first lycée (secondary school for pupils from 15 to 18 years of age) in France to prepare deaf pupils for the Baccalaureate. So it was useful after 20 years of experience to ask whether the structure that had been set up matched what the pupils needed to succeed and to fulfil themselves. Grouped together in a specific class, they were integrated in an ordinary class that prepared them for the Science Baccalaureate in 4 years. They sat for the Baccalaureate exams under the same conditions of anonymity as the non-deaf students, and pursued varied studies over increasingly long periods of time. Autonomy and a sense of responsibility made these young deaf people more determined, tougher, and more persevering while at the same time encouraging a harmonious relationship with non-deaf people. Motivation, integration, and communication with non-deaf people and mastery of the language are essential factors in adapting to the work world. One obstacle remains: the use of the telephone. Despite their deafness, the former pupils of the Lycée J. Renard felt fully integrated into social and professional life (author's summary).

Evaluative Commentary – A long-term experiment with a significant number of pupils that shows the contribution of integrative education to the social and professional integration of young deaf people.

Author and Title - Giroud-Pamier, Marie-Claude: Poetic writing and argumentation.

Publication Details - Institute of young deaf people of the region of Auvergne "Les gravouses" Gérard Philippe in Clermond-Ferrand.

10 years of integration in the Collège Gérard Philippe (1983-1993) page 30 to 40.

Centre régional de documentation pédagogique d'Auvergne (Regional centre of educational documentation of Auvergne). Collection of documents.

Language - France.

Country of Origin - French.

Type of Research - Description and analysis of a teaching method for 16-year old deaf students (classe de seconde).

Methodology - After articles presenting deafness, the contribution of sign language and supplemented spoken language, of the verbal-tonal method in learning, this article precisely describes the use of poetic writing in the learning of argumentation, a skill that is expected during the French exam of the Baccalaureate.

Main Findings - A pupil cannot master argumentative techniques (dissertation-summary) if he has not mastered the language. For deaf pupils it is necessary to move from representation (semantic mode) to language in the strict sense that partly escapes representation. The acquisition of language is not training, it is a pleasure. The excursion into poetic writing (the author provides examples of exercises) allows preparation for dissertations and summaries, strengthened by the pleasure of the act of poetry and the final product.

Author and Title - Fournier, Christiane: Sign language: an aid in learning French.

Publication Details - Institute of young deaf people of the département of Auvergne "Les gravouses"/Collège Gérard Philippe in Clermont-Ferrand
10 years of integration in the collège Gérard Philippe (1983-1993) p 41- 50
Centre régional de documentation pédagogique d'Auvergne (Regional centre of educational documentation of Auvergne). Collection of documents.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Type of Research - Description and analysis.

Sample - Collège.

Main Findings - Sign language can be considered as a native language or a first language for deaf children, and can be used as such for teaching French, which is in this case a second language. The use of sign language as a language of reference enables pupils to memorize word meanings better, to understand certain syntactic structures, to become aware of the different levels of the language, and to grasp the variations of the meaning of the word depending on the context. A prerequisite for this learning: thorough knowledge of both languages by the teacher and the children.

Evaluative Commentary - A fine analysis of the links between the two languages, illustrated by many examples and teaching techniques, by a specialist in teaching sign language and a trainer of teachers.

Author and Title - Troel, Dominique: An integration... integrations... two years in a collège for four young highly deaf people.

Publication Details - In Liaisons CNEFJS/ Bulletin du Centre national de formation des enseignants intervenant auprès de jeunes sourds. N° 3/01 2001 (Newsletter of the National Centre for Training Teachers Working with Young Deaf People).

Language - France.

Country of Origin - French.

Type of Research - Personal experience and qualitative analysis.

Methodology - This article presents an experiment in the integration of four young deaf people in a collège. The author proposes questioning the experiment while stressing that the article does not claim to be a review or an assessment.

Main Findings - Educational integration in an ordinary class of a collège leads young people and the people in their environment to define first of all their position as adolescents and pupils in the group, which requires reciprocal information. The stakes are considerable, and they result in a discussion about ethics, economics, linguistics, and teaching. As for teaching, the existence of a palliative interface, sign language, should not lead us to forget the indispensable role of teaching.

Evaluative Commentary – An original analysis of the specific character of teaching deaf pupils in a collège as it raises a number of problems that may seem isolated from one another.

Author and Title - The integration of deaf pupils in secondary education.

Publication Details - CNEFEI (Centre national d'études et de formation pour l'enfance inadaptée - National Centre of Studies and Training for Handicapped Children), 1994.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Type of Research - Text of reports read at a national teacher-training course

Methodology - This report describes, among other things, several experiments in secondary schools (collèges and lycées) with the use of LPC (supplemented spoken language) or sign language (bilingual teacher or interpreter).

Sample - Deaf children, adolescents and young adults from nursery school to the university.

Main Findings - Considerable resources are used here: financing of interpreters by regional authorities, high degree of involvement on the part of the teaching team and parents. The rapporteur stresses the fragility of an atypical and uncertain system.

Evaluative Commentary - This experiment dates from 1994, and the report indicates positive points but also difficulties with this system. A certain number of these difficulties have been solved since then by establishing a national policy and its implementation with human and material resources.

Publication Details - Liaisons/ Bulletin du centre national de formation des enseignants intervenant auprès des jeunes sourds N°8 (Newsletter of the National Centre for Training Teachers Working with Young Deaf People) 1996.

Language – French.

Country of Origin – France.

Type of Research - Texts of discussions during a day-long conference.

Methodology – This text deals with the general framework of educational integration, methods, the role of different participants, and presents integration experiments in a short and concise way.

Sample - Deaf adolescents in secondary schools (collèges and lycées).

Main Findings - Among the various contributions, the following should be mentioned:

Tagger, Nicole, *l'intégration: les modalités de coopération entre l'établissement spécialisé et l'établissement d'accueil*. Pages 43 to 48 (*Integration: methods of co-operation between the specialised school and the host school*).

Van Iseghem, Richard, *l'expérience des classes conjointes INJS de Paris-Collège P. Alviset*. Pages 61 to 68 (*The experiment of joint INJS classes in Paris at the Collège P. Alviset*).

Duroux, Y; Jambert, B, *Intégration en collège*, pages 85 to 93 (*Integration in a collège*).

Abid, Hamadi; Bourque, Richard, *présentation d'un dispositif d'intégration de classes spécialisées dans les lycées d'Argenteuil*. Pages 99 to 105 (*presentation of a system of integrating specialised classes in the lycée of Argenteuil*)

Manteau, Elisabeth, *des classes spécialisées pour jeunes sourds intégrées à un lycée public*. Pages 111 to 116 (*presentation of a system of integrating specialised classes in the lycée of Argenteuil*).

Evaluative Commentary - A work rich in many original ideas and experiments, including some covering several decades. The roles of all the participants – teachers, institutional authorities, pupils, people from outside the schools, families – and many systems – individual and collective integrations, support services – are all discussed. Each article is too short for an individual presentation, but the sum of all of them, in addition to more general articles, shows recurring themes in the conditions for success of integration.

Author and Title - Bourque, Richard: The deaf adolescent in a technical or professional lycée.

Publication Details - In Le courrier de Suresnes, Centre national d'études et de formation pour l'enfance inadaptée (National Centre of Studies and Training for Handicapped Children). Dossier: Educational integration in secondary school. N° 68 Pages 29 to 33, 1996.

Language – French.

Country of Origin – France.

Type of Research – Analysis.

Main Findings – Care must be taken not to underestimate the difficulties of the young deaf person or the person with hearing difficulties and educators must not limit themselves to a purely educational approach. Social and professional integration must not be forgotten.

Evaluative Commentary – In the present integrative trend, this analysis reminds readers that the role of adults is not to act as a “prosthesis” for schooling, but to develop the autonomy of the young person in his educational, professional, and social life.

Author and Title - Tagger, Nicole: *Communication with a young deaf person. A short manual for teachers who have a pupil with an auditory deficiency in their class.*

Publication Details - Lyon, Presses Universitaires de Lyon, collection Ethologie et psychologie des communications, 1994.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Description - Thanks to the integration policy pursued by the Ministry of National Education, more and more deaf pupils are included part time or full time in ordinary classes. The objective of this document is to help teachers who have a deaf pupil in their class to overcome the apprehension and concerns that might be caused by initial difficulties in communicating. It is perfectly possible to communicate with a young deaf person if certain precautions are taken. Most of these precautions are easy to take thanks to the technical recommendations proposed by the author. The appendix contains information enabling the "new" reader to find his/her way more easily in the field of communication problems and their social-educational context (French sign language - LSF, signed French, dactylography/finger spelling, different types of schools, vocational counselling).

Author and Title - Tagger, Nicole: A paradox of educational integration: the deaf pupil helped by his linguistic mediator.

Publication Details - Marginalisation, integration [Dossier] – *La nouvelle revue de l'AS: educational integration and specialized education*, 01/10/1999, n° 8, pp. 131-142.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Description - Since 1975 more and more young deaf people have benefited from integration measures. From the annexed class to individual integration, with or without institutional support, methods and individual paths have become diversified, especially in view of the fact that the French Sign Language (LSF) has at the same time made a big comeback in schools after one century of exclusion. Moreover, new techniques have been developed. Although some systems have not been evaluated, tangible results have been observed: the variety of training programmes and professions now open to deaf people and an increasingly good level of education. However, the dissemination of the most innovative of integration support methods (with an LPC encoder or an LSF interpreter) is still limited. This raises doubts about the reality of integration and raises concern that some projects might lead to illusory results.

Visual Handicap

Author and Title - Guide for teachers teaching a pupil with a visual deficiency.

Publication Details - Ministry of National Education, Teaching Division, 2001.

Language - French.

Country of Origin – France.

Type of Research – Teaching guide.

Methodology - This guide that is aimed at non-specialized teachers who teach visually deficient students in primary and secondary schools. It seeks to strengthen the awareness of teachers to these questions and to propose adaptations in teaching.

Sample - Visually deficient pupils working "in black" (expression used by blind people to refer to the writing of sighted people) in ordinary classes.

Main Findings - The apprehension and concern caused by the arrival of a visually deficient pupil in the class are usual. The difficulties for the adolescent are of a material, organisational, and educational nature. The methodological aid is used especially at the beginning of the year. The adaptation of written documents is an essential point.

Evaluative Commentary - This very concise guide presents the technical and medical aspects of visual deficiency, and then describes the technical and afterwards the pedagogical adaptations, to be implemented. It focuses mainly on learning in primary school, but the general recommendations are also appropriate for secondary school.

Author and Title - Lewi-Dumont, Rochette, Remond: The educational integration of visually deficient adolescents in secondary school structures.

Publication Details - In Le courrier de Suresnes, Centre national d'études et de formation pour l'enfance inadaptée (National Centre of Studies and Training for Handicapped Children). Dossier: Educational integration in secondary school. N° 68 Pages 49 to 55, 1996.

Language – French.

Country of Origin – France.

Type of Research - Qualitative and quantitative.

Sample - Visually deficient adolescents, a survey of all of France.

Main Findings - Three constant factors essential to successful integration in school are identified:

- It must be accompanied by social integration and the achievement of pupil autonomy
- It must be measured on the basis of success in school
- It must remain an educational choice and must be supported by human and material resources.

Author and Title - Lewi-Dumont, Nathalie et al: The education of pupils with visual deficiencies in ordinary schools [Dossier].

Publication Details - *Réadaptation*, 01.12.1998, n° 455, pp. 3-48.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Description - This dossier, aimed at helping and informing primary and secondary school teachers with visually deficient pupils in their classes, presents in the introduction the history of the education of children with visual deficiencies. It is structured in three large chapters. First of all it explains the characteristics of visual deficiency, its impact on the individual, and gives a definition of the visually deficient pupil. Then it discusses the different teaching methods and presents specialised schools with their adapted systems as well as the different forms of integration in schools (from early childhood to higher education). Finally, the last part, more specifically aimed at teachers, provides many educational and pedagogical points of reference, proposes pedagogical adaptation tools, and discusses several specific techniques like Braille, locomotion, or AVJ (Activités de la Vie Journalière – Everyday Life Activities). Four pages of documentation with administrative provisions, official texts, acronyms, useful addresses and a bibliography complete this dossier.

Motor and related disabilities

Author and Title - Guide for teachers who teach a pupil with a motor deficiency.

Publication Details - Ministry of National Education, Teaching Division, 2001.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Type of Research – Teaching guide.

Methodology - This guide, which is aimed at non-specialised teachers who teach pupils with motor deficiencies in primary and secondary schools, seeks to develop the awareness of teachers to the key issues and to propose adaptations in teaching.

Sample - Primary and secondary school pupils with a motor deficiency.

Main Findings - When teachers want to adapt teaching to pupils with motor disabilities, they often think of limiting physical or environmental constraints. The difficulties due to problems related to their handicap, in particular perceptual, cognitive, or emotional ones, are less obvious but nonetheless considerable.

Evaluative Commentary - This guide clearly describes the position of the pupil in the complex situation of a person with a motor deficiency, but also of a person in his/her environment, and it proposes initiatives that take this into consideration and that deal with this whole set of parameters.

Author and Title - Delile, Michèle: Pursuing the educational integration of young people with motor handicaps in college.

Publication Details - DDEEAS report. Resource centre of the CNEFEI, Suresnes, 1997.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Type of Research - Survey carried out in five specialised aid services.

Sample - In this survey the individual integration process of adolescents and children with motor disabilities in ordinary school structures in Seine St. Denis and Val de Marne is discussed.

Main Findings - Through the analysis of the relation between individual integration and education, the author defines on the one hand the priority qualities of the integrated child, expected by partners during an individual integration – general autonomy, scholastic skills, attitudes appropriate for a child, support of the family – and on the other hand the limits of the integration carried out by the collège and the school. The study of the similarities and differences in the five integration aid services and the analysis of the objectives of the school for the child with a motor disability leads to a definition of the problematic factors – material constraints, the school population, changes of structures, entry into adolescence, desire for normalization – and the favourable elements – an appropriate material and human environment, information and training of teachers, support by a care-providing service – to integration in the school programme.

Lastly, a correlation is established between the expectations of the three components of integration - the family, assistance services, and the school - in order to try to open prospects for orientation for a joint integration policy.

Author and Title - Monnain, Claude: Educational integration of adolescents with physical and sensory disabilities in the college.

Publication Details - DDEEAS report. Resource centre of the CNEFEI, Suresnes, 1997.

Language - French.

Country of Origin – France.

Type of Research – Study.

Methodology - On the basis of questionnaires and interviews the author shows the position and the role of the care-providing service and its director in supporting educational integration.

Sample - Adolescents with physical and sensory handicaps supervised by a care-providing centre in the Loiret region who are integrated individually and collectively.

Main Findings - Referring to various texts and laws and to the specific problems related to the special character of disabilities, the author shows the dynamic and original approach of initiatives carried out in order to meet the needs of the young person and his family.

On the basis of two examples of integration he shows that the initiatives of preparation and implementation of projects favour integration, hence the specific role of the director.

Author and Title - Ministry of National Education and CNEFEI: National Centre of Studies and Training for Handicapped Children: The education of children and adolescents with problems of health in primary school, in the collège and the lycée.

Publication Details - Paris, *Réadaptation*, 01/11/1995, n° 424.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Description - This special issue entitled "Dossiers on integration" of the review *Réadaptation* deals with the education of pupils with health problems. Its purpose is to meet more effectively the needs of children and adolescents suffering from disease who attend schools. In this issue we find technical data about some fifteen diseases (asthma, cancer, cardio related conditions, epilepsy, haemophilia, neuromuscular diseases, AIDS etc). For each disease a clinical chart is presented. This chart indicates the problems caused by the disease and the interventions proposed. Practical advice is also given (adjustable furniture, contact information about the attending physician etc) as well as pedagogical recommendations to be followed (scholastic support, another person to help, time for exams etc). Lastly, this dossier contains the addresses of different organisations able to provide assistance or additional information. The official texts from the Ministry of National Education concerning this problem are in the appendix.

Intellectual disabilities

Author and Title - Handicap and educational integration.

Publication Details - Publications de Montlignon n°29, 1997.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Type of Research - Reports on policies, presentation and analyses of experiments.

Methodology - This collective work presents official texts and outlines the changes in policies that have led to educational integration. Experiments in collective and individual integration are presented. Some have been dealt with in other reviews in articles mentioned: *Integration in collèges of adolescents with a mental handicap* (P-H Vinay); *An original integration experience through sports activity* (J-C Bruyez); *The experience of an integrated class at the collège-Lycée of St Michel de Picpus* (C Philip); *The integrated system of the "E. de Marlonne" collège with the SESSAD "La Senelle" in Laval* (R Leblanc).

Sample - Pupils with intellectual deficiencies, behaviour problems, and serious communication problems are collectively integrated into primary, and especially secondary schools.

Author and Title - Courteix, M.C; Gautheron, G; Imbert, M. - Integration of young adolescents in an UPI.

Publication Details - In Le courrier de Suresnes, Centre national d'études et de formation pour l'enfance inadaptée (National Centre of Studies and Training for Handicapped Children). Dossier: educational integration in secondary school. N° 68 Pages 34 à 39, 1996.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Type of Research - Longitudinal survey over 6 years.

Methodology - Description of the plan for the functioning of one of the first UPIs of France.

Sample - Adolescents with mental handicaps, mostly adolescents with Down's syndrome in collective integration in a college.

Main Findings - A host population without special difficulties is a prerequisite for the success of this approach. The flexible collective system makes it possible to define individual plans, and the educational ideas that arise therefore apparently benefit everyone.

Evaluative Commentary -This article describes the experiment in the collège shown in the audiovisual document "From nursery school to the collège: the integration of children and adolescents with mental deficiencies" described later in this review.

Author and Title - Courteix, Marie-Claude and Gazay-Gonnet, Dominique – *From the nursery school to the collège*. Video cassette VHS, SECAM colour, sound.

Publication Details - Editions du Centre National d'Etudes et de Formation pour l'Enfance inadaptée (CNEFEI), Suresnes, 1996.

Language - French.

Country of Origin – France.

Type of Research – Descriptive.

Methodology - Film. Collection of data. Information, explanations, exchanges and complementary experiences shed light on this data.

Sample - Children with intellectual deficiencies integrated into CLIS (Classes d'Intégration Scolaire – Educational Integration Classes) and UPIs (Pedagogical Units of Integration).

Main Findings - Since 1990 children with intellectual deficiencies have pursued a programme in the schools of Puy-de-Dôme. Most of them attend the CLIS (Classe d'Intégration Scolaire – Educational Integration Class) at school and continue their studies in the UPI (Unité Pédagogique d'Intégration – Pedagogical Integration Unit) of a collège. These structures are supervised by specialised teachers. In secondary school some of the teaching time is provided by the teachers of the collège. The children that are integrated in this way (attendance of ordinary classes at school, physical education and sports and English at the collège), share space with the other pupils (recreation, meals etc). Supervision is provided by different institutions or specialised services. In addition to this approach to problems and privileged institutional strategies to solve them, the film explores various sequences characteristic of school life, and presents interviews of professionals that have contributed to integration in nursery school, elementary school, and in the college.

Evaluative Commentary – This film shows that integration requires the preparation of a personalised plan for each child, according to his/her potential, acquired skills and knowledge, as well as needs on the educational, emotional and therapeutic levels.

Author and Title - Chaumon, Monique and Vinay, Pierre Henri: The integration of mentally handicapped adolescents in the college.

Publication Details - The AIS dossiers in secondary education N°1 January 1997. Editions du Centre National de Suresnes (CNEFEI) Paris-Cronstadt centre.

Language – French.

Country of Origin – France.

Type of Research - Description and analysis on the basis of a national survey.

Methodology - The objective of this survey was to list all the structures and systems that enable mentally handicapped adolescents to study in a collège, to analyse several significant experiments with classes “annexed” into the collège, to describe the specific character of the UPI system, and to define the conditions and factors favourable to the functioning of the UPIs. The results of the national survey on educational integration of young people with mental handicaps in the collège are presented and analysed.

Main Findings and Evaluative Commentary – A complete survey of the functioning of the UPIs on the national scale that clearly identifies the types of functioning and organisations conducive to proper education of young people with mental handicaps: the “human” scale of host schools, an “ordinary” school population, a fixed room for the pupils, a teaching team that volunteered for this role, training for this team, a prior agreement and a multi-partner plan, personalised and adaptable teaching plans, regular work with families.

Author and Title - SEGPA of the collège Paul Bert, Institut Médico educational collège of Auxerre (Yonne).

Publication Details - Integration in SEGPA - second review of the results of co-operation between a therapeutic-educational institute and a SEGPA of a collège. School year 1994-1995.

Language –French.

Country of Origin – France (Yonne).

Type of Research - Review of an experiment

Methodology - The authors describe integration experiments over two years and analyse the conditions for these integration activities; the reactions and developments that they lead to among the professionals of the two schools.

Sample - Mentally handicapped adolescents in a college.

Main Findings - It is not only necessary to build a general framework for integration, it is also necessary to build adaptable, personalised integration paths with the help of a multidisciplinary team, in which each participant's contributions are clearly defined and complementary.

Evaluative Commentary - A brief analysis (19 pages) that nonetheless reviews all the difficulties that arise and that proposes approaches to overcome them before, during, and after educational integration.

This experiment has been discussed in many articles, including one in the courrier de Suresnes (CNEFEI) n°63, a description of the conditions of educational integration in the SEGPA, presented below.

Author and Title - Mege-Courteix, Marie Claude: Mentally handicapped adolescents in a college.

Publication Details - Learning to live together: handicap and educational integration. Pages 165 to 176: Regional centre of educational documentation of Clermont-Ferrand, 1998.

Language – French.

Country of Origin – France.

Type of Research - Analysis of an experiment.

Methodology - Analysis of the conditions for successful integration.

Sample – Collège.

Main Findings - The conditions for successful integration are linked to rather constant data. Factors are, for example, the quality of preparation, information and co-ordination; the follow-up both of the collective plan and the personalised plans; relationships between host schools and support services, and the development and dynamics of the approach of the plan.

Evaluative Commentary – A discussion of the conditions, difficulties, and advantages of integration which opens up a discussion - without taking a position - on an essential aspect of the evaluation of integration: success after studies in the college.

Author and Title - Integration in secondary school, a necessary step.

Publication Details - In Le courrier de Suresnes (CNEFEI) n° 63, pages 71 to 78, 1995.

Language – French.

Country of Origin – France.

Type of Research – Analysis.

Methodology - Analysis of an integration experiment in terms of its concrete aspects (meals, travel etc) as well as its institutional aspects (profile of young people, links with commissions etc) and educational aspects (meetings with young professionals, projects etc).

Sample - Pupils of an IME (a specialised school) in SEGPA (educational adaptation system).

Main Findings - Integration is possible in secondary school. This requires (in 1995) overcoming many difficulties, organizing multi-disciplinary supervision, and personalising as much as possible the programme for pupils for whom educational integration is only a gateway to social and professional integration.

Evaluative Commentary – A survey that proposes ideas to think over, and presents an organisational structure that is still relevant even if the administrative environment and resources have since changed.

Author and Title - Philip, Christine: The educational system and young autistic people.

Publication Details - Learning to live together: handicap and educational integration. Pages 177 to 189; Regional centre of educational documentation of Clermont-Ferrand, 1998.

Language – French.

Country of Origin – France.

Type of Research - Description and analysis.

Methodology - Study of establishing one of the first classes for autistic adolescents in a college.

Sample - Autistic pupils in a college.

Main Findings - Setting up a class for autistic adolescents requires overcoming a certain number of difficulties: a host school must be found, the framework for co-operation between teachers and parents must be defined, the worries of the teachers and the other pupils must be eliminated. The newness of this point of view on handicaps seems to be beneficial for all.

Evaluative Commentary - In addition to the description and the relevant analysis of the system, this article raises questions related to the functioning of this type of system: what is the role of care in it (this dimension was not studied because it was absent from this experiment), and what is the future for pupils after the collège?

Author and Title - Triquet, Francis: Opening the collège to adolescents with a mental handicap.

Publication Details - In Revue du CERFOP (Cercle d'études et de recherches sur la formation professionnelle – Circle of studies and research on professional training) n° 12 Pages 179 to 187, 1997.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Type of Research - Qualitative.

Methodology - This article, written by the principal of a collège, describes the setting up of a UPI and its impact on the teachers' methods and the life of the collège.

Sample – Collège.

Main Findings - General information about the people in the concrete situation (teachers and pupils) shows the partnership between teachers and with outside professionals are indispensable prerequisites for successful integration. This integration has a positive impact on the educational methods of the teachers (in particular those with pupils with scholastic problems), on the life of the school, and on the general education of the pupils of the college.

Evaluative Commentary – With great modesty, the author forgets one very important factor in the success of this experiment: the strong and constant involvement of the head of the school in maintaining links with the partners, the material conditions of education, and the support for the teaching methods and experiments.

Author and Title - Clere, J: Educational integration: discussions and reviews of a method in specialised education.

Publication Details - *The neuropsychiatry of childhood and adolescence*, 01.05.1998, n° 5-6, pp. 328-334.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Description - Educational integration brings the child, the family, and the school into play. Educational integration must not consist of haphazard action based on utopias because it is the child in difficulty who will pay the price. The review of several years of work in specialised education leads to the conclusion that the destabilising forces affecting professionals and national education in particular must be stopped. The modest results cannot justify any passivity combined with depression.

Author and Title - Grubar, Jean-Claude. Ed; Martinet, Monique Ed; Muh, Jean-Pierre: *Autism and integration*.

Publication Details - Villeneuve-d'Ascq, Presses universitaires de Lille, 1994.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Description - This book provides a panorama of the integration of autistic children. In the first and second parts it deals with the problems of educational integration encountered by parents, the educational and therapeutic team, and the child him/herself. The third part reports on the present situation of educational integration in France. The fourth part discusses educational adaptation through educational integration.

Author and Title - Hochmann, Jacques: A collective educational integration with children with developmental problems.

Publication Details - Educational integration: myth or reality? [Dossier] - *Psychologie et éducation*, 01.09.1999, n° 38, pp. 39-49.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Description - The access to social integration of children with developmental problems also requires educational integration. In this article J. Hochmann presents his ideas, the fruit of some thirty years of experience. The techniques implemented to facilitate integration do not eliminate all the difficulties described. The TEACCH method is called into question in terms of the author's frame of reference, namely psychoanalysis.

General questions and issues

Author and Title - Belmont, Brigitte; Verillon, Alette; Auble, Jean-Pierre: To integrate handicapped children in ordinary classes: what types of co-operation?

Publication Details - Marginalization, integration – *La nouvelle revue de l'AS: educational adaptation and integration*, 01/10/1999, n° 8, pp. 186-197.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Type of Research - Qualitative and prospective.

Methodology - Including children in ordinary classes most often entails educational arrangements taking the children's difficulties into account. Teachers participating in integration initiatives want to be helped, in particular by specialised professionals that keep track of these children. The description and analysis of these wishes constitute the substance of this article.

Sample - Handicapped children integrated in ordinary classrooms.

Main Findings - This article presents the work methods that may be implemented between the teachers in the host school and the specialists in regular contact with them. In the exchanges that take place between them the pooling of observations about the child, plays an essential role.

Evaluative Commentary - From their co-operation both teachers and specialists derive help in their integration work, but there is also a professional benefit. Their co-operation also provides an opportunity to think over the way to take into consideration the needs of all pupils.

Author and Title - Bonjour, Pierre and Lapeyre, Michèle: Semaphores to shed light on the educational adventure.

Publication Details - Educational integration: myth or reality? [Dossier] - *Psychologie et éducation*, 01.09.1999, n° 38, pp. 57-66.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Type of Research - Descriptive and prospective.

Methodology - The intention of the authors is to re-launch a dynamic process that has slowed down by the introduction of new educational objectives. Official statements in France over the past twenty years about integration might suggest that handicapped pupils or pupils in great difficulty are increasingly kept in an ordinary environment, thanks to the development of integration systems. Unfortunately, this idea must be carefully and clearly qualified according to the two authors. In their opinion, even if there has been a switch from an approach focused on the institution to an approach focused on the notion of service, the difficulties of “professional positioning” caused by the notion of service among personnel too often trigger defensive reactions that are an obstacle to integration.

Sample - Handicapped children

Main Findings - The authors describe educational integration as a singular, complex process dependent on the environment. If one aspect of the needs of the child is forgotten, integration may fail.

Evaluative Commentary - It is important to develop tools and models facilitating the preparation and monitoring of individualised support plans. The point is to provide tools for the teachers’ objectives and to move from *intentions to action*, in terms of the help sought. According to the authors, four factors must be considered: the emotional factor, the social factor, the cognitive factor, and the instrumental factor. A support plan neglecting one or several of these spheres would lead to an impasse. It is in the name of the right to integration for all pupils that an evaluative, forward looking and multi-faceted approach is required.

Author and Title - Bonjour, Pierre; Lapeyre, Michèle; Stiker, Henri-Jacques Préf:
The integration of pupils with specific needs, from intentions to action.

Publication Details - Ramonville-Saint-Agne, Erès, 2000.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Type of Research - Descriptive, analytical, prospective.

Methodology - The authors have carried out an extensive investigative project on the theme of educational integration of children with specific needs.

Sample - Handicapped children.

Main Findings - Sometimes certain things are impossible, but some things are also necessary. The necessary and the impossible must not be placed in a position of opposition to one another, nor must they necessarily determine a choice. On the contrary, they should be linked. The value from the authors is that they propose a tool for action. Their “semaphore” can be used by individuals suffering from a handicap as part of a self-evaluation approach.

Evaluative Commentary - The proposal to set up integration tools that take into account all the parameters of the child as subject seems relevant. The point is to lead people in difficulty to become the protagonists of their own integration process.

Author and Title - Boye, Valérie: *Educational integration auxiliaries in Bas-Rhin: training, function, and the pupils being educated.*

Publication Details - CREAL, Strasbourg, 1998.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Type of Research - Descriptive.

Methodology - Descriptive

Sample - Normal classrooms.

Main Findings - The educational integration auxiliary is an “experimental” professional that can be found especially in Alsace. This document reports on a study conducted by the CREAL d’ALSACE on the evaluation of needs in this field.

Evaluative Commentary - There is a real need in the field for educational support for handicapped children, but at the same time the study raises the question of the permanence and structuring of this support.

Author and Title - Gardou, Charles: What integration for the third millennium?

Publication Details - Educational integration: myth or reality? [Dossier] - *Psychologie et éducation*, 01.09.1999, n° 38, pp. 29-38.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Type of Research - Prospective.

Methodology - Analytical.

Sample - Schools.

Main Findings - The author analyses the conditions that might lead to integration in action at the beginning of the 3rd millennium. The point is to approach the child's difficulties in terms of educational challenges to be met, but also to use resources that make it possible to move from physical integration to true integration in society.

Evaluative Commentary - Accepting heterogeneity as the ordinary condition of schools constitutes a step forward toward creating an environment for all. This requires taking into account the problems of access to knowledge, but also the development, through education, of a true culture of integration.

Author and Title - Lesain-Delabarre, Jean-Marc and Garel, Jean-Pierre: Being the parent of a handicapped pupil as a profession: strategic aspects of educational integration.

Publication Details - Marginalisation, integration [Dossier] – *La nouvelle revue de l'AIS: educational adaptation and integration*, 01/10/1999, n° 8, p. 221-232.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Description - The parents of a handicapped pupil develop various strategies aimed at supporting the education of their child. The analyses of interviews of three families reveal challenges that mobilise these families as well as the elements of being the parent of a handicapped child as a “profession” in terms of five types of activity. The most important aspect of this profession is not the type of activity of the parent, but rather the way these activities are carried out. Some attitudes seem to be particularly important.

Author and Title - Monville, Michel. Dir; Tomkiewicz, Stanislas and Gardou, Charles [et al.]: Educational integration: myth or reality? [Dossier].

Publication Details - *Psychologie et éducation*, 01.09.1999, n° 38, 111 p.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Description - Even though educational integration can be included in laws, its concrete implementation entails ethical principles about the respect which is due to the handicapped person. Awareness of the need to accept difference does not eliminate the need for critical distance: the ideological and economic stakes involved require great vigilance. This discussion is first based on interviews conducted by Stanislaw Tomkiewicz and Charles Gardou. It is completed by reports of integration experiments with various types of handicaps.

Author and Title - Plaisance, Eric: What integration?

Publication Details - Marginalisation, integration [Dossier] – La nouvelle revue de l'AI: educational integration and specialized education
01/10/1999, n° 8, pp. 61-73.

Language - French.

Country of Origin - France.

Description - The educational integration policy for handicapped children is first of all placed in the context of other social policies developed in France, at least as concerns the terms used. The notions of social and cultural integration and of insertion thus raise the question of their relation to assimilation or differentiation. The situations of Italy and Great Britain are then examined from the viewpoint of general orientations, procedures, and terms adopted in the field of special education since the end of the 1970s. For example, the discussions underway in Great Britain on the notion of special educational need and inclusive education are mentioned. Lastly, the obstacles to the extension of educational integration in France are analysed on the basis of surveys of teamwork, partnership, and co-operation.

Appendix D: GERMANY

Author and Title - Siegfried Arnz: Integration an der Hauptschule? Warum eine gemeinsame Beschulung auch an Hauptschulen sinnvoll und erfolgreich sein kann.

Publication Details - Berliner Lehrerzeitung (blz), 51/ 55 (1997)5, 10-11

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Germany.

Type of Research - Report of experience from point of view of the head teacher.

Sample - Integration classes in a "Hauptschule" (School at lower secondary level providing a basis general education) in Berlin.

Main Findings - Description of the organisational possibilities and the kind of realisation of inclusive education inside and outside lessons for children with and without SEN in a "Hauptschule".

Evaluative Commentary - In Germany's tripartite secondary educational system the "Hauptschulen" play a qualitatively important role next to the comprehensive schools. The flexible organisational and practical kinds of the realisation of inclusive education for pupils with and without SEN in the "Hauptschule" is described from the point of view of the head teacher.

Author and Title - Ines Boban: "Ist es Liebe, wenn man ganz nahe bei einem sein will?" A review of 6 years integration in a comprehensive school in Hamburg.

Publication Details - Behinderte in Familie, Schule und Gesellschaft, 19 (1996)3, 5-11.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Germany.

Type of Research - Report of experience

Sample - One integration class in a comprehensive school in Hamburg.

Main Findings - Report of experience about inclusive education and ensuring the development of personality of mentally retarded children in a comprehensive school.

Evaluative Commentary - Vivid description of the possibilities and difficulties for meeting and developing the needs and abilities of pupils with mentally handicaps in a comprehensive school.

Author and Title - Gerda Dicke, Rainer Maikowski: Das Spannungsverhältnis zwischen individueller und gemeinsamer Förderung in der Sekundarschule und die praktischen Möglichkeiten der Gestaltung und Planung des Unterrichts.

Publication Details -3-407-25206-4, Ulf Preuss- Lausitz, Ulf; Rainer Maikowski (Eds.): Integrationspädagogik in der Sekundarstufe, Weinheim und Basel: Beltz Verlag, 1998, S. 218-233.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Germany.

Type of Research - Overview of principles and methods of inclusive teaching practice in integration classes at secondary level.

Sample - Integration classes in secondary schools in Berlin.

Main Findings - This article describes the special and - as regards content - significant conditions for teaching and learning as well as the organisational prerequisites and methodical/practical possibilities for inclusive education at the secondary level of education.

Some charts (giving the framework of dimensions and criteria for differentiation; forms of teaching; structural elements of inclusive education; general and individual work schedules for students of German language classes) clarify the content further.

Evaluative Commentary - In the field of inclusive education at the secondary level this is a very useful help for orientating professionals, with concepts for development and methods for planning classes.

Author and Title - J. Friedemann, A. Nolke, E. Görge, u.a.
Gemeinsamer Unterricht in der Sekundarstufe I.

Publication Details - ISBN: 3-88327-318-X, Monographie, Frankfurt/ M., 1994.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Germany.

Type of Research - Anthology of different articles about inclusive education in secondary schools in Hessian (Federal State of Germany).

Sample - Integration classes in the secondary school.

Main Findings - Inclusive education for pupils with and without disabilities. The articles in this book show that inclusive education is also successful at the secondary level.

Evaluative Commentary - The articles provide an introduction to the practice of inclusive education at secondary schools in Hessian.

Author and Title - U. Harth, B. Ockenfels: "Eine Schule für alle Kinder". Gemeinsamer Unterricht von behinderten und nichtbehinderten Kindern und Jugendlichen in der Sekundarstufe I der Gesamtschule Holweide.

Publication Details - Köln 1993, Schriftenreihe des Kultusministeriums Nordrhein-Westfalen, Heft 52, Verlagsgesellschaft Ritterbach mbh.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Germany.

Type of Research - Report of experience.

Sample - Integration classes of one comprehensive school.

Main Findings - Examples of practice of inclusive education in different subjects as well as the extra curricular sector at one comprehensive school.

Evaluative Commentary - Reflection of the construction and practice of inclusive education at one comprehensive school in North Rhine Westphalia (Federal State in Germany).

Author and Title - Anne Hildeschmidt, Alfred Sander: Integration behinderteter Schüler und Schülerinnen in der Sekundarstufe I.

Publication Details - Heilpädagogische Forschung, 21 (1995)1, 14-26.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Germany.

Type of Research - Qualitative and quantitative empirical investigations, and the discussion of their results.

Methodology - Observation in lessons, interviews with parents, socio-metric investigation, analysis of different educational targets.

Sample - Mainstream schools with integration classes in a school experiment in Saarland (Federal State of Germany).

Main Findings - Summary of a research report about the development in a school experiment for the integration of pupils with disabilities into the lower secondary school. Topics: parents` view; team-teaching, German language, maths, integration of pupils with learning disabilities.

Evaluative Commentary - Evaluation of possibilities and problems of inclusive education in this Federal State with respect to the political/educational framework of conditions.

Apart from the instance of positive initial stages of the development, there is a critical view of the results of an expansion of inclusive education at the secondary level.

Author and Title - Inge Krämer- Kilic: Zur Bedeutung kooperativen Lernens in integrativen Klassen dargestellt an Hand eines Unterrichtsbeispiels.

Publication Details - Zeitschrift für Heilpädagogik, 52/2001/1, S.22-27.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Germany.

Type of Research - Analysis of one example in class.

Methodology - Discussion of the effectiveness of the programme for co-operative learning in inclusive education.

Sample - One integration class in a secondary school.

Main Findings - The theoretical explanations of the effectiveness of co-operative learning as well as the example of the selected classroom activities show that the potential for development of inclusive education is to be found in further didactic development of the power that lies in the interaction between peers. It is in this mutual process that more grounded experience and knowledge such as receptive kinds of learning will be promoted.

Evaluative Commentary - This contribution shows the significance that types of co-operative learning have for the social and academic development of students (in integration classes).

Author and Title - Almut Köbberling: Gemeinsamkeit und Vielfalt: Wege in verschiedene Lebenswelten.

Publication Details - ISBN 3-7799-1382-8, in Anne Hildeschmidt, Irmtraud Schnell (Eds.): Integrationspädagogik; Auf dem Weg zu einer Schule für alle. Juventa Weinheim 1998, S.257-276.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Germany.

Type of Research - Interviews with parents and teachers, observations in classes, social analysis of the climate in classes, emotional conditions, self- concept and the network of social relationships, discussion of the results.

Methodology - Quantitative and qualitative empirical investigations over 10 years.

Sample - 79 integration classes in a Hamburg school experiment on the secondary level.

Main Findings - The résumé of some important findings of the scientific survey of the experimental integration of students with a mental disability in Hamburg comprehensive schools focuses on social and emotional development.

The young peoples` crises of finding an identity and attempts to overcome these are described with respect to traditional forms of education as well as educational modifications and a higher degree of initial individualisation and differentiation in the teaching of subjects.

Evaluative Commentary - In the discussion of the results the author makes clear that mentally handicapped students prepare themselves for different perspectives in life through their "integrative, inclusive and special learning" and obtain "scope for [their] own decisions" through the methods of individualisation and joint advancement.

Author and Title - Johannes Lambert: Notengebung für Schüler mit Behinderungen. Ein Thema für alle Schularten.

Publication Details - Schulverwaltung. Ausgabe Baden-Württemberg, 11/2002/7-8, S.148-151.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Germany.

Type of Research - Aids for orientation on the basis of practical experience with giving marks in one Federal State in Germany.

Methodology - Description from principles and their illustration for daily life in schools.

Sample - Different types of schools in Baden Württemberg (Federal State of Germany).

Main Findings - General principles for measuring the achievement and for giving marks to students with disabilities are formulated and in individual cases checked for their practicability. Concrete questions of procedure and possible legal aids are presented.

Evaluative Commentary - This is a practical basis for orientation in making individual decisions when giving marks to students with disabilities.

Author and Title - Sabina Lange: Die Klasse mit dem doppelten I. Erfahrungen einer Integrationsklasse in einer IGS.

Publication Details - Zeitschriftenaufsatz; Beispiele, 18/2000/2, S.31-34.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Germany.

Type of Research - Report of experience.

Methodology - Interviews.

Sample - Integration class in a comprehensive school.

Main Findings - The special conditions in a comprehensive school are beneficial for students with learning disabilities.

Various possibilities open up with joint teaching between several teachers.

An interview gives an interesting view of personal attitudes, expectations and requirements of those involved.

Evaluative Commentary - A good insight in practical work in an integration class and the teachers' point of view.

Author and Title - Manfred Rosenberger (Eds.): Schule ohne Aussonderung –Idee, Konzepte, Zukunftschancen.
Pädagogische Förderung behinderter und von Behinderung bedrohter Kinder und Jugendlicher.

Publication Details - ISBN 3-472-03008-9, Luchterhand, Neuwied, Kriftel, Berlin 1998.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Germany.

Type of Research - Reports of the “Länder” and basic articles.

Sample - Practice of inclusive education in all “Länder” of Germany.

Main Findings - Programmes, legal aspects, problems in the school organisation, important implementation strategies, financing, integrative didactics in the primary school and starting points for the secondary level are described and then are developed for the achievement of the idea “ School for all”.
They show the present state of implementation in Germany as well as the plans for the future.

Evaluative Commentary - A wide view of concepts, practice and problems in inclusive education in Germany.

Author and Title - Rainer Maikowski: Modelle der Integration in der Sekundarstufe.

Publication Details - ISBN 3-87964-280-X, In: Petra Gehrman, Birgit Hüwe
Forschungsprofile der Integration von Behinderten, Bochumer Symposium, Essen
1993, S. 148-172.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Germany.

Type of Research - Discussion of concepts and practice of integration at the
secondary level.

Sample - Practice of integration in Germany.

Main Findings - This report deals with political, educational and organisational pre-
requisites in inclusive education at the secondary level. It shows the pros and cons of
the different models and describes the development and problems in individualisation
and differentiation of integrated educational practice.

Evaluative Commentary - Critical overview of the political/educational conditions
and practical potential of development in inclusive education at the secondary level.

Author and Title - Dieter Dumke: Schulische Integration in der Sekundarstufe.

Publication Details - ISBN: 3-7799-1382-8, In: Anne Hildeschildt; Irmtraud Schnell (Eds.) Integrationspädagogik. Auf dem Weg zu einer Schule für alle. Juventa, Weinheim 1998, S.241- 256

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Germany.

Type of Research - Discussion of the results of different questionnaires and socio-metric investigations of teachers and students in secondary schools in North Rhine Westphalia.

Methodology - Secondary analysis of empirical classroom investigations.

Sample - Secondary schools with mainstreaming in North Rhine Westphalia.

Main Findings - The willingness or non - willingness of teachers towards inclusive education depends on their attitudes concerning the possibilities of integrating disabled students in secondary schools. Two objections are often mentioned:

- those of a formal and legal quality
- those of a methodical and didactical quality.

Taking in account the structural problems of inclusive education in the German hierarchical system of secondary education, the author discusses the attitudes of teachers and students toward inclusive education and describes the basic requirements of such an education: team-teaching, individual differentiation, learning in projects, working in groups, weekly planning (Wochenplanarbeit) and their effects on achievement and social integration.

Evaluative Commentary - A very useful summary of attitudes of students and teachers towards inclusive classroom practice and the requirement of such an educational approach.

Author and Title - Marianne Poppe: Grundlegende didaktische Anforderungen an integrativen Unterricht in der Sekundarstufe I.

Publication Details - ISBN: 3-407-2506-4, In: Preuss- Lausitz, Rainer Maikowski (Eds.): Integrationspädagogik in der Sekundarstufe. Gemeinsame Erziehung behinderter und nichtbehinderter Jugendlicher. Weinheim: Beltz, 1998, S. 172-189.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Germany.

Type of Research - Discussion of didactical requirements for classroom practice in secondary schools against the background of the author's own practice and of teaching and the counselling of teachers.

Methodology - Description of basics: didactical models and practical steps to reach inclusive classroom practice.

Main Findings - In teaching and counselling teachers the author tried to develop the concept of inclusive education. This is the background to the discussion of the basic didactical requirements of inclusive education in secondary schools in this report:

- structural pre-suppositions (place, space, time, methods of teaching)
- basics for inclusive education (heterogeneity, equality, differentiation, community and self-government) didactical models.

Evaluative Commentary - A highly recommended handling of inclusive classroom practice in secondary schools.

Author and Title - Ullrich Heimlich, Sven Jacobs (Eds.): Integrative Schulentwicklung im Sekundarbereich. Das Beispiel der Integrierten Gesamtschule Halle/ Saale.

Publication Details - Bad Heilbrunn: Klinkhardt, 2001, S.205pp.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Germany.

Type of Research - Evaluation research in connection with an inclusive school development.

Methodology - Combination of quantitative (questionnaire from students and teachers) and qualitative methods (case studies, group discussions, observations, dialogical evaluation) in the framework of evaluative research.

Sample - 4 mainstream classes in an integrated secondary school in Halle / Saale. (in Saxony Anhalt, a Federal State in Germany) within the school years 1997/98 (75 students, 8 teachers, 4 students with learning difficulties) and 1998/99 (80 students 7 teachers, 4 students with learning difficulties).

Main Findings - The integration of students with learning difficulties into inclusive classes in secondary schools requires inclusive processes on several levels:

- individual education of students with SEN
- integrated learning situations
- interdisciplinary teams
- inclusive school programmes.

Evaluative Commentary - There are no problems in social, emotional integration as well as integration on the level of academic goals for students with learning difficulties in secondary schools if an academic programme is implemented that includes basic elements of open education such as working plans for a week, daily times of free work, learning stations and an individualised classroom education. The main reason for the success of inclusive education in this school is the co-operation within the interdisciplinary teams and not only the co-operation between two teachers in the classroom. At the end of the first two years of school development the integrated secondary school in Halle / Saale decided to build inclusive classrooms from school year 5 to 10.

Appendix E: GREECE

Author and Title - Helios European Seminar: Legislation on Educational Integration in Europe: Trends and Changes.

Group II: Trends and Changes in Secondary Education – Educational System and Integration in Greece.

Publication Details – Ministry of Education, Pedagogical Institute, Athens, 1996.

Language – Greek.

Country of Origin – Greece.

Type of Research - Discussion of research findings.

Methodology - The main aim of the research was to record the trends and views of people in SEN field.

Sample - Part I: Secondary School teachers in 1,300 SEN school units in all over the country.

Part II: 200 secondary teachers – random sampling.

Main Findings - Limited funding for inclusion processes

- Lack of teachers' training in SEN issues and inclusion practices
- Students' drop out from secondary education is mainly caused by the lack of differentiated curricula
- Limited use and knowledge of Information Technology benefits.

Evaluative Commentary - Although the aim of the study was to push governmental bodies to revise policies concerning inclusion processes, teachers' self evaluation and open-minded views concerning their professional status in SEN forum did not prove strong enough to achieve it. The study could have a more elaborated next stage.

Author and Title - Venetta Lampropoulou: The integration of Deaf Children in Greece: Results of a needs assessment study.

Publication Details - Tel Aviv Academic Press: Ramot Publishing, 1998.

Language – English.

Country of Origin – Greece.

Type of Research - Quantitative analysis.

Methodology - Survey Questionnaire.

Sample - Parents of deaf children (N=33), Teachers of deaf children (N=44), Deaf adults (N=18).

Main Findings - According to the results the 3 groups identified different needs and priorities. However there were 4 similarities in the perception of needs and priorities: 1) deaf awareness programmes for hearing teachers and students, 2) services of a psychologist, 3) support services, 4) pre-vocational training. Additionally teachers and parents seemed to have similar views related to audio-logical provision and support services. Deaf adults were the most critical of the educational programmes provided in integrated units, while teachers were the least critical.

Evaluative Commentary - People who were involved in the education of deaf children were not satisfied with the educational programmes in integrated units. Deaf children in ordinary schools may face problems of discrimination and isolation without the provision of awareness programmes. Finally, deaf people should participate in the decision making process of the schools.

Author and Title - Venetta Lampropoulou: Special Schools or Full Inclusion? Problems and Needs as Perceived by Deaf Students.

Publication Details - Australian Association of the Deaf Inc. 1999.

Language – English.

Country of Origin – Greece.

Type of Research - Quantitative and Qualitative analysis.

Methodology - Survey questionnaire and semi-structured interviews.

Sample - 18 deaf students who graduated from special schools for the deaf and school/classes for hearing students.

Main Findings - Deaf people who graduated from both programmes (special schools for the deaf and hearing schools) believed that although the majority of the goals included in the survey were important for the education of deaf children, they were not achieved in any of the programmes. In addition deaf students had not benefited from the education provided in hearing schools.

According to the analysis of the semi-structured interviews deaf people believed that deaf schools helped deaf students to acquire deaf identity, to learn Sign Language and things useful for their life, to communicate and make friends. On the other hand their educational programme was very poor in comparison with that of the hearing schools.

Evaluative Commentary - The educational needs of the deaf students are complex and require a series of support services, appropriate planning, qualitative curriculum and specialised deaf and hearing personnel. The question of where the deaf students should be educated could be replaced by the question of how we can make sure that all deaf students receive all services and support needed in order to achieve a qualitative and equivalent education in any school programme.

Author and Title - Georgia Fantaki: Survey on SEN Units.

Publication Details - Ministry of Education, Directorate of Special Education, 2000.

Language – Greek and English.

Country of Origin – Greece.

Type of Research - Qualitative and quantitative, study, discussion of research findings.

Methodology - The research aimed to record the population of SEN pupils and the framework within which school and social inclusion is pursued.

Sample - Primary and secondary education pupils in total (N= 13,596) of the country (4- 24 years old). The study was addressed to all SEN units (special schools, N=203 and inclusion courses in mainstream schools, N=715).

Main Findings - There has been a tendency of withdrawing pupils from special schools and moving them to mainstream schools. The inclusion practices employed in secondary schooling are still very poor since subject teachers have a limited knowledge of how to differentiate their work as well as how to deal with the “different”.

Evaluative Commentary - The limitation of the research is the “distance response” to questionnaires. Although the method was proved reliable (pilot work, double checking of answers, comparative studies with official documents), there was no chance for observations. The main implications emerging from the results is the design of teachers’ in-service training and the establishment of more inclusion courses.

Author and Title - Susana Padeliadu & Antonia Patsiodimou: Attitudes and Perceptions of Teachers about the Training in Special Education.

Publication Details - Thessaloniki, Action Joint-Stock Company, 2000.

Language – Greek.

Country of Origin – Greece.

Type of Research - Quantitative analysis.

Methodology - Survey questionnaire and interviews.

Sample – 2,428 Teachers in total (Primary Education, N= 1,536, Secondary Education, N=405, In-service Training Programmes, N=487).

Main Findings - According to the results, teachers of secondary education seemed to prefer training programmes of special education rather than programmes focusing on one category of special needs. However they mainly preferred training on issues relating to behavioural problems and learning disabilities. Regarding the skills that needed to be acquired, higher mean scores appeared about behavioural organisation, parents' counselling and motives of learning for SEN pupils. Additionally, practice at schools was of main importance and especially teaching in a whole class of SEN pupils rather than teaching in an integration unit or teaching only one SEN pupil. Finally, the motives for participating in training programmes were: the information about "within the class" problem solving as well as personal interest.

According to the findings of the interviews, teachers of regular classes did not know what their attitude towards SEN pupils and what their role as a teacher should be. The differentiation of the attitude towards SEN pupils seemed to be strongly dependent on appropriate training programmes after which the attitude changes.

Evaluative Commentary - Teachers of secondary education seemed to have lower interest about special education. That can be attributed to the very few special education units in secondary education and shows the necessities for the near future.

Author and Title - Susana Padeliadu & Venetta Lampropoulou: Adolescence and Youth - Attitudes towards students with special needs and their integration.

Publication Details - Nea Paideia (Journal) 2000.

Language – Greek.

Country of Origin - Greece.

Type of Research - Quantitative analysis.

Methodology - Scales: Attitudes Towards Disabled Pupils (ATDP) & towards school integration – Padeliadu (1994).

Sample - 995 pupils in total (High School, N=312, Lyceum, N=367, University N=316).

Main Findings - Students were more positive towards disabled students, while there was no statistically important difference between pupils of High School and Lyceum. Regarding their attitude towards school integration of SEN pupils, there were the same results as above. Additionally according to the analysis of Mann-Whitney for the differences due to the gender, it was found that there was statistically important difference only for the pupils of high school. Specifically, girls were more positive than boys towards the integration of SEN pupils.

There was an additional analysis on whether attitudes towards SEN pupils is a predictive factor for attitudes towards school integration. It was found that pupils with more positive attitude towards disability had more positive attitude towards school integration.

Author and Title - Argyropoulos, V: An Investigation into Tactual Shape Perception and Geometrical Concepts in Students who are Blind (2002).

Publication Details - Dissertation (PhD, University of Birmingham).

Language – English.

Country of Origin – Greek.

Type of Research - Qualitative analysis.

Methodology - Action Research: set of activities, open-ended interviews. Middle-order categories (Dey, 1993).

Sample - N=35 teachers (Special school, N₁ = 20 teachers & Mainstream school, N₂ = 15 teachers).

Analytical study of 19 blind and visually impaired students.

Main Findings - Information obtained by tactual exploration is not always in accordance with information obtained by geometrical constructs (theorems, rules, and postulates). It depends on touch, posture, movement, language, prior knowledge and conditions of the tasks.

The power of repetition causes the formation of spatial representations.

Memory by touch (Haptic memory) when dealing with geometry, is much more powerful than sighted memory.

Tactual shape perception depends heavily on orientation of shapes.

Standard geometric vocabulary appears to be a barrier for communication between students, teacher-student, student-text-books.

There is an inconsistency between levels of understanding & Curriculum.

The Curriculum depends more heavily on instruction than on levels of understanding.

Social, political, ethical and cultural issues are involved in the way of blind students' understanding.

Evaluative Commentary - It is felt that the way in which the parameters of tactual shape perception relate to a shape concept constitutes a multidimensional interrelating system to formulate a level of tactual imagery which leads to shape coding. This analysis sheds light on the state of our knowledge of the way by which students with severe visual impairments recognise a shape via the parameters of tactual shape perception.

This study which concentrated initially on the individual, broadened to other contexts apart from those which were connected to school, developing a consideration of social and political factors and the impact of these factors on the individual's cognitive development.

Author and Title - Dragona, Davou: Learning Difficulties in Secondary Education.

Publication Details - Doxiadis Institution: Athens.

Language – Greek.

Country of Origin – Greece.

Type of Research - Qualitative analysis of case studies in Perama secondary schools.

Methodology - Observations on inclusion processes.

Sample - Students in mainstream schools, 12-16 years old, poor socio-economic background. The area of Perama belongs to Borough of Piraeus. The majority of the population can be described as working class.

Main Findings - Relationship between socio economic factors and implementation of school policy.

Evaluative Commentary - Interesting observations and remarks on school policies.

Appendix F: ICELAND

Author and Title - Eggertsdóttir, R., Marinósson, G. L., Sigales, C., Auðunsdóttir, I., Haraldsdóttir, H., Pacheco, J., Wilhelm, M., & Jónsdóttir, B. 2002, Bætt skilyrði til náms. Starfsþróun í heildtæku skólastarfi. (Pathways to inclusion. A guide to staff development.)

Publication Details - Book edited by Eggertsdóttir, R., Marinósson, G. L., Reykjavík: Rannsóknarstofnun Kennaraháskóla Íslands [Iceland University of Education Research Institute].

Language – Icelandic.

Country of Origin - Iceland, Austria, Portugal, Spain (a European Leonardo da Vinci project).

Type of Research – Qualitative multiple case study.

Methodology - The purpose of the ETAI study (enhancing teacher abilities in inclusion) was to identify common elements in exemplary practices in inclusive education in a variety of school contexts and to construct staff development material for compulsory school staff that could be used internationally. For this purpose case studies were made in four European countries. The case studies were first analysed separately and then together to bring out common elements. A handbook of staff development was based on the findings.

Sample - Compulsory schools that had shown exemplary practices in inclusive education were chosen to serve as cases in each country by the respective national representatives in the study. All were compulsory mainstream schools. In Austria and Iceland the focus was on one classroom, in Portugal on one school and in Spain (Catalunya) on three school clusters of an infants' and a primary school.

Method of Research - Interviews, observations, document analysis.

Main Findings – Nine issues emerged as important and common for the successful implementation of the policy of inclusive education in all the cases: preparation for schooling, curriculum planning, classroom practice, collaboration and co-ordination, pupils' social interaction, home-school collaboration, evaluation and assessment, support services and staff development.

Evaluative Commentary - This is one of a number of case studies on inclusive education to be published in Iceland and Europe in recent years. What sets it apart is the methodology that makes it easier to draw out common elements. Although the emerging themes are largely institutional in their formulation the details provided on preparation for schooling, collaboration at all levels of organisation and a variety of teaching methods makes the study valuable as a basis for school development in the direction of educational and social inclusion. Implications for classroom practice are therefore considerable.

Author and Title - Einarsdóttir, S. 2002, Að vera í sérdeild. Átján fyrrum nemendur lýsa reynslu sinni. [Attending a special unit. Eighteen former pupils describe their experiences].

Publication Details - Unpublished M.A.thesis, University of Iceland, Reykjavík.

Language – Icelandic.

Country of Origin – Iceland.

Type of Research - Qualitative study.

Methodology - The objectives of the study were to investigate the participants' experience of being in a special unit for some time during their school years and secondly to study their career after leaving school. Focus was on their feeling of well-being, their educational attainments and social relations in the special unit compared to that in a mainstream class.

Theoretical framework included theories of normalisation, integration and inclusion.

Sample - 18 individuals, aged 18-29 years old, who all attended a special unit in mainstream compulsory school at age 13, 14 or 15.

Method of Research - In-depth interviews on past experience.

Main Findings - The support provided for pupils with special needs in mainstream classrooms is in many instances insufficient. The pupils interviewed generally felt comfortable in the special unit they attended, primarily because they mastered the work required of them. Some felt that the curriculum in the special unit was too limited and restricted their options in upper-secondary school. The social standing of these individuals in school varied a great deal, social inclusion depending on their prowess in sport and games. Some felt that the special unit isolated them from the mainstream. Most of the participants had had difficulties with their further studies but managed well in a job.

Evaluative Commentary - This is a valuable contribution to the limited knowledge that we have of pupils' own experiences in school. Implications for classroom practice are that if all special needs pupils are to receive their education in mainstream classes, the teaching has to change in the direction of greater personal support and encouragement for those who find it difficult to master the work and feel socially included. Early intervention for this purpose is necessary, as is fewer pupils per teacher, greater support for class teachers and improved teacher knowledge and skills with special needs pupils. This applies particularly to pupils who have multiple difficulties. Mixing pupils who primarily have learning problems with those primarily with behaviour problems in a small group in a special unit is counter productive.

Author and Title - Marinósson, G. L. - The response to pupil diversity by a mainstream compulsory school in Iceland.

Publication Details - Unpublished Ph.D. thesis. Institute of Education, University of London, London.

Language – English.

Country of Origin - Iceland.

Type of Research - Long- term ethnographic case study.

Methodology - The purposes of the study were to describe how a mainstream compulsory school reacts to a diversity of pupil needs and attempt to explain why it reacts as it does. Diversity in this context refers to diversity in educational needs. Theoretical framework included social constructionism, symbolic interactionism and organisation theory. Data collection spanned over 3 years.

Sample - One compulsory mainstream school was selected as a case.

Method of Research - Interviews, observations, document analysis.

Main Findings - The findings show that although the school works according to a national policy of inclusive education, it implements it only to a limited extent due to a number of institutional influences that produce a variety of special educational needs. These influences are based on often contradictory value systems including market, bureaucratic and pedagogic values, notions of knowledge and professional group interests. These influences at the macro level are counteracted by Christian, humanitarian values and notions of equity and equality at the micro level. The resultant dilemma is a reflection of the school's hybrid role as a bureaucratic, pedagogic and professional institution. The author concludes that these institutional influences need to be recognised for the present psycho-medical categorisation of special needs to be deconstructed to give room for a pedagogic construction of pupil diversity.

Evaluative Commentary - The research approach used here - ethnography that focuses on institutional factors influencing the construction of special needs - provides a valuable alternative view of issues that are traditionally discussed within a psycho-medical paradigm. As regards implications for classroom practice the study describes a number of practices and notions that contribute to the construction of special educational needs.

Appendix G: LUXEMBOURG

Author and Title - Teachers of the “Technical Secondary School (régime préparatoire)” in Esch-sur-Alzette, Luxembourg with the help of SCRIPT, the university of Namur and SPOS.

Report 1998-1999: Project “Elèves en difficultés” (Pupils with special educational needs).

Publication Details - Luxembourg, 1998-1999.

Language – French.

Country of Origin – Luxembourg.

Type of Research - Report, experiences, ideas, evaluation of the project.

Methodology - Interviews and personal reports from teachers and students about the project.

This document presents the implementation of the project at the Technical Secondary School (régime préparatoire) in the south of Luxembourg (Esch-sur-Alzette).

Sample - Teachers working with students with special educational needs in a Technical Secondary School; pedagogues working at the university of Namur, professionals of the services SCRIPT and SPOS; students with special educational needs (especially learning disabilities, behavioural problems).

Main Findings - The teachers involved in this project want to improve and develop the students’ cognitive, social and emotional competences. They wish to motivate the youngsters, to give them self-confidence, confidence in adults and in school.

Evaluative Commentary - The teachers of “Technical Secondary School” in Esch-sur-Alzette have exchanged their ideas and practices, have created, experimented with and searched for new procedures, methods, ways to help students with special educational needs.

The teachers have noticed an improvement in the progress and behaviour of the students.

The students like the new methods, the new school.

Author and Title - Teachers of “Technical Secondary School” in Ettelbruck, Luxembourg and other Secondary Schools, professionals of the services SCRIPT and SPOS, professionals of the university of Namur (FUNDP).
Report 1998-1999: Project “Elèves en difficultés (Pupils with special educational needs).

Publication Details - Luxembourg, 1998-1999.

Language – French and German.

Country of Origin – Luxembourg.

Type of Research - Report, experiences, ideas, evaluation of the project.

Methodology - Interviews and personal reports of teachers’ and students’ perspectives.

Sample - Teachers working with students with special educational needs in Technical Secondary School; pedagogues working at the university of Namur, SCRIPT, SPOS; students with special educational needs (especially learning disabilities, behavioural problems).

Main Findings - The teachers involved in this project want to improve the students’ cognitive, social and emotional competences. They want to motivate the youngsters, to give them self-confidence, confidence in adults and in school.
This report shows the importance of team-work.

Evaluative Commentary - Fundamental statements made by teachers concerning the assistance of students with special educational needs:

1. to have a positive, confident and benevolent approach towards the disabled student, to restore his self-opinion and confidence;
2. to allow the students to feel assured, secure through the fact of being part of a class, a group;
3. to develop a class-contract with the students in order to create a “respectful” atmosphere, environment;
4. to create a relaxed and open “adult-student relationship”;
5. to develop the student’s motivation for education and his/her independence, autonomy;
6. to listen to the student in an open and individualised way;
7. to stimulate the student’s awareness of his learning process;
8. to control conflicts between students through dialogue;

Team-work, dialogue between teachers, preparation of pedagogical projects, exchange of ideas, problems and solutions are all highlighted as important factors.

Author and Title - Ministère de l'Éducation Nationale, de la Formation Professionnelle et des Sports: Plan-Cadre pour classes à enseignement fondamental (Enseignement Secondaire Technique Régime préparatoire).

Publication Details - Ministère de l'Éducation Nationale, de la Formation Professionnelle et des Sports, Luxembourg, 2001.

Language – French.

Country of Origin – Luxembourg.

Type of Research - A descriptive and evaluative report.

Methodology - Report

Description of pedagogical projects in Secondary Technical Schools (régime préparatoire), the objectives and means to assist students with special educational needs.

Sample - Teachers working with students with special educational needs in Technical Secondary School (régime préparatoire); students of Technical Secondary School with special educational needs; SCRIPT: “Département Education et Technologie de la FUNDP Namur”.

Main Findings – This document presents examples of projects for students with special educational needs in Technical Secondary School.

An important point is to open the school to “partners”, to create an “educative community”, a TEAM of professionals (teachers, pedagogues, psychologists etc) working together, exchanging ideas, sharing the same aim to create a stimulating educational atmosphere for each individual student.

Evaluative Commentary - The document shows the importance of preparing projects in order to help students with special educational needs, to create a school atmosphere that takes notice of the needs and abilities of each individual child.

Author and Title - M. Gaston Greiveldinger, Director of Technical Secondary School, Régime Préparatoire: L'enseignement modulaire: Une voie de la réussite ? Une voie de l'échec ?

Publication Details - Lycée Technique du Centre (LTC), juin 2000.

Language – French.

Country of Origin – Luxembourg.

Methodology - Report, Description.

Sample - Students with special educational needs in Technical Secondary School (régime préparatoire) seem to:

- lack factual knowledge and “savoir-faire”;
- be students with low cultural capital;
- present learning problems;
- have low level in languages;
- lack self-control;
- present behavioural problems, temperamental troubles.

Main Findings - School cannot mean the same for each individual student.

An adapted pedagogy will allow the student to progress, develop according to his/her progress and affinities while improving his/her strong points and developing his/her autonomy: the rhythm of his/her progress in different subjects will not necessarily be synchronous. The duration of the studies is not fixed in advance.

The “parking” aspect of school:

- This type of school is not really acceptable;
- Contents and programmes are not adapted to the abilities of the students;
- Unfavourable working conditions;
- Risk of accelerated “burn out” for teacher and student.

What is required is:

- Planned transition from primary to post primary education;
- Students with special educational needs are able to evaluate if certain learning conditions are respected;
- Creation and experimentation of new pedagogical approaches for the teachers.

Evaluative Commentary - The aim of the “regime préparatoire” is to prepare the students for another pedagogical approach in Technical Secondary Education and to get a professional qualification.

An adequate pedagogical practice is to improve the 3Ds - lack of motivation (démotivation), disengagement (désengagement), discouragement (découragement) - of the student. This requires a change of methods and psycho-pedagogical assistance in: the redefinition of contents and programmes; the individualisation of education; the redefinition of modular teaching; pedagogical innovation.

Appendix H: The NETHERLANDS

Author and Title - Berkenbosch, J.R. (1997).

Regionale samenwerkingsverbanden VO-VSO: stand van zaken (in beleidsperspectief).

Publication Details - Amsterdam: SCO-Kohnstamm Instituut.

Language - Dutch.

Country of Origin - The Netherlands.

Type of Research - Qualitative and quantitative research.

Methodology - The focus of this study is the co-operation between regular and special secondary education schools. The main questions of the research are: in what way do the schools co-operate and what are the effects of co-operation? Documents were analysed and co-ordinators of the regional clusters completed questionnaires.

Sample - 66 of the 85 co-ordinators of regional school clusters completed the questionnaires (78%).

Main Findings - Half of the clusters have taken measures to stimulate co-operation between regular and special secondary education schools.

The most important activities that have been started as part of the co-operation include initiating pedagogic-didactic arrangements - remedial teaching, programmes to solve problems: 70% of clusters; (preventive) peripatetic supervision; 90% of clusters; part-time education at regular schools for SEN students: 59% of clusters; courses to improve knowledge about handicapped students: 97% of clusters; and making appointments about referring students: 58% of clusters. The co-ordinators think that:

- both peripatetic and preventive peripatetic supervision has led to a higher number of students obtaining a regular certificate (81%)
- less referrals to secondary special education schools (66%)
- teachers in regular secondary education becoming more willing to accept differences between students when teaching (57 and 49% resp.)
- a higher number of regular secondary schools having a more specific policy on dealing with handicapped students (54 and 38% resp.)
- part-time regular and part-time special secondary education has resulted in making a switch from special to regular education easier (91%)
- changed teachers' attitude towards differences between students in their classroom (46%)
- defined regular schools' policies on dealing with handicapped students (44%)
- the newly developed placement options in the projects enabled students to attend an educational setting (86%)
- the effect of the co-operation between regular and special secondary schools was that students were not referred to special education schools (41%)
- the knowledge of teachers on educating special needs students was enhanced (60%)

- schools changed their policy towards having special needs students (59%).

Evaluative Commentary - The study does not focus on effects or outputs in terms of academic achievement, emotional outcomes or social behaviour of students integrated in regular secondary schools

Author and Title - Kool, E. and Derriks, M. (1995). *Ambulante begeleiding. Werkwijzen en effecten.*

Publication Details - Amsterdam: Stichting Centrum voor Onderwijsonderzoek (SCO).

Language - Dutch.

Country of Origin - The Netherlands.

Type of Research - Descriptive research.

Methodology - The second part of this study focuses on the relationship between ambulant teaching and the effects at student level. Integrated students who are referred from a special to a mainstream school are allowed to make use of ambulant (or peripatetic) teaching. Special school teachers visited mainstream schools to work with special needs students and to support the classroom teachers. Ambulant teachers and principals completed questionnaires.

Sample - 50 special schools participated in this study (25 primary and 25 secondary education schools). Within each school, one ambulant teacher was selected. Two students and their classroom teachers from each ambulant teacher were picked out to participate. A total of 47 secondary school students were selected: 25 with severe and 22 with mild handicaps.

Main Findings - Findings indicate that most students who received ambulant teaching performed in accordance with, or above, expectations. Compared to their regular education peers, 54-69% of these students achieved an average or above average level in reading, spelling, maths and Dutch language. Concerning social-emotional functioning, for at least 89% of the students no decrease was reported; 87% of the students were considered to be motivated. Overall, 89% of the students were successfully included. Students who were not successfully included were mainly severely mentally retarded.

Evaluative Commentary - Results indicate that one of the criteria for referring students to regular schools using ambulant teacher support is an above average social-emotional level of functioning. In this sense results could reflect the selection procedures. From the start of the placement in mainstream education, these students' motivation and self-confidence were considered to be higher than those of their regular education peers.

Author and Title - Oudenhoven, D. and Baarveld, F. (1999). *De opvang van gehandicapte leerlingen in het reguliere basis- en voortgezet onderwijs.*

Publication Details - Nijmegen: Instituut voor Toegepaste Sociale wetenschappen.

Language - Dutch.

Country of Origin - The Netherlands.

Type of Research - Qualitative research.

Methodology - This study focuses on the following questions:

- What measures are taken to integrate handicapped students in regular primary and secondary schools? (What provisions are made in terms of staff and material facilities, what is the role of external experts?)
- What is the opinion of teachers and support staff on the effects of integrating handicapped students?
- What are obstructing and stimulating factors for successful integration?

Questionnaires were completed by principals and ambulant teachers (teachers who are connected to a special education school and visit mainstream schools to work with individual students and support their regular teacher). In addition, ambulant teachers were interviewed.

Sample - The sample of the secondary education part of the study consisted of 69 principals and 55 ambulant teachers of 69 handicapped students (8 blind, 22 partially sighted, 4 deaf, 11 hearing impaired, 3 with severe speech disorders, 12 physically handicapped, 7 multiple handicapped, 2 unknown).

Main Findings - Findings suggest that 33% of secondary schools integrating handicapped students receive one hour extra per week to support the student, 10% receive 2.3 or 4 hours per week, while the other schools did not receive extra hours. In 85% of schools the buildings were adjusted for the handicapped students.

Most of the schools (89%) took special practical-organisational measures in order to care for the handicapped students.

In general no special didactical measurements were taken and 60% of the handicapped students used the same materials as the non-handicapped ones. Most handicapped students (84%) participated in the whole educational and activity timetable.

Some of the handicapped students received extra support from ambulant teachers for an extra 7 hours a month on average.

Almost all of the principals think that the inclusion led to more teacher expertise and more willingness to integrate handicapped students. In their opinion negative points included more pressure on teachers, less attention for other students and lower tempo of the lessons.

According to teachers, students feel accepted in the school and have good relationships, especially with adults. The opinion of teachers towards the behaviour and self-confidence of the students was also positive. Teachers were less positive about academic achievement and social skills.

Important factors for integrating handicapped students in secondary schools are personal skills such as ability to communicate well, able to eat and drink themselves, mobility and intellectual skills.

Evaluative Commentary - The study results are based on perceptions of effective classroom practices and do not contain evidence-based information.

Author and Title - Oudenhoven, D. and Romijn, C. (1998). *Onderzoek naar de Ambulante Begeleiding vanuit de Ammanstichting*.

Publication Details - Nijmegen: ITS.

Language - Dutch.

Country of Origin - The Netherlands.

Type of Research - Qualitative and quantitative research.

Methodology - This study focuses on peripatetic supervision for deaf or hearing impaired students or students with severe speech disorders in regular primary and secondary schools. The perception from schools, teachers, students and their parents about peripatetic supervision was studied using telephone interviews.

Sample - 89 students in regular secondary schools were receiving peripatetic supervision from appropriate special schools. The researchers took a sample of schools that received peripatetic supervision. Finally, 43 secondary schools were in the sample and only 17 schools (1 school for deaf students, 12 schools for hearing impaired students and 4 schools for students with severe speech disorders) participated. The researchers also took a sample of parents who were involved: 41 parents were in the sample and 29 parents participated.

Main Findings - Some findings about the content of the peripatetic supervision were discussed with the schools. According to the parents the peripatetic supervision was good; for deaf and hearing-impaired students a little better than for students with severe speech disorders. Parents perceived that students had some problems in understanding the lessons, but they hardly had problems with feeling at home at school, in contact with classmates and adults and in their behaviour at school. Students with severe speech disorders had fewer problems in these areas than deaf or hearing impaired students.

Evaluative Commentary - The study results are based on perceptions of the schools and parents and do not contain evidence-based information.

Author and Title -Thema groep 9 (1996). *Helios II programma. Vergroten van de samenwerking tussen regulier voortgezet en speciaal onderwijs/ Programm Helios II. Für eine Verstärkung der Kooperation zwischen Regelschulen und Sonderschulen.*

Publication Details - Trykkeri: A/S Modersmålets.

Language - Dutch and German.

Country of Origin - Denmark, but including case study material from the Netherlands.

Type of Research - Qualitative research.

Methodology - This book discusses mainstream and special education interaction through the experiences and conclusions of a working group of people with disabilities, parents, administrators, mainstream teachers, teachers in special education, therapists, and professionals in special needs from 10 European countries.

Part 1 presents fundamental principles for co-operation between special and mainstream education and essential elements for co-operation and transition to an open environment. Part 2 provides brief outlines of special needs education systems in the 10 participating countries, including the country's legislation, facts and figures on students with special needs, overall organisation, types of provision, and future actions. It then describes examples of good practice in the area of mainstream/special education.

Only the part about examples of good practice in the Netherlands was studied.

There are 4 examples in secondary education.

1. Three special secondary schools collaborating with one regular school. The project focused on students with learning, behavioural and social-emotional problems.
2. Five special secondary schools working with five regular schools. The project focused again on students with learning, behavioural and social-emotional problems.
3. This project contained 2 projects for physically handicapped students. The projects focused on co-operation between mainstream and special education in order to integrate students with special needs in mainstream secondary schools.
4. Two special secondary schools work with seven regular schools. The project focused on students with dyslexia, (other) learning problems, behavioural and social problems. After two or three years the students integrate in regular schools

Sample - 1: 4 schools; 2: 10 schools; 3: not clear; 4: 9 schools.

Main Findings - Findings suggest that:

1. mainstream and special schools succeeded in collaborating. The number of drop-outs was also reduced;
2. co-operation between schools was successful;
3. activities were as expected, but more involvement from the whole team would have been preferred;
4. more students were integrated in mainstream schools

Evaluative Commentary - The study results are based on perceptions of the schools and do not contain evidence-based information.

Appendix I: NORWAY

Author and Title - Skårbrevik, J. K. (1996): *Spesialpedagogiske tiltak på dagsorden. Evaluering av prosjektet "Omstrukturering av spesialundervisning"* (Special education measures on the agenda. Evaluation of the "Special Education Restructuring" project).

Publication Details - Møreforskning. Research report no. 14/96.

Language - Norwegian.

Country of Origin - Norway.

Type of Research - Quantitative & qualitative.

Methodology - The purpose of this study was to evaluate the extent to which the restructuring of special needs education was achieved. The goal of this restructuring was to give students with special educational needs equitable, local and adapted education. The focus of the evaluation was to conduct an analysis of the transition from political decisions to local action plans (municipal/county municipal). Another purpose of the evaluation was to identify factors of importance in order to implement equitable, adapted and local education.

Sample - The survey's population was children and adolescents who received special needs education on a case-by-case basis. This corresponded to some 8,000 children of pre-school age and 30,000 pupils at primary and lower secondary school and approximately 8–10,000 students in upper secondary school. The sample was based on a representative sample of municipalities and a certain number of children at each age level. This sample matched the GSI database for primary and lower secondary school.

Method of Research - Descriptive; Questionnaire.

Main Findings - Key aspects of adapted and inclusive education for pupils with special educational needs were assessed in order to determine the extent to which these needs were met. The following areas appeared to be of importance:

- Sufficient scope of special needs education
- Schooling adapted to the pupil's educational needs
- Training resources according to the needs of the pupil
- The pupil benefits from the schooling
- Teachers have sufficient expertise
- The teaching enables pupils to participate in classroom teaching
- The classroom environment promotes social inclusion
- The programme of studies promotes personal growth
- The majority supported the view that at present pupils with special needs receive and benefit from adapted and inclusive education at school.

Parents' assessment of pupils' progress was positive. Parents assessed pupils' level of enjoyment as high or very high. The results indicated that parents believe that schools are more successful at achieving social inclusion than academic progress.

Evaluative Commentary - This study showed that local solutions for adapted and including education are being developed at schools.

Author and Title - Skogen, K., Nes, K., Strømstad, M. (to be published in 2003): *En vurdering av om innføring av L 97 har ført til at skolen har utviklet en inkluderende praksis, faglig, sosialt og kulturelt.* (Has the introduction of Reform 97 lead to the development of more inclusive practices in schools – socially, academically and culturally?)

Publication Details - Final report of the "Evaluation of Reform 97" research programme.

Language - Norwegian.

Country of Origin - Norway.

Type of Research - Quantitative & qualitative.

Methodology - The project sought to evaluate the implementation of the "Reform 97" school reform in terms of inclusion. The concept of inclusion was operationalised according to the cultures, policies and practices of the school. An important source was *Index for Inclusion – Developing Learning and Participation in Schools* by Booth, T, and Ainscow, M. & al., Bristol, 2000. Professor Tony Booth was the project's consultant.

Sample - The evaluation took place in one municipality in Hedmark county – Ringsaker. The survey's informants were parents, students and teachers. The project also included action research at a few schools, where the Index for Inclusion was used for school development.

Method of Research - Survey, case studies, observations and interviews.

Main Findings - The preliminary results of this study showed that:

- The main actors at school – school managers, teachers, etc. – do not have a uniform and shared view of the term 'inclusion'.
- The form in which it is practiced in the classroom varies greatly.
- An including practice is gradually being developed.
- It is unclear how much "Reform 97" has influenced these developments.
- In order to succeed at inclusion, the following characteristics appeared to be crucial.

A large degree of:

- adapted education in three areas: academic, social and cultural
- good pupil/pupil and pupil/teacher relations
- belonging
- participation
- influence
- co-operation between pupils
- co-operation between teachers and pupils
- co-operation between teachers.

Evaluative Commentary - The main conclusion of this research project was that work of including pupils into the classroom is under development. Schooling that is academically, socially and culturally adapted to pupils is a key factor in assessing good classroom practice. Ensuring that all pupils have good relationships and feel a

sense of belonging is crucial, as well as pupil participation, influence and good working relationships in order to contribute to the development of good classroom practice.

Author and Title - Nordahl, T, Sørli, M (1998): *Project School and Behaviour Problems: Brukerperspektiv på skolen - elever og foreldre om skole og relasjoner* (A user's perspective on school – pupils' and parents' view of school and relations).

Publication Details - Norwegian Social Research (NOVA): Report 12d/98.

Language - Norwegian.

Country of Origin - Norway.

Type of Research - Quantitative.

Methodology - The aim of the project was to contribute knowledge relevant to the field of education about behavioural problems in the school setting. This was achieved through an empirical follow-up study focusing on stability in the competence and behaviour of pupils at three age levels, and selected contextual factors in the school environment, with special focus on pupils with behavioural problems. Characteristics of the pupils' competence, attitudes, behaviour at school, and their school situation and learning environment were assessed. The theoretical approach was interactionistic and competence-oriented, in contrast to the more common individual problem-oriented focus of comparable studies. International as well as nationally-validated questionnaires were used.

Sample - The sample consisted of all pupils from years 4, 7 and 10 at primary and lower secondary school (aged 9, 12 and 15) from 16 schools in two urban municipalities in Norway. 1,200 children and youths, their teachers, parents, and school administrators participated.

Method of Research - Questionnaire.

Main Findings - The results of this sub-survey showed that pupils' academic performance had little relation to whether they had good or poor relationships with their fellow pupils or teachers. However, there was a clear correlation between low self-esteem and poor relationships at school and between high self-esteem and positive relations. There was a moderate correlation between how pupils assessed their social skills and their relations with fellow pupils and teachers.

This study also looked at the impact on learning of a pupil's positive or negative view of school. Pupils differentiated here between their level of social satisfaction at school and their level of satisfaction with the schooling. The results showed that many pupils found the school situation boring. However, the majority of pupils liked school and were happy there.

Evaluative Commentary - The study showed that there was a correlation between education at school, satisfaction at school and attitudes towards school and learning, according to pupils. Pupils who were not happy with the teaching and who do not see school and learning as important had a clear tendency to display behavioural problems at school.

Author and Title - Sørli, M (1997): *Project School and Behaviour Problems: Atferdsproblemer i skolen. Fokus på stabilitet, endring - og forandring* (Behavioural problems at school. Focus on stability, change – and transformation).

Publication Details - Article from the "Special Education Knowledge and Action Development" research programme (1993-99), *Spesialpedagogikk*, Special issue. ISSN 0332-8457.

Language - Norwegian.

Country of Origin - Norway.

Type of Research - Quantitative.

Methodology - The aim of the project was to contribute knowledge relevant to the field of education about behavioural problems in the school setting. This was achieved through an empirical follow-up study focusing on stability in the competence and behaviour of pupils at three age levels, and selected contextual factors in the school environment, with special focus on pupils with behavioural problems. Characteristics of the pupils' competence, attitudes, behaviour at school, and their school situation and learning environment were assessed. The theoretical approach was interactionistic and competence-oriented, in contrast to the more common individual problem-oriented focus of comparable studies. International as well as nationally-validated questionnaires were used.

Sample - The sample consisted of all pupils from years 4, 7 and 10 at primary and lower secondary school (aged 9, 12 and 15) from 16 schools in two urban municipalities in Norway. 1,200 children and youths, their teachers, parents, and school administrators participated.

Method of Research - Questionnaire.

Main Findings - The study showed that behavioural problems at school are linked to individual and contextual matters. Here individual factors were linked to the pupil – e.g. view of oneself, and academic and social skills. Socio-economic factors in the environment in which a pupil grows up appear to have little impact on how a pupil behaves at school. Pupils being given a voice in relation to school life and clear rules did not appear to be of great importance either. Behavioural problems are linked to the level of pupils' skills and the structural and qualitative aspects of the academic and social conditions for learning.

Evaluative Commentary - The study showed that both individual issues and contextual factors linked to factors such as the classroom environment, the content of schooling and forms of work, participation and clear rules played an important role in the development of behavioural problems.

Author and Title - Ogden, T. (1998): *Elevatferd og læringsmiljø. Læreres erfaring med og syn på elevatferd og læringsmiljø i grunnskolen* (Student behaviour and the learning environment. Teachers' experience and views of student behaviour and the learning environment in primary school).

Publication Details - Oslo: Norwegian Ministry of Church, Education and Research.

Language - Norwegian.

Country of Origin - Norway.

Type of Research - Quantitative.

Methodology - The purpose of this study was to conduct a survey of teachers' experience of behavioural problems at school. Teachers were asked to describe what they had experienced over the past week, with examples of typical problem behaviour.

These teachers were also asked to describe their experience of typical problem behaviour in the classroom over the past school year and the need for educational assistance.

Finally, the teachers were asked to describe their reactions to problem behaviour and to provide suggestions for actions.

Sample - 10 % of all primary schools and lower secondary schools in Norway, selected at random from the Ministry's lists. The response percentage, measured in numbers of teachers who responded, was 66 %, equivalent to 3,661 teachers.

Method of Research - Descriptive; questionnaire.

Main Findings - One general recurring finding was that behavioural problems increased as students aged.

In the main, the study showed little correlation between teacher variables such as gender, age, training and their assessment of the degree of behavioural problems in the classroom.

Serious infringements of standards and rules occurred most often in the classes and schools where the less serious behavioural problems were most prevalent.

The teachers' own assessments showed that schools where teachers state that the school has clear standards for positive behaviour in class and in the school environment, and effective routines for following up any infringement of the school's rules and standards also experience fewer behavioural problems. The content of these standards and routines varied from school to school.

The study also showed that academic shortcomings are more common than behavioural problems at school. Teachers' assessments of pupils' classroom behaviour were less positive than their assessments of their motivation, the work they put in and their satisfaction, but more positive than the assessment of their skills, maturity and academic performance.

Evaluative Commentary - The study showed a connection between (a) clear standards for behaviour and routines for following up any infringement; and (b) behavioural problems experienced less frequently. However, the study did not

indicate any defined content for standards and routines, nor did the design of the study make it possible to check for other causes such as educational organisation. The implications for classroom practice are therefore limited.

Author and Title - Skaalvik, E. M. (1998): project "*Elevenes opplevelser av skolen*" *faglige og sosiale støttetiltak - Skolens vurdering av behov og tilbud* ("Pupils' perceptions of school" – academic and social support measures – the school's assessment of needs and demand).

Publication Details - Article from the "Special Education Knowledge and Action Development" research programme (1993-99), *Spesialpedagogikk*, Special issue. ISSN 0332-8457.

Language - Norwegian.

Country of Origin - Norway.

Type of Research - Quantitative.

Methodology - The purpose of this study was to examine how schools assess pupils' need for academic and social support and support measures, based on the vague and fluctuating boundary between adapted education in ordinary schooling and special needs education. It was also the purpose of the study to examine how teaching is adapted for special needs pupils in a classroom context.

Sample - The sample of pupils consisted of 2,190 pupils in years 4, 7 and 9 in primary and lower secondary school in 532 schools in 14 municipalities in the counties of Sør-Trøndelag and Nord-Trøndelag in 1996. The schools were selected to best represent the counties of the Trøndelag region (stratified selection). The pupils were distributed among 129 classes at school, and all of the pupils in the selected classes participated in the study (except for a few pupils whose parents did not allow them to participate). The distribution of the number of pupils, according to the year at school was the following for year 4: 59 classes and 826 pupils. Year 7: 40 classes and 730 pupils. Year 9: 33 classes and 633 pupils. The need for academic and social support measures was assessed separately. Pupils' need for support was classified using a tripartite scale: 1) No special needs 2) Need for regular support measures 3) Need for special needs education.

Method of Research - Questionnaire.

Main Findings - The study's results indicated that schools may appear to be unable to deal with the natural variation in pupils' abilities, skills, interests and backgrounds. It was the schools' assessment that every fourth or fifth pupil needs specially-adapted schooling. About every third pupil that a school deems requires specially-adapted schooling is not offered such schooling. The fact that so many pupils are deemed as requiring special needs education may indicate that it is difficult for general studies teachers to include and organise individually-adapted schooling for pupils with special needs. There proved to be a lower need for social support than for academic support. The majority of the pupils that needed academic support were also deemed as requiring social support.

Evaluative Commentary - The main conclusion of this report indicated that differentiation and individual adaptation do not characterise all education, but that they characterise general teaching in the classroom. In such a context, a large

number of pupils will need specially-adapted schooling. Schools' perception of their inability to deal with differentiation and individual adaptation may influence the assessment, and may give a higher figure than is actually the case, which may create special educational needs for some pupils. Good classroom practice is characterised by individually-adapted and differentiated programmes of study. Teachers' lack of expertise on differentiation and individual adaptation of classroom teaching may lead to pupils receiving special educational needs.

Author and Title - Wormnæs, S. (1997): *Kvalitet i skolehverdagen til elever med bevegelsesvansker* (Quality in the school days of pupils with limited mobility).

Publication Details - Project report *Kvalitet i spesialpedagogisk arbeid - et paraplyprosjekt* (Quality in special education work – an umbrella project) – report no. 9/97.

Language - Norwegian.

Country of Origin - Norway.

Type of Research - Qualitative.

Methodology - The project's goal was to find out what school and teachers are doing for pupils with limited mobility, and to identify the expectations, perceptions and experience pupils, their guardians and teachers have of the school day of pupils with limited mobility. The project had two goals: 1) To chart how children with limited mobility and their parents and teachers experience and perceive the school day in order to shed light on and review issues that these actors believe are of importance in order to give them the best school day possible. 2) To chart some of the issues that enable pupils with limited mobility to learn, be socialised, be happy and develop on a personal level.

Sample - The study's population was primary and lower secondary school pupils in Telemark county with limited mobility. The statistics for this county showed some 40 children with such disabilities. At the beginning of the umbrella project, a questionnaire was sent to all of the schools that formed the basis for the sample in some of the sub-projects. The responses indicated that there were 34 pupils with limited mobility. The ones with serious problems communicating and/or physical disability were omitted from the sample because the focus was on the adaptation of schooling for pupils with limited motor skills. All year 4 and 7 pupils were included in the sample, making up a total of 13 pupils.

Method of Research - Interview – a combination of an ethnographically-inspired interview method and semi-structured interviews.

Main Findings - The study's results identified several key areas, which the informants believed needed emphasis in the school day.

- *A sense of coping* and development of an environment where pupils respected and included each other in all school activities were viewed as very important.

- *Social relations* was considered very important. At the lower secondary school level there was less physical activity during recess and pupils spoke with each other more, and pupils with limited mobility were less excluded and had greater social relations with the other pupils than at primary school.

- *Enjoyment* showed that most pupils with limited mobility appeared to be happy, but teachers stated that they were more touchy than other pupils. This was linked to a sense of not being able to do the same things the others did, and being different.

- *Adapted education in the classroom* – it appeared that most schools choose organisational models where pupils' needs are not identified to a great extent. The choice of models showed little sign of being linked to pupils' different needs.

- *Individual curricula* – the way these were developed for these pupils differed. This may be due to pupils not necessarily having learning disabilities, but perhaps to a greater extent needing technical aids and practical help.
- *Computers* were only used by two pupils, and their use was not integrated with the rest of the teaching. This was quite conspicuous, considering the fact that this is a good tool for pupils with limited mobility.

Evaluative Commentary - A main conclusion of this study was that there appears to be a need for more expertise, awareness and discussions regarding how different measures can promote or inhibit pupils' social integration. The building of a self-image and relationship-building have proven to be key to developing good classroom practice. The 'normalisation' of a physical disability can lead to it becoming invisible. The ambivalence between that which is the same and that which is different needs to be made clear.

Author and Title - Rognhaug, B. (1997): *Kvalitet i opplæring av elever med psykisk utviklingshemming* (Quality in the schooling of physically-disabled pupils).

Publication Details - Project report *Kvalitet i spesialpedagogisk arbeid - et paraplyprosjekt* (Quality in special education work – an umbrella project) – report no. 10/97.

Language - Norwegian.

Country of Origin - Norway.

Type of Research - Qualitative.

Methodology - The study's purpose was to draw on Gunzburg's studies, which assert that schooling must be placed in a life perspective, and examine the following areas of education:

- communication
- self-help functions
- social skills
- employment.

The basis for descriptions and analyses in this study drew on Gunzburg's studies (1973) on the schooling of physically-disabled pupils. Gunzburg particularly focused on the content of schooling, and his schooling goals formed the basis for the data collection. The methods used to implement educational measures are as important as the content. The TEACCH method (Intervention and Education of Autistic and Communication Handicapped Children), a methodical approach developed for autistic children and children with communications disabilities, is also used for physically-disabled pupils to an increasing extent. The TEACCH method was used for two of the pupils covered by this study.

Sample - Three pupil cases formed the starting-point for this survey. There was no way to obtain an overview of categories of pupils in the GSI primary and lower secondary school database, as pupils are not grouped in this database according to physical disability/learning disabilities. At the beginning of the umbrella project, a screening survey was sent to all of the schools that formed the basis for the sample in some of the sub-projects. The results of this screening gave an overview of all of the physically disabled pupils in the county (Telemark) where the study was conducted. In collaboration with the National Education Office, the Educational and Psychological Counselling Service and the headmasters in Telemark county, an overview of the good examples was obtained, but a list was not drawn up of the criteria for good examples. When the sample became too large to conduct case studies, five cases were randomly selected. Two led to rejection. This left three schools that participated with a total of three pupil cases. The education of these three pupils was assessed as qualitatively good as a basis for a phenomenological study of the educational situation of physically-disabled pupils.

Method of Research - Case study.

Main Findings - The results of this study indicate that the lesser the degree of physical disability, the greater the opportunity to adapt within the central framework,

and in accordance with the majority of the class. The greater the degree of physical disability, the greater the need for schooling that is based on other educational goals than those found in the Reform 97 framework, and the academic work in class. In this context, this is a matter of content and methods that address a perspective where education will have a functional value in a life context.

Evaluative Commentary - Including pupils with special needs usually has to do with following the central curriculum for the subject, along the same lines as the other pupils. This study shows that if maturity and the level of learning are far below the class average, there will be another form of inclusion than that needed by the majority of students.

Author and Title - Nilsen, S (1993): *Undervisningstilpasning i grunnskolen - fra intensjon til praksis* (Adapting education in primary and lower secondary school – from intention to practice).

Publication Details - University of Oslo, Department of Special Needs Education, Doctoral thesis in Special Needs Education (dr. scient), 1993.

Language - Norwegian.

Country of Origin - Norway.

Type of Research - Qualitative

Methodology - The main topic of this research was the adaptation of teaching in ordinary primary and lower secondary school, according to pupils' abilities and skills (adaptation of education). This issue was examined, both in terms of adaptation of general teaching and special needs teaching, and analysed on both the level of intention and practice. The variation in practical adaptation of teaching was further examined in relation to attitude factors in teachers and their perceptions of different context and framework conditions.

Sample - Class teachers were chosen as the informant group because they were best able to provide information about both the class and individual students' teaching, so that it was possible to link the information.

Method of Research - A source-analytical and descriptive-analytical study. The data in the descriptive-analytical study was collected using two surveys of class head teachers:

- survey on adaptation of teaching in the class
- survey on special education for individual pupils, with extra classes.

Main Findings - The results of the study showed a main pattern in the teachers' attitude profile and that the degree of adaptation of general teaching is associated with it. The main pattern had the following characteristics:

- high support for the intention of adapted education
- high confidence in the implementation and feasibility of the intention
- positive attitude towards care
- positive attitude towards integration/inclusion.

The results showed that a large majority of teachers agreed with the intentions that have been drawn up. The teachers feel that they are under an obligation to follow them up in their teaching. At the same time they believe that it is only possible to implement them to a certain extent, and this results in no changes being made to their form of teaching. Disagreeing with the intention of inclusion may be an obstacle to changing practice.

Evaluative Commentary - The result showed that even though teachers have the right attitude, teaching practice will not necessarily change. The study concluded that teacher attitudes are of importance in order to implement inclusive education, but it is not enough for them to have the right attitude in order to change practices.

Author and Title - Nilsen, S. (1997): *Individuelle opplæringsplaner - redskap for kvalitet i spesialpedagogisk arbeid* (Individual curricula – tools for quality in work with special needs education).

Publication Details - Project report *Kvalitet i spesialpedagogisk arbeid - et paraplyprosjekt* (Quality in work with special needs education – an umbrella project) – final report, chap. 6, pp. 97-112.

Language - Norwegian.

Country of Origin - Norway.

Type of Research - Quantitative & Qualitative.

Methodology - The study's purpose was to examine three areas in the work with an individual curriculum (IC). The one area was the propagation and occurrences of ICs. The other area was IC content. The third area was the teachers' experiences with the use of ICs in their work and their assessment of the utility.

Sample - Data was collected through two surveys. A shared screening survey, covering primary and lower secondary school in Telemark county, was conducted as part of the total umbrella project. Using a questionnaire, data was collected on how schools draw up and use ICs, local curricula and class curricula. The data collection covered the 1995-1996 academic year, and was conducted in the early spring of 1996. Responses were obtained from 139 schools in Telemark county (i.e. 90 % of the 150 primary and lower secondary schools in the county). A separate post-survey was conducted, as part of this sub-project, using the county's school institutions. Responses were received from all of the county's 18 municipalities. In order to benefit from teachers' experiences with ICs, interviews were the method used. The interviews were conducted in the spring of 1997, and informants were selected, using information that was obtained during the first screening study.

Method of Research - Questionnaire and interviews.

Main Findings - The results can be summed up with the following main points:

- ICs can contribute to a pupil's individual needs being given greater emphasis, to teaching consciously being based on knowledge of the pupil's skills and abilities – both resources and difficulties – and adapted to this basis.
- When the IC is compared to the class curriculum, it can contribute to both inclusion and differentiation, so that the pupils' curriculum is adapted within the framework of the class.
- The use of such curricula can contribute to an ongoing and systematic assessment of the pupil's development and the training he/she receives, and provide a basis for adjusting actions and programmes.

Evaluative Commentary - The results showed that teachers of pupils with special educational needs who participate in the process of developing an IC, promote shared reflection and contribute to a shared information basis and shared attitudes and strategies. This in turn contributes to consistency in education and thus to greater unity in terms of the pupil's total curriculum.

Appendix J: SPAIN

Author and Title - Antonio M^a López Ocaña and Manuel Zafra Jiménez: *La atención a la diversidad en la E.S.O. Una propuesta posible*. [Attention to diversity in Obligatory High School Education. One possible proposal].

Publication Details - Granada's IDEAL Newspaper, Education section devoted to ATTENTION TO DIVERSITY. April, Tuesday 24, 2001.

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- Comprensividad y enseñanza personalizada en educación secundaria [Comprehensiveness and personalised teaching in high school]. Department of Education and Science. Council of Andalusia. February, 1994.
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Language - Spanish (Castilian).

Country of Origin - Spain.

Type of Research - Attention to diversity and integration of ethnic minorities and school populations at social risk.

Methodology - Approach through significant curricular adaptation and a centre project based on co-existence values.

Sample - 200 students at “Fernando de los Ríos” High School Institute, in Fuente Vaqueros, Granada, Spain.

Main Findings – The application of the *Attention to Diversity Programme* allows for higher and better levels of integration and school success in marginal and socially deprived populations.

Evaluative Commentary - The *Attention to Diversity Programme* referred to here has been applied to three courses with almost half of the school population in the centre. It requires a flexible implementation of organisation, spaces, timing, methodology and evaluation. They all have a remarkable educational character. During the execution of this experience a marked decrease in school absenteeism, desertion and failure was observed.

Author and Title - Emilio Sáez Ros et al: *Un aula de audición y lenguaje en un centro de secundaria. La escolarización preferente de deficientes auditivos* [A class for hearing and language in a high school centre. Preference schooling for the auditory impaired].

Publication Details -10th Anniversary of the Integration of the Auditory Impaired. Alhambra High School Institute, 1990-2000. Edited by the Teacher Education Centre of Granada. ISBN: 84-8144-204-6.

Language - Spanish (Castilian).

Country of Origin - Spain.

Type of Research - Educational innovation experience for the integration of auditory impaired students in high school.

Methodology - Adjustment of the centre's curricular project and classes' programming. Use of sign language interpreters for bilingual education cases.

Sample - Auditory impaired students schooled in the Alhambra High School Institute.

Main findings - The use of educational reinforcement measures, curricular adaptation and complementary support, together with the use of Spanish sign language, contributed to enhance the quality of the educational attention and the performance of impaired students, increasing the percentage of students achieving a basic high school qualification and entering the university.

Evaluative Commentary - This experience started in 1990 and is still running today due to its high level of revenue for the educational community.

The Department of Education and Science supports this experience with human and material resources.

Author and Title - Pere Alzina Seguí. *Treballar amb la diversitat: nous enfocaments curriculars i metodològics* [Working with diversity: our curricular and methodological approach].

Publication Details - Universitat de les Illes Balears. Servei de publicacions i intercanvi científic. Cas Jai amb col·laboració amb l'Institut d'Àlaior i Institut Menorquí d'estudis. [University of the Balearic Islands. Scientific Exchange and Publication Service. Cas Jai in co-operation with the Menorquian Institute for Studies.] Palma de Mallorca.

Language - Catalan.

Country of Origin - Spain.

Type of Research - Qualitative research (action research paradigm); bibliographic study and discussion of the research results.

Methodology - Co-design (students and teachers) of a research process or work project in a compulsory High School second year students' class, with a reduced ratio (17 students per class). The project has been organised following the directives stated by the theory of Teaching for Comprehension. Thus, the generating topics were designed (subjects approached from a global point of view, capable of generating curiosity, interest and motivation).

Sample - The project was carried out in a compulsory High School second year class in the Josep Miquel Guardia d'Àlaior Institute, in a town of 7,000 inhabitants, with traditional industry and a growing tourism services sector. Thanks to the voluntary increase of teachers' working hours, the number of students per class has been reduced (from three to five groups in second year, 17 students per class, including those with special educational needs). The class included two girls with special educational needs (one presenting Down syndrome, and another one multi-impaired, hearing and language impaired), one immigrant from Maghreb, two students with a highly conflictual family situation and one student with severe learning difficulties.

Main findings - High school education should re-consider the sense of curriculum, timing and spacing. The National curriculum is not a valid solution and the current rigidity as to spacing and timing makes it difficult or impossible to include seriously impaired students in the classrooms.

- Changing the curriculum is possible if students are listened to with attention, and if knowledge is built out of their questions, interests, curiosity and needs.
- The combination of various different support for access to information facilitates the comprehension of phenomena considered.
- It is necessary to start from real and complex situations that involve the development and use of many skills and several learning processes: writing, reading, comprehension, analysis, comparison, according to the requirements of the designed project.
- A caring relationship between teachers and students is very important in open activities, where everything has to be made concrete and previously discussed.

- The over-arching nature of contents in the different areas means the beginning of the end for parcelled and simplistic statements of the classical scientific disciplines.

Working from generative topics and relevant fundamental questions gives sense to practice and work in the classroom; children understand the sense of the teaching work if faced with real, familiar, up-to-date and potentially interesting tasks.

Evaluative Commentary – If children from different origins, with different interests and motivations, are included in a class; if people from different cultures, or seriously impaired people (among them, one who cannot follow any contents corresponding to the course of reference at all), and children with social and family problems, or with important emotional problems that prevent them from learning, are included in a class, it is impossible to work with a closed curriculum or with text books, when there is a child that cannot even read and write. If we mean to work from the principles of inclusion, how can we work with a textbook or a closed curriculum, if we have children in the class whose impairment does not allow them to read, write, listen or speak? Working on the basis of wide-open and flexible projects is a must.

- The inclusive work plan of projects is not easy, and it implies organising the class according to flexible criteria, and working out resolutions to conflicts generated by the co-existence of such different people.
- A high degree of optimism and good organisation skills, capable of supporting autonomy and co-operative work in students, are required.
- This experience cannot be easily generalised: it involves abandoning the official curriculum or making it flexible in important core topics with guidelines capable of promoting understanding.

Author and Title - Antoni Navarro Calabuig, Tomás Martínez García: *Un Mundo de Silencio [A World of Silence]*.

Publication Details - Support video to explain the experience of integration of auditory impaired students in high school. ISBN 84-8498-816-3.

Language - Spanish (Castilian).

Country of Origin - Spain.

Type of Research - Compilation of the adaptation process in a high school centre, of teacher education studies regarding integration and intervention of auditory impaired students, explanation of the experience and results.

Sample - Students with different degrees of auditory impairment starting the 1991-92 course.

Main findings - The development of support measures to the learning-teaching process necessarily involves the organisational reconstruction of the institution itself. This means not only teachers of the different disciplines will be involved, but also, together with them, other professionals come onto the scene (psycho-pedagogists, visiting teachers, therapeutic pedagogy teachers, language therapists, etc), that will have a direct responsibility in the support tasks.

Students presenting special educational needs in the ordinary educational setting, require adequate response mechanisms. Nevertheless, the type and methods of these responses will depend, on one hand, on the level and complexity of the educational needs, and on the other hand, on the professional and personal abilities and skills of the school community. Through this video, the process of education for students with special educational needs and the need for training of the teachers involved is shown.

This experience highlights the starting point for intervention for diversity, as well as the motivation of the staff as a key element to overcoming the difficulties arising at the beginning, when including these students in schools, and to creating a culture of centres in which intervention for diversity is one of the defining elements of the centre's Educational Project, overcoming the general problems generated by this situation, such as:

- No team working habit amongst the staff.
- Information and education required to work with these kinds of students.
- Agreement between the working team and the Administration providing guidelines for: objectives, contents, assessment, etc.
- Adequate decisions that match the organisational reality of a given centre.

Evaluative commentary - This video has had positive results, proving that through co-operative work, engaging the centre's staff and the different departments, the problems generated by the support needs of students presenting special educational needs can be overcome.

On the other hand it served as a source of practical experience prior to the adaptation to the General Regulation Law for the Educational System this centre had to make (former Professional Development High School Institute).

This lead to establishing working guidelines for the different professionals involved - particularly for those included in the new educational system such as psycho-pedagogists, tutors, teachers of therapeutic pedagogy, hearing and language teachers, etc – and finally, creating awareness and promoting adaptation in the educational community towards support for diversity.

Author and Title - Hernández Ros, J.; Berrocal Solano, C: *El I.E.S. Pedro Peñalver [Pedro Peñalver High School Institute] (El Algar. Murcia).*

Publication Details - *1st National Meeting for Attention to Diversity: Education and Immigration.* Town Hall of Elche, 2002, 211-217.

Language - Spanish (Castilian).

Country of Origin - Spain.

Type of Research - Action research. Experimental project for educational compensation.

Methodology - Intervention through Multicultural Grouping to assist socially and culturally handicapped students through group adaptation of curricula. Its flexible structure is similar to the Curricular Diversification Programme, and its organisation is a symbiosis between primary and high school.

Sample - 36 students: 12 from Obligatory High School 1st year and 14 from the 2nd year.

Main Findings - Working with smaller groups has increased the students' self-confidence and has supported intercultural enrichment. As to the area of language, students have improved comprehension and oral expression; alphabetic students have learnt to read and write; the rest have achieved an acceptable expression level. The greater difficulty has arisen in the social science and natural science areas, in those students with a low level in Spanish. In mathematics they have all improved according to their own learning rhythm.

Evaluative Commentary - The Directorate and the staff have considered this grouping very positive: students have been supported according to their own needs; the atmosphere and spirit in the centre has improved; students are better integrated into the educational community, and the staff have been able to perform their teaching duties with fewer difficulties.

It has been possible to carry this work out through:

- the validation of the curriculum prepared in four levels of curricular competence,
- the use of new technologies in class as a tool for work,
- the creation of multicultural grouping for educational compensation in Obligatory High School 3rd year,
- and the recognition on the part of the Educational Administration of groups as compensatory diversification.

These factors have positively supported the realisation of this experience, which is a model to develop in other centres.

Author and Title - Sánchez Naharro, J. A: *Informe sobre el funcionamiento de las “Aulas Taller de aprendizaje del español”* [Report on the operation of “Workshop classes to learn Spanish”]. Gerardo Molina High School Institute, Torre Pacheco (Murcia).

Publication Details - *1st National Meeting for Attention to Diversity: Education and Immigration*. Town Hall of Elche, 2002, 171-175.

Language - Spanish (Castilian).

Country of Origin - Spain.

Type of Research - Experimental project for educational compensation.

Methodology - Intervention in Workshop Classes organised in 5 levels:
1st Level: Teachers working in Workshop Classes. Scheduling and meetings;
2nd Level: Areas teaching Maghrebi students in their groups: curricular adaptation and meetings;
3rd Level: Departments that do not teach Maghrebi students directly. Support material and basic vocabulary. Meetings.
4th Level: With Maghrebi students. Tutorials, activities in the Centre, Gerardo Molina Intercultural Youth Association;
5th Level: Action with families: meetings with parents.

Sample – 26 students.

Main Findings - Working in workshop classes on learning Spanish as a second language supports the integration of foreign students.

Evaluative Commentary - This experience has highlighted that the work carried out in these classes improves the linguistic skills in students with a severe lack of knowledge of the Spanish language, and their integration in the centre and the environment as well. Also, it opens academic and professional opportunities for them and prevents co-existence issues.

Author and Title - Arnaiz, P.; De Haro, R.; Navarro, J: *Learners' Diversity: the integration of Maghrebi children in mainstream classrooms in Spain.*

Publication Details - In K. Watson (Ed.): *Doing Comparative Education Research: Issues and problems* (p. 153-168). Oxford: Symposium Book. 2001.

Language - English.

Country of Origin - Spain.

Type of Research - Descriptive Study. The general objective is to describe, analyse and evaluate the progressive incorporation of Maghrebi children and the type of educational solutions provided to current cultural diversity in schools in the Murcia region.

Methodology - Data collected via semi-structured interviews with parents, teachers, school Directorate and students.

Sample - Nine school centres located in areas with the highest presence of foreign immigrant students.

Main Findings - Educational reality is not observed from the same viewpoint by the Directorate, teaching staff, Maghrebi students and parents. Centres try to project themselves as operating within a normal situation, which makes the "multicultural problem" provide an obvious answer in these centres: problems are reduced to the lack of knowledge of Spanish as a second language and the lack of tutors that are responsible for these students. Another pending matter is family-centred relationships.

Evaluative Commentary - Our obligation as teachers is to demonstrate the acceptance, awareness of and valuation of cultural differences in the same educational space or - which is in fact the same - to build a democratic, plural and equitable society that respects the individual identity of each student at all times.

Author and Title - Arnaiz, P.; Castejón, J.L.; Garrido Gil, C.F.; Rojo Martínez, A: *Evaluación del cambio de actitud del profesorado tras su participación en un programmea de atención a la diversidad* [Evaluation of change in the teaching staff's attitude after participating in an Attention to Diversity Programme].

Publication Details - *Revista de Enseñanza* [Teaching Magazine], 17-18. 309-324. 1999-2000.

Language - Spanish (Castilian).

Country of Origin - Spain

Type of Research -This article introduces the results of research work conducted in primary school and high school centres. The objective of the project was to study whether there were changes in the teaching staff's attitude towards diversity, in both educational levels, after participating in an educational programme. The objectives of such a programme were to help the staff to understand, in a different way, the special educational needs present in their classes and provide them with the opportunity to work in teams.

Methodology – The research attempted to identify change in the staff's attitude towards attention to diversity, after participating in a programme for an in-service education (UNESCO) project. Once the centres had been selected, organisational and educational dynamics was defined, which governed the design, implementation and evaluation of the project, the operating structure of the centre itself and the structure of external support to the centre.

3 phases were set for the two courses the project implemented:

1. Knowledge of the UNESCO Project and the package of work units involved, through discussion and analysis of them. Decision making regarding the unit/units to be executed and their design.
2. Application of the didactical activities designed.
3. Follow up and evaluation of the actions performed.

Sample - 24 teachers belonging to two centres.

Main Findings - The results point out the beneficial effect of the teaching staff's participation in the educational experience carried out.

Evaluative Commentary - The evaluation of the change produced by the staff's participation in this experience highlights a certain improvement in the perception of change in both centres. This fact highlights the staff's trend to change attitudes and educational practices in favour of attention to diversity. Also, it shows that attention to diversity in a centre is not an exclusive task of some of the teachers, but it demands a generalised change in educational practices and co-operative work processes on the part of the teaching staff as a whole, to perform a profound transformation of the centres' curricular and organisational framework.

Author and Title - Cambra Vergés, C: *Procesos de composición de textos narrativos escritos por alumnos sordos* [Processes of composition of narrative texts written by deaf students].

Publication Details - Rev. Lop., Fon., Audiol., vol XIV, nº 2 (96-101), 1994.

Language - Spanish (Castilian).

Country of Origin - Spain.

Type of Research - Action research.

Methodology - Firstly, a psycho-linguistic evaluation was conducted, then, a pre-test for reading comprehension and written production, and finally, the intervention was conducted.

Sample - Two groups of 11 pre-locution profoundly deaf adolescents integrated in public centres: one experimental group and one control group.

Main Findings - The main conclusion is the need to apply a specific educational programme for the deaf student to improve the production of written texts process in the school context, not only to improve narrative but also to improve enjoyment in writing.

Evaluative Commentary - The most positive results in this research work were those in which the teacher applied a greater diversity of communication strategies when having to intervene in order to address the problems presented by deaf student completing the exercises.

This research work clearly details the whole procedure conducted.

Author and Title - Silvestre Benach, N: *Las interacciones entre profesor y adolescente sordo profundo integrado en el aula regular con oyentes (1)* [Interaction between the teacher and the profound deaf adolescent in a regular class with hearing students (1)].

Publication Details - Re. Logop. Fon., Audiol., vol II., n° 3 (170-171), 1991.

Language - Spanish (Castilian).

Country of Origin - Spain.

Type of Research - Action research with statistical study.

Methodology - Consideration of curricular adaptations and, in particular, those regarding linguistic modifications. It is a mainly descriptive study about the interaction between the deaf student and the teacher in an ordinary class.

Sample - 11 classes in ordinary schools within the Obligatory High School system, with students 12-17 years of age. Students presenting a profound deafness of about 90 dB.

Main Findings - Interaction between the teacher and the deaf student depends mainly on the aims of the communication and the verbal form used.

Evaluative Commentary - The general hypothesis of this work is that among all the adaptations performed according to the communicational abilities of the deaf student, some are absolutely necessary for communication to occur, optimum material conditions for lip reading, etc, but there are others that may happen to be barely adequate or even restrictive for the development of their linguistic abilities.

The study introduced in this article is part of a wider research work sponsored by the DIGYT under #PB87-0619.

Author and Title - García Fernández, J. M. y Pérez Cobacho, J: *El niño con déficit auditivo en el aula* [The auditory impaired child in class] Chapters 9, 10 and 13.

Publication Details - DM (Diego Marín- Librero Editor) 2001.

Language - Spanish.

Country of Origin - Spain.

Methodology - Inclusion in an ordinary centre. Individually adapting the ordinary curriculum to each student, according to the level of development of his/her language as a consequence of the hearing loss s/he presents.

Sample - Hearing impaired students in Obligatory High School and College.

Main Findings - This book's objective is to make an estimation of the world of auditory impairment, focusing on the evolutionary development of deaf people as well as on their educational opportunities and the current procedures for intervention.

Evaluative Commentary - This publication is the result of the collaborative work of various professionals: teachers, psychologists, therapeutic pedagogy teachers, deaf language interpreters, etc, with a wide experience in auditory impairment.

The selection of chapters 9, 10 and 13 is based on the fact that they are direct experiences of the application of computers in class, of Individual Curricular Adaptations and of an educational experience of integration in the Virgen del Remedio High School Institute, in Alicante. In order to give the book an educational tool feature, each chapter includes a short self-evaluation test at the end, which helps the reader focus on follow up that improves understanding and access to this unknown world of the deaf, as well.

Author and Title - 1st National Congress on Auditory Impairment: *Un camino hacia la igualdad* [A way to equity] (Lectures 2 and 3, pages 13-25).

Publication Details - APANAH [Association for Parents and Friends of Auditory Impaired Children and Adolescents] Elda, March 24th and 25th, 2000.

Language - Spanish (Castilian).

Country of Origin - Spain.

Type of Research - Action research.

Sample - Primary school students from Pedagogy Notebooks #256, Madrid, and Obligatory High School education students from Virgen del Remedio High School Institute, in Alicante.

Main Findings - It is necessary to promote a culture of respect for diversity, a structure with a representation of all the actors included in the educational community. Thus, it is necessary to have the resources and organisation in the centre to accomplish a true inclusion of hearing impaired students, both in the class and in the whole centre, as well as in society generally.

Evaluative Commentary - The objective of this Congress was to generate information, to open ways for integrative goals. In addition, it aimed to approach integration from the employment, educational, family and health sectors, thus enabling the creation of a space for consideration and thoughtfulness.

The selection of these two lectures is due to the fact that they are considered as being within the educational profile and that they focus upon a school model according to the individual educational need of each student.

Author and Title - Figueras Pacheco High School Institute (Alicante) Department of Orientation *Integración de alumnos con necesidades educativas especiales* [Integration of students with special educational needs].

Publication Details - Project conducted during 1996-1997.

Language - Spanish (Castilian).

Country of Origin - Spain.

Type of Research - Considerations of the educational practice with deaf and blind students.

Methodology - Theoretical essay about sensory impairments:

- Case studies of students
- Developing the framework document to make curricular adaptations.

Sample - Blind and deaf students attending the centre.

Main Findings - Every teacher can have students with these problems in their class, so they should have a basis to start working from. It is important that teachers have: methodological possibilities available, communication strategies, and opportunities to share models about educational practice with these students with their colleagues. These factors are more important than supplying them with “a direct and real method” to use with their students. This last idea is useless, as there are no identical deaf students and not all of them respond alike in all areas.

Evaluative Commentary - This project was useful for bringing the teaching staff closer to global provision for diversity and in particular, to the integration of students with SEN.

Not every participating teacher started from the same situation, as some of them did not have integrated students in their classes. Those who did have them, understood more clearly the sense and cope of the contents discussed, as they could compare contents with their teaching practice.

The Individual Document for Curricular Adaptation developed is very comprehensive material, very helpful for decision making on how to intervene with students with SEN.

Appendix K: SWEDEN

Author and Title - Inger Eriksson: Särskolelever i vanliga grundskoleklasser.

Publication Details - Pedagogiska-psykologiska problem Nr 649, ISSN 0346-5004. 1998. Institutionen för pedagogik. Lärarhögskolan. Malmö högskola.

Language - Swedish.

Country of Origin - Sweden.

Type of Research - Qualitative.

Methodology - Pedagogical circumstances and social situations for included pupils with cognitive disability were studied. The study was based on observations in 11 classrooms in grade 1, 2, 4, 5, 7 and 8 and on interviews with class teacher and special teacher in these grades. The main part of the results are presented as descriptions of the eleven classrooms, so called situations of inclusion.

Sample - 17 pupils with cognitive disability in eleven classrooms.

Method of Research - Observations and interviews.

Main Findings - Co-operation between class teacher and special teacher is important.

It is not more difficult to include older than younger pupils. If the pupil often spends time outside the classroom, inclusion is difficult to achieve. The support given outside the classroom might give the pupil knowledge and self-confidence, but in the study it is shown that this support cannot compensate for the drawbacks of being away from the class. Inclusion depends very much on the pupil's abilities to fully participate in the class. There is a mutual influence between class, teacher and pupil with disability. What helps pupils with disability in education also helps other pupils.

Evaluative Commentary - A small study, no general conclusions can be drawn from the study.

Author and Title - Helena Hemmingsson: Student – Environment Fit for Students with Physical Disabilities.

Publication Details - Doctoral thesis. From the Department of Clinical Neuroscience, Occupational Therapy and Elderly Research, Division of Occupational Therapy.

Language - English.

Country of Origin - Sweden.

Type of Research - Quantitative and Qualitative.

Methodology - Non-parametric methodology; a comparative and explorative study in the hermeneutic tradition. Five minor studies.

Sample – In total 89 students with physical disability across all five studies.

Method of Research - Statistic scale, coding, interviews, semi-structured field observations.

Main Findings - Study III: The need for adjustments for students in upper secondary schools is mostly encountered in association with writing in the classroom, with homework and assistance. Older pupils experienced significantly more barriers in school than younger ones even though they have the same level of access to an assistant. Analyses indicate that school organisation seems to be less favourable in senior level and problems are not primarily related to diagnoses or level of mobility. Most improvements to promote participation of students with physical disability are to organise and carry out activities in schools.

Study IV: The study of temporal structures shows that different teaching styles in the classroom hinder or help these pupil's time-problems. Four teaching styles are identified: the conductor style, the dialogue style, the group-work style and the individual task style. Each style permits the pupil to participate in different ways. The conductor style is the most demanding for pupils with physical disability as it demands all pupils to keep to the same pace.

Study V: The last explorative study is about how the assistant influences participation. A very striking finding is that the pupils have limited influence in the assistance provided and little control over when and how support is given. The assistance is supposed to promote the pupils' participation in learning activities, but the pupils with disabilities often seem to prioritise social participation with peers.

Evaluative Commentary - The two last studies are of most interest for schooling. The study starts in a categorical perspective, but the result shows need of relational provision.

Author and Title - Inga-Lill Jakobsson: Diagnos i skolan. En studie av skolsituationer för elever med syndromdiagnos.

Publication Details - Doctoral thesis. Göteborg Studies in Education sciences 185. Acta Universitatis Gothoburgensis.2002.

Language - Swedish.

Country of Origin - Sweden.

Type of Research - A multi-disciplinary, co-operation research, taking advantage of knowledge from different disciplines, mainly special education and psycho medical syndrome-diagnoses.

Methodology - An ethnographic study.

Sample - 50 pupils with four different aetiological syndrome diagnoses. (The chosen syndromes were: 1. CDGS with symptoms during infancy and childhood as failure-to thrive, floppiness, growth retardation, severe psychomotor and mental developmental delay, stroke-like episodes, frequently occurring infections, weakness of legs and sometimes visual inattention and squinting. 2. FAS with signs as growth deficiency, psychical abnormalities and central nervous system dysfunction often resulting in learning disability, poor impulse control, deficits in language and mathematical skills and problems with social interaction, attention and judgement. 3. CATCH 22 with symptoms such as physical impairments, developmental delay in areas of cognition, speech and socialisation. This means difficulties in learning, speech, motor function, perception, attention, activity level, and social relations. 4. Turner's Syndrome pupils have an incomplete pubertal development, a particular neuro-cognitive profile with normally developed language abilities but impaired visual-spatial and/or visual/perceptual abilities. They often have difficulties in spatial ability causing mathematical, motor control, co-ordination, emotional, and social problems.) (Jakobsson, 2002, s 209).

Method of Research - Ethnographic strategies; observation, field notes, dialogues.

Main Findings - Pupils with syndrome-diagnoses interplay between the surrounding context, which makes it necessary to look at the entire school situation to grasp what happens in school. Societal ideology and regulations seem to influence mainly through local interpretations and decisions. Many groups co-operated around the pupil, parents often act as co-ordinators between institutions and activities. In this interplay the most important elements seem to be communication, personal relationships, and co-operation between various actors. The diagnoses as a guide in pedagogical questions seem to be limited.

Evaluative Commentary - Although starting in a categorical perspective, the study breaks established boundaries by doing an ethnographic study and discussing the complex interplay on different levels, a relational result.

Appendix L: SWITZERLAND

Author and Title - Bless, Gerard: *Einführung integrierter Unterrichtsformen für Schülerinnen und Schüler mit besonderen Bedürfnissen in den Ländern der OECD* (Introduction to Integrated Forms of Schooling for Students with Special Needs in OECD Countries).

Publication Details - SKBF 98:065.

Language - German and French.

Country of Origin - Switzerland.

Method of Research - Descriptive: analysis of documents, case studies.

Main Findings - Conditions for the introduction of integrative forms of schooling in Switzerland, causing no additional costs and not disturbing the usual instruction.

Factors inhibiting the implementation of integration in Switzerland:

- there is no unified political will
- parents interested in integration have difficulties being heard
- there is a strong special school lobby
- sluggish educational system with 26 independent cantonal education administrations
- structures of financing that have been conceived with segregation in mind.

Author and Title - Bürli, Alois: *Annäherungsversuche zwischen Regel- und Sonderpädagogik* (An Attempt to Unify Normal and Special Education).

Publication Details - Article in: Schweizerische Zeitschrift für Heilpädagogik, 10/2001, p. 13-21.

Language - German and French.

Country of Origin - Switzerland.

Type of Research - Descriptive article based on a number of research studies carried out in Switzerland across different levels of schooling.

Main Findings - The differences in performance between the divided and the integrated secondary I level are very slight and do not speak for one or the other system. The following disadvantages may be formulated very carefully:

- integrative secondary I level: unfavourable for the development of performance, since the system has levelling effects
- divided secondary I level: has demonstrable effects, specific to stratum and therefore little positive effect for social equalization

More important factors that affect pupil performance: quality of the school, attitudes of the teachers towards the pupils, school climate, and the support from the parental home.

Author and Title - Dozio, Edo: *Lebenshilfe in der Lehranstalt. Pädagogische Betreuung in den unteren Klassen der Sekundarstufe im Tessin* (Counseling in Schools: Educational Counseling in the Lower Classes of the Secondary Schools in Ticino).

Publication Details - Article in: *Psychoscope* 6/95, p. 11-13.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Switzerland.

Type of Research - Descriptive: qualitative data, case study.

Main Findings - State of the teaching profession in Ticino (in Italian-speaking Switzerland):

- difficult position of the school special education teachers
- great variety of possibilities for intervention raises questions
- attitude of teachers wishing to “heal” pupils
- support cannot guarantee the weeding out of deficient pupil performance, but it can offer many opportunities and contribute to the improvement of the general educational situation of pupils with SEN.

Author and Title - Fonds national suisse de la recherche scientifique FNS: Une scolarité intégrée apporte plus d'avantages.
Schweizerischer Nationalfonds: *Integratio in Regelklassen eher von Vorteil* (Integrated Students are at an Advantage).

Publication Details - Article in: Educateur (French) / Press release on the Internet (German).

Language - French and German.

Country of Origin - Switzerland

Type of Research - Descriptive article in a journal / Press release based upon a study at the University of Fribourg.

Main Findings - Students with SEN who spend their school careers in regular schools are better prepared for vocational life than those who are placed in special classes.

Author and Title - Leuthard, Martin: *Integrative Schulungsform an der Oberstufe: Bestandesaufnahme der Versuchserfahrungen* (Integrative Schooling at the Secondary Level: Current Status of the Test Experience).

Publication Details - Zurich, Erziehungsdirektion, Pädagogische Abteilung, Zurich, 1995a (first published in 1992).

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Switzerland.

Type of Research - State of the art report: qualitative data, interviews.

Sample - Teachers in seven integrative schools in Canton Zurich.

Main Findings - Problems with the introduction of integration at the secondary I level are seen to be:

- demarcation between changing/movable school types and learning groups
- probationary periods create unrest
- pupils with SEN already have a school biography with long-term stress and high expectation of failure
- problematic burdening of the support situation as a “catchall”.

General point - the basis of trust between teachers and pupils with SEN has a great effect upon the success of integration; integrative schooling makes it possible for pupils with SEN to remain in the regular classes, even if the learning goals are not achieved; co-operation among the teachers seems to be the central point in the organisation of scholastic support.

Author and Title - Leuthard, Martin: *Die integrative Schulungsform an der abteilungsübergreifenden Oberstufe. Erfahrungen der Versuchsgemeinden* (Integrative Schooling at the Interdisciplinary Secondary Level: Experience Gathered in Test Communes).

Publication Details - Department of Education of the Canton of Zurich, Zurich, 1995b.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Switzerland.

Methodology - Evaluation/Case Study: qualitative and quantitative data, interviews.

Sample - Seven integrative schools in Canton Zurich.

Main Findings - Prerequisites for a successful integrative schooling at the secondary I level:

- the broadest possible consensus among all the participants with regards to integrative schooling
- clearly defined roles and co-operative leadership ease collaboration and the mastering of common tasks
- care-planning must be regulated in a binding manner and be well supported
- all teachers in a school with integrative schooling must support this form of schooling
- as much instruction as possible in the regular classes and as little individual support as possible has a beneficial effect on the integration of pupils with SEN
- the school climate must be supportive for the pupils with SEN
- differentiated instruction is important, not only in the class but also in the various achievement groups.

Author and Title - Müller-Stump, Karin and Rossi Marty, Sandra: *Integration auf der Oberstufe. Begleitung eines Projekts* (Integration at the Secondary Level: Tracking a Project).

Publication Details - Edition SZH, Luzern, 1994.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Switzerland.

Methodology - Case study: tests, interviews.

Sample - Two classes in a school, 38 pupils, 10 of them pupils with SEN.

Main Findings - Framework conditions:

- all participants must support integration, good information is important here, as is public relations
- too much segregation through individual support prevents a good class-school climate
- differentiation in the classes is necessary
- support by special education teachers has better effects than "silent integration".

Teachers: the teachers involved must want to teach together, be capable of criticism, of being part of a team, and attain a high level of agreement regarding goals

Instruction:

- possibilities for flexible organisation must be guaranteed
- regular teachers must adapt their instruction.

Author and Title - Riedo, Dominicq: *“Ich war halt nie ein guter Schüler!” – Biographien und Berufslaufbahnen von ehemals schulleistungsschwachen Schülerinnen und Schülern* (“I was never a good student!” – Biographies and Vocational Careers of Former Students Who were Weak in School).

Publication Details - Student Thesis / Article in: Vierteljahresschrift für Heilpädagogik, 4/1999, 427-441.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Switzerland.

Type of Research - Long-term study: narrative interviews, study of biographies.

Sample - 68 young adults.

Main Findings – The social dimension is most important: negative experiences have implications for the entire life, positive experiences (e.g. good relationships with teachers) lead to the development of a strong social environment (friends and relationships).

Didactic dimension: supportive and committed leadership, individual teaching/learning methods, and definite but adapted performance conditions are positively valued.

Individual dimension: the people questioned were well-disposed towards their learning difficulties and critically scrutinize their denial of achievement.

Institutional dimension: on the one hand, this is not a central theme by the pupils with SEN who were schooled in integrated settings, on the other hand, this is viewed as restrictive by pupils from special schools.

Author and Title - Siegen, Josef: *Schulorganisation und Schülerbefindlichkeit auf der Sekundarstufe I* (School Organization and the State of School Children at the Secondary I Level).

Publication Details - Student Thesis / SKBF 1/96/31.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Switzerland.

Type of Research - Survey: standardized questionnaire.

Sample - 940 pupils.

Main Findings - There is no difference in the special subjects between the divided and the integrated secondary I level, although the pupils with SEN feel more accepted in the integrative school form of schooling than their colleagues in the segregated school form.

Author and Title - Steiner, Hans: *Integration und Förderung von IKK-Schüler in der Oberstufe am Beispiel der Schulgemeinden Obersaxen, Lugnez und Vals* (Integration and Furthering of IKK Pupils in the Secondary Level using Examples from the Schools of Obersaxen, Lugnez, and Vals).

Publication Details - Student thesis.

Language - German.

Country of Origin - Switzerland.

Type of Research - Case studies: document analysis, interviews and questionnaire.

Sample - Three special education teachers, five pupils, four regular teachers (Realschule - secondary school with modern curriculum)

Main Findings - Social, emotional, and performance-motivational integration appears to function in the schools investigated, even when specific limits are apparent:

- the pupils with SEN are overburdened to some extent
- teachers find too little space for individual support
- the integrated pupils with mental disabilities all have to change to a special school in the course of their time at school.

Need for action is seen primarily at the level of the teachers: differentiated instruction, co-operation, mutual support, clear attitude in favour of integration needs to be improved and developed.